

CROSS-BORDER CONTROL OF PRIORITY COMMUNICABLE DISEASES IN SEA REGION OF WHO:

LOOKING BACK, LOOKING AHEAD

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**Agreement for Performance of Work with
World Health Organization and Centre for Development and Policy Practice (CDPP),
Hyderabad, India**

Terms of Reference and Budget

Background:

Cross-border Control of Priority Communicable Diseases in SEA Region of WHO: Looking Back, Looking Ahead

Several countries in the South East Asia Region (SEAR) of the WHO share borders with one another, and at times with more than one country. India, for example shares its land borders with four countries of the Region viz. Nepal, Bhutan, Bangladesh and Myanmar. Diseases do not respect political borders and diseases travel with humans, animals, insects, and environmental route. People move between borders legally and illegally for various reasons viz. political, conflict, economic, employment, education, pilgrimage, tourism voluntarily and even against their will like human trafficking. Diseases like malaria, tuberculosis (TB), visceral leishmaniasis (Kala-azar), HIV, Japanese encephalitis have been highlighted as diseases of public health concern.

South-East Asia Regional Office of the WHO has been alive to this problem and has taken initiatives since mid-1990s. The Health Ministers of these countries have expressed their concern and flagged as an issue for the WHO to initiate collaborative measures for cross border control of communicable diseases. The main purpose of cross border collaboration is to ensure health care access to people of these countries living in the border districts or crossing the border and ensure treatment regardless of their nationality or legal status. During the last 25 years SEARO/WHO has organized several rounds of consultations, discussions not only within the countries of the region but also with countries of Western Pacific Region as well to share experiences of cross border communicable diseases control. During the period SEARO/WHO has facilitated development of joint strategies, action plans, and funded pilot projects. The need for control of priority communicable diseases across borders has been amplified with new and emerging infections flaring up in the region, destructive impact of climate change, enhanced migration including from conflict areas, and vulnerable health systems in the area.

An effective programme to prevent and control communicable diseases, in border areas is a regional public good, and would provide better health security for populations in the countries. Twenty-five years of this initiative is an opportune time to look back and look ahead. It is proposed to do a rapid review and suggest possible areas for action, if needed.

Terms of Reference

The review would include, but not limited to:

1. Mapping of organizations involved in cross-border work (including, but not limited to UN organizations like IOM, UNHCR, and other NGOs); review data and literature on social and associated epidemiological impact on border regions of the countries concerned. Create a repository on the subject
2. Assess regional communicable disease control policies and programs (including inclusion/exclusion policies of non-nationals in the packages and/or health insurance schemes for coverage of infectious diseases, and restrictions on entry, stay or residence for foreign nationals based on HIV status). Bring out their strong points and areas that need strengthening. Identify lessons learned from other cross-border communicable disease control initiatives including beyond the SEAR.

3. Underscore and understand the barriers, in cooperation and collaboration between countries for cross-border communicable disease control, across departments and ministries, including country policies
4. Study cost benefit analyses of various interventions, if available, to highlight the economic costs that region pays for not controlling these diseases across borders

Methods and descriptions of the tasks/process:

The following will be done by the contractual partner:

- i. Secondary research for publications, policy papers, meeting reports etc.;
- ii. Interactions with individuals, organizations etc.
- iii. Write a report and provide recommendations.

Deliverables:

1. Recommendations (short and long-term) to synergize the work of various partners working with different programmes and steps WHO can take to ensure their alignment with WHO guidance.
2. Framework for a sustainable action plan which includes political buy-in.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ACF	Active Case Finding
AFP	Acute Flaccid Paralysis
AIDS	Acquired Immunodeficiency syndrome
AMW	Auxiliary Midwives
ANM	Auxiliary Nurse Midwife
API	Annual Parasite Index
ART	Anti-retroviral Treatment
ASEAN	Association of Southeast Asian Nations
ATC	Access to Care
AYUSH	Ayurveda Yoga Unani Siddha Homeopathy
BBIN	Bangladesh, Bhutan, India and Nepal
BCC	Behaviour Change Communication
BCR	Benefit-Cost Ratio
BHS	Basic Health Service
BMGF	Bill Melinda Gates Foundation
BRAC	Bangladesh Rural Action Committee
BTC	Bodoland Territorial Council (BTC)
CBHI	Cross-Border Health Initiative
CBO	Community Based Organization
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
CEDAW	Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women
CGPP	CORE Group Polio Project
CHW	Community Health Workers
CL	Cutaneous Leishmaniasis
CLHIV	Children Living with HIV
CLMV	Cambodia Laos Myanmar Vietnam
CMW	Committee on Migrant Workers
DS-TB	Drug-susceptible TB
ECHR	European Court of Human Rights

EMPHASIS	Enhancing Mobile Population’s Access to HIV and AIDS Services, Information and Support
ERS	European Respiratory Society
FMR	Free Movement Regime
GAVI	Gates Alliance for Vaccines and Immunization
GFATM	Global Fund for HIV/AIDS, Tuberculosis, and Malaria
GMP	Global Malaria Programme
GMS	Greater Mekong Sub-region
GTS	Global Technical Strategy
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
HOA	Horn of Africa
ICCPR	International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights
ICDDR, B	International Centre for Diarrhoeal Disease Research, Bangladesh
ICMR	Indian Council of Medical Research
ICRMW	International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of their Families
IEC	Information, Education and Communication
IHR	International Health Regulation
ILO	International Labour Organisation
IOM	International Organization for Migration
IRS	Indoor Residual Spraying
IU	Implementation Units
KA	Kala-azar
LLIN	Long-Lasting Insecticidal Net
LSDI	Lubombo Spatial Development Initiative
LTBI	Latent TB Infection
MARPS	Most-At-Risk-Groups
MDG	Millenium Development Goals
MDR	Multi-Drug Resistance
MMPs	Migrants and Mobile Populations
MSDS	Migrant Service Delivery System
NACO	National AIDS Control Organization
NFME	National Framework for Malaria Elimination

NMCP	Myanmar National Malaria Control
NTD	Neglected Tropical Disease
NTP	National TB Control Programme
NVBDCP	National Vector Borne Disease Control
PATH	Program for Appropriate Technology in Health
PHC	Primary Health Center
PKDL	Post Kala-azar Dermal Leishmaniasis
PLHIV	People Living with HIV
RMRI	Rajendra Memorial Research Institute of Medical Sciences (India)
RR-TB	Rifampicin-Resistant Tuberculosis
SAARC	South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SEARO	South East Asia Regional Office
SPS	Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures
STAC	SAARC Tuberculosis and HIV/AIDS Centre
STI	Sexually Transmitted Infection
TBT	Technical Barriers to Trade
TI	Targeted Interventions
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNFPA	United Nations Fund for Population Activities
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UNICEF	United Nations Children's Fund
UNODC	United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
VBD	Vector-borne Diseases
VHS	Voluntary Health Staff
VL	Visceral Leishmaniasis
WHO	World Health Organization
WPV	Wild Polio Virus
WTO	World Trade Organization

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Southeast Asia Regional office of the WHO was far ahead of its times when it took initiative in mid-1990s for cross border control of priority communicable diseases (Malaria, Kala-azar, Tuberculosis and HIV) in Bangladesh, Bhutan, India and Nepal (BBIN). Adopting an integrated approach, pilot studies were done in districts on both sides of international border between India and these countries in 2002. An evaluation done after 2 years of implementation of these studies indicated that though joint strategies, action plans, were developed but the success in the pilot projects was limited. The level of commitments on all sides, and the follow-up actions were inadequate. Multi-sectoral and multi-partner involvement was insufficient. Utilization of inter-country mechanisms was weak. There was a mismatch between the expectations and the capacity of the health systems. These hinderances persist even in 2021.

This document takes a stock of the activities undertaken for cross border control of communicable diseases, experiences and lessons learnt in these countries, and proposes an action plan for future.

By the year 2000, the BBIN countries had signed up for Kala-azar elimination, lot of effort was put on decreasing the number of Kala-azar cases to reach elimination targets. Despite significant progress, the detection of new foci in districts not covered under the elimination programme, the increasing contribution PKDL cases in disease transmission, increasing number of cases from across the border are worrying. In malaria too, appreciable progress has been made towards elimination, but imported cases from across the border is delaying countries getting malaria-free status. Though in elimination strategies and action plans for Tuberculosis and HIV, migrants figure prominently, no evidence could be found on special efforts made in border districts. The document suggests that Myanmar should be added to the BBIN group as it shares a land border with India, there is unrestricted movement across the border, and Myanmar also has high burden of malaria, tuberculosis and HIV (Chapter 3 and 4). The entire sub-region can be considered as a single land mass for action. The document examines the policies and programmes for cross-border control of these diseases including access to healthcare for the migrant populations. An analysis of the barriers to accessing healthcare in the border districts indicate that poor access both in terms of physical access (reaching) and material access (tests, medicines, healthcare staff) is a hinderance. Qualitative research on experiences of migrants indicates that the absence of a government issued identity card is often the toughest hurdle to access public health services (Chapter 5). It looks at experiences of control of communicable diseases between various countries in the SEA Region and beyond, and identifies the lessons which could be adopted locally (Chapter 6). Data on the economic cost of not controlling these diseases (Chapter 7) could be used as an important convincing argument for the countries to invest in the control of these diseases. Cost-benefit studies of malaria elimination done for example in Fujian province, China, Sri Lanka, Malawi, Ghana, and of Kala-azar elimination in Nepal, provide a positive reference value and return on investments for other countries. Chapter 8 provides information on potential partners who could possibly be involved in cross-border control of diseases, and a stakeholder analysis based on level of influence and level of importance is presented for malaria and Kala-azar. Several partners have gained useful experience of cross-border coordination and collaboration. Some of the best practices for cross-border coordination have been identified for adoption. A review of these experiences also brings out that poor political leadership, inadequate financing, and less than optimum coordination between various partners not only within the national borders but even across them are major barriers. Once addressed these emerge as accelerators of the programme. It should be possible to develop specific approaches and strategies to engage with various stakeholders. Recommendations for improving coordination and collaboration between different stakeholders and how to synergize their work are provided in Chapter 9.

To improve coordination and create synergies between partners a short term strategy could be a bilateral approach where an MoU for cross-border collaboration between countries is reached to harmonize policies, synergize activities and to delineate the roles and responsibilities of each participating partners. A point person be identified in the SEARO as well as in the WHO Country offices to coordinate cross-border activities. In the medium term, a coordinating unit at the SEA Regional office (with appropriate support facilities including staff) be set-up for diseases nearer to the targets of elimination (malaria and Kala-azar). In the long term, since trans-border is a cross-cutting issue, the responsibilities of this coordinating unit be expanded to cover Tuberculosis, HIV, and other diseases as well.

Finally, in Chapter 10, a framework of a two-phased action plan for improving cross-border coordination is suggested. The aim of the action plan is to re-energize the activities for control of priority communicable diseases and put them on fast track. It consists of 4 arms: Political arm, Coordination arm, Technical arm, and an implementation arm. This plan is India centric. Not only because of high burden of these diseases, but also the leadership role that India is eager to play. India's vision for the Region is Security to All and Growth for All – is a reflection of its policy of inclusiveness, and its Neighbourhood First' Policy seeks to develop better relations with country's neighbours.

The political arm will have Prime Ministers (or equivalent) of all concerned countries, to be led by Indian Prime Minister bringing together health and non-health Ministries and Departments to improve coordination. Reasons for suggesting that the political arm be housed in BIMSTEC are elaborated. The technical support to countries and coordination between countries can best be provided by SEA Regional office of the WHO, for which it would need to be strengthened. The implementation of the action plan and strengthening of health systems in border districts would have to be done by individual countries, as it is the funnel through which all public health programmes are delivered.

It is hoped that this document will trigger a discussion among the key stakeholders to give shape to an action plan that would provide momentum to control of priority communicable diseases amongst Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar and Nepal.

INTRODUCTION

Cross-border movement of people has been a pathway for the spread of infectious diseases since time immemorial and continues to do so even today. Be it the presumed spread of smallpox from Egypt to India, a thousand years before Christ or 2500 years later when Christopher Columbus' arrival in the Caribbeans at the end of the 15th century led to a disease breakout among the native Americans or in 2020 the pandemic of COVID-19 which has taken a heavy toll of lives across the world.

A spontaneous response, therefore, has been a call for travel bans and strict enforcement of restricted entry of foreigners through the borders. However, a clamping down on movement and migration is neither a feasible nor a desirable solution to cross border disease control. The availability of better tools for prevention, diagnosis, and management of diseases, has reduced but not totally eliminated the threat of "imported cases". These new tools and new capacities have also given wind to the sails in moving rapidly towards transforming strategies from control of diseases to their elimination and finally eradication.

In areas where vector-borne diseases are prevalent, elimination has become a distinct possibility through breaking the chain of transmission and sustaining these efforts. Many countries have proved that this is indeed possible, especially for Malaria. As of mid-2021, three countries in India's neighbourhood viz China, Sri Lanka and the Maldives have been certified malaria-free, while others are making rapid progress. In some Kala-Azar endemic countries like Bangladesh and Nepal, the number of new indigenous cases has been brought down significantly, reaching a situation when Kala- Azar ceases to be a public health problem is a distinct possibility.

The "disease-free" status is less secured in areas where efficient vectors, freely accessible human hosts, and optimum environmental conditions persist. The threat of importation of malaria is real, especially through mobile and migrant populations. Kala-Azar outbreaks have also been linked to the migration pattern of seasonal labourers in the region, specifically Nepal and India. This risk requires urgent attention.

HIV, as other infections caused by transmissible pathogens, has been viewed in many countries as an "imported problem". Governments were quick to blame others as the source of infection. Travel was quickly identified as a risk factor. This was supported by data of high HIV prevalence among migrant workers. In Tuberculosis, too, migrants have been identified as "key populations".

As countries of the South East Asia Region inch towards the target of malaria and kala-azar elimination, the focus of cross-border initiatives is to prevent the re-establishment of focal chains of transmission as a result of imported cases. While in HIV and tuberculosis, it is to ensure that migrants have access to diagnosis, treatment and follow-up services, irrespective of their nationality, especially in the districts on either side of the international border.

The Regional Office of the South East Asia Region has been alive to the problem of cross border control of infectious diseases since the mid-1990s and had the foresight to take initiatives for the control of HIV, tuberculosis, malaria and kala-azar between Bangladesh, Bhutan, India and Nepal. Several Regional, sub-Regional and bi-lateral meetings / consultation of technical experts, programme managers, policy and decision makers, funders have been organised. Though some progress has been made in the last twenty years, there is still a long road to be covered.

Over the period of time, the global and regional concept of, and approach to combat communicable disease control has evolved. There has been a gradual but distinct change. In September 2000, the member states of the United Nations signed up to the eight Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) to reduce extreme poverty by 2015. The MDG 6 addresses HIV/AIDS, malaria and other diseases and sets the target of halting HIV/AIDS and malaria by 2015 and beginning to reverse their spread. In 2015, the world adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Agenda with 17 Sustainable Development Goals at its core.

The SDG 3's mission is to "ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages" and is underpinned by 13 targets. Target 3.3 aims to also end the epidemics of AIDS, TB, malaria and neglected tropical diseases. To assist the countries in reaching SDG 3 targets, key disease-specific global strategic frameworks have been developed. The SEA region of the WHO has developed strategies for the countries of the region aligning to the global strategies and has revised its regional strategy, and formulated action-plans. Regional Action Plans too have been developed. These developments have not only brought in renewed energy, fresh players, new partnerships and platforms, but new opportunities as well. An increase in the number of partners is good news but is accompanied by the fresh challenge of synergizing their work.

Some of the other relevant developments include release of the 3rd edition of the International Health Regulations (2005) which outlines member countries' rights and obligations in dealing with public health activities and emergencies if they hold the potential to spill over to neighbouring countries; the Global Action Plan to promote the health of refugees and migrants which positions WHO at the centre to support the public health aspects of refugee and migrant health. The usefulness of cross-border efforts to control communicable diseases (like malaria, tuberculosis, HIV/AIDS, Ebola, poliomyelitis, onchocerciasis etc), and strengthening communicable disease surveillance (for example South-Eastern Europe Health Network; East African Integrated Disease Surveillance Network, Middle-East Consortium on Infectious Disease Surveillance, Mekong Basin Disease Surveillance Network etc) has been demonstrated in several parts of the world.

We got an APW to look back over the twenty-year period in terms of the progress made in cross-border control of HIV, tuberculosis, malaria and Kala-Azar in Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Nepal and Myanmar, map the organisations involved in cross-border work, review the socio-epidemiological impact on border regions, assess the region's policies and programmes, identify lessons learnt from other cross-border communicable disease control programmes, study cost-benefit analysis of various interventions, underscore the barriers in cooperation and coordination for cross border control of diseases. Finally, the recommendations for synergizing the work of various partners and suggest a framework for a sustainable action plan which includes the political-buy-in.

METHODS

Given the nature of the exercise, the research team decided to adopt a wide-ranging methodology that would tap into all possible sources of information and insight. While secondary data and literature on this issue is indeed scarce, a focused literature survey was taken up to highlight best practices from across the world. The second step then was to consult a number of stakeholders who have worked on and studied this issue of cross border collaborations. These interviews and discussions allowed for some fresh inputs for the report. The third step was to then amalgamate the learning from both the processes and glean observations made and suggestions offered. Finally, as et of focus group discussions within the team led to the preparation of short term and medium-term interventions that have been suggested here.

Terms of Reference

1. Mapping of organizations involved in cross-border work (including but not limited to UN organizations like IOM, UNHCR, and other NGOs); review data and literature on social and associated epidemiological impact on border regions of the countries concerned. Create a repository on the subject
2. Assess regional communicable disease control policies and programs (including inclusion/exclusion policies of non-nationals in the packages and/or health insurance schemes for coverage of infectious diseases, and restrictions on entry, stay or residence for foreign nationals based on HIV status). Bring out their strong points and areas that need strengthening. Identify lessons learned from other cross-border communicable disease control initiatives, including beyond the SEAR.
3. Underscore and understand the barriers, in cooperation and collaboration between countries for cross-border communicable disease control, across departments and ministries, including country policies
4. Study cost-benefit analyses of various interventions, if available, to highlight the economic costs that the region pays for not controlling these diseases across borders

Period of review: The review covers a twenty year period between 2001 and 2021.

Geographical area covered: Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar and Nepal.

The earlier efforts of the WHO's SEA Regional office at cross border control of priority communicable diseases (malaria, kala-azar, tuberculosis, and HIV/AIDS) were between Bangladesh, Bhutan, India and Nepal. There is another country with which India shares 1600 kms of its land borders, Myanmar. Four North-Eastern states of India viz. Arunachal Pradesh, Nagaland, Manipur and Mizoram share boundaries with Myanmar. Both countries share a heritage of religious, linguistic and ethnic ties and people from both countries move across the international border as there is a Free Movement Regime. This allows tribes in border areas to travel up to 16 kms on either side without visa restrictions. There are over 300 000 people living within 10 kms from the border who frequently cross the border. Including Myanmar in cross border initiatives is important because of potential cross-border spread of artemisinin-resistant malaria; amongst the 30 high TB burden countries Myanmar is ranked tenth, and amongst the high multidrug resistant countries it is ranked ninth. Myanmar has the second-highest HIV prevalence in South East Asia (0.7%). Kala-azar cases have not been reported from Myanmar. Myanmar has been actively collaborating with neighbouring countries for

cross border control of communicable diseases, for example with Thailand (efforts along the border especially against HIV, TB and Malaria), China (for cross border control of malaria). Since Bangladesh, Bhutan, India Myanmar and Nepal form a single landmass, it is prudent to extend the activities for cross border control of identified communicable diseases.

Diseases covered: Malaria, TB, HIV, Kala-azar.

This document builds upon the earlier work done by the SEA Regional Office in these four priority communicable diseases

Primary Research Question:

What progress has been made in controlling cross-border priority communicable diseases in the South-East Asia Region of the WHO?

Secondary Research Questions:

1. What are the policies, programmes, practices, guidelines and experiences in cross border control of priority communicable diseases (the big-4: Malaria, TB, HIV, Kala-azar) in the last twenty years (2001-2021) in Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar and Nepal?
2. What are the effects, benefits, and limitations in cross border control of priority communicable diseases (Malaria, TB, HIV, Kala-azar) in the last twenty years (2001-2021) between Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar and Nepal?
3. Who are the main stakeholders? What do they bring to the table?

Methods

Two approaches were used – review of literature and interactions with individuals and representatives of organizations.

a. Search Strategy

Peer-reviewed Journals: PubMed and Google Scholar were searched for relevant documents published between 2001 and 2021.

The following search keywords would be used:

S No.	Keywords		
1	Cross-border	Communicable Diseases Control	South-East Asia
2	Cross-border	Malaria Control	India-Bangladesh
			India-Bhutan
			India-Myanmar
			India-Nepal
3	Cross-border	HIV Control	India-Bangladesh
			India-Bhutan
			India-Myanmar
			India-Nepal
4	Cross-border	Tuberculosis Control	India-Bangladesh
			India-Bhutan
			India-Myanmar
			India-Nepal
5	Cross-border	Kal-azar Control	India-Bangladesh
			India-Bhutan
			India-Myanmar
			India-Nepal

Literature survey:

The ‘white’ literature, mostly found in PubMed, are in scientific reviewed journals typically involving multi-stage reviews and editorial comments involving authors, editors and reviewers. Some of it is behind paywalls.

Domains selected through the literature review: “Cross-border migration”, “Migrants’ health”, “South Asia”, “HIV”, “Places of origin”, “Bangladeshi migrants”, “Nepalese migrants”, “Migrants and TB”, “Malaria and migrants”, and “Migration-related policies”. To obtain the most relevant findings, the review was narrowed to peer-reviewed materials published between 2001 and 2020, except for some materials we considered relevant, despite being published before the specified timeframe. For issues such as policies related to migrants and country-specific schemes, documents were included without any time limit.

The grey literature is the research and analysis publications outside of academic publishing and has had limited peer review. Contributions from grey literature (such as research reports, working papers and government/official documents) are usually available through search engines like ‘Google’ and/or visiting the websites of the organizations/agencies.

The search results are available as Annex No 2.

The literature search also threw up names of the organizations/agencies who are actively engaged in cross-border disease control.

Their websites were accessed to know their role in cross border communicable disease control / elimination.

A very limited number of publications were available in the white literature; both white and grey literature produced, published (between 2001 and 2021), and available have been included in this review. The report highlights key contributions made during this period, published in English by scientific journals, intergovernmental organizations, partnerships, national, regional and international platforms.

a. Interviews

Key personnel from various organizations were contacted and interviewed to get their perspective of the issues related to cross border disease control.

REGIONAL AND COUNTRY-LEVEL BURDEN OF DISEASES

The South-East Asia Region of the WHO region comprises eleven countries: Bangladesh, Bhutan, Democratic People's Republic of Korea, India, Indonesia, Maldives, Myanmar, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Thailand and Timor-Leste. It is home to roughly a quarter of the world's population.

Of the estimated population of the region's countries in 2020 (2044 million), 80% reside in Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar, and Nepal. These countries also have a high burden of communicable diseases. These have signed up for various World Health Assembly resolutions calling for the elimination of malaria, TB, reduction of HIV, and regional elimination of visceral leishmaniasis (Kala-Azar). Many countries of the region have made significant progress in achieving elimination targets, but there is a constant fear of an imported case setting up a chain of local transmission (for example, of malaria) undoing the gains. The region cannot be free of diseases until all the countries of the region are.

Priority Diseases

HIV, Tuberculosis, Kala-azar and Malaria are major public health concerns. Malaria has epidemic potential. Drug-resistant *P. falciparum* is found along both sides of many international borders. Treatment of tuberculosis, care and support for AIDS in border areas require specific attention. Kala-Azar is endemic in a few South Asian countries, especially along their international borders. AIDS, TB, malaria and kala-azar, constitute unique problems in border areas that require cooperation between countries to address the specific issues related to combat these diseases.

HIV

It is estimated that in 2020, globally, nearly 38m (range 30.2-45.1m) people were living with HIV. Of this 3.7m (range 2.8-4.4m), about 10% were living in countries of the SEA region. There were about 1.5 million new infections globally, and of these 100 000 were in the SEA region. India, Myanmar and Nepal are among the five countries which account for the majority of the HIV burden. In contrast, Bangladesh, Bhutan, the Maldives, Sri Lanka and Timor-Leste account for about 2 million people living with HIV (2018). In 2017, India had 2.1m people living with HIV- the third-largest figure globally. India, Myanmar and Nepal are among the five countries which account for a majority of the HIV burden, while Bangladesh, Bhutan, along with Maldives, Sri Lanka and Timor-Leste account for about 2 million people living with HIV (2018). In 2017, India had 2.1m people living with HIV- the third-largest figure globally.

A vital feature of the HIV epidemic in the region is that most new HIV infections occur among key populations such as sex workers, men who have sex with men, transgender persons and people who inject drugs and their partners. As per the fast track targets of UNAIDS, 95-95-95 (which require 95% of those living with HIV to know their HIV status, 95% of all people diagnosed with HIV infection to receive sustained antiretroviral therapy, and 95% of all people on such therapy to have viral suppression by 2030), this fast track approach will avert 17.6 million new infections and 10.8 million AIDS-related deaths between 2016 and 2030.

Nearly 60% of the estimated 3.7 million people in the region living with HIV are now receiving lifelong antiretroviral therapy. The Maldives, Sri Lanka and Thailand have eliminated mother-to-child transmission of HIV and syphilis. Bhutan, India and Nepal have decriminalized same-sex relations, reflecting Regionwide efforts to promote inclusivity, reduce stigma and increase access to HIV services¹.

Source: GAM and national programs

(Some of the data points not available through GAM have been obtained from national programmes)

The three states with the highest HIV prevalence in India are Manipur, Mizoram, and Nagaland, which share their border with Myanmar.

Targets to end the HIV epidemic

The commitments outlined in the '2021 Political Declaration on HIV and AIDS: Ending inequalities and getting on track to and AIDS By 2030' call for urgent action in to achieve saturation coverage priority prevention and treatment approaches. Central to hopes for ending the AIDS epidemic is the achievement of the 95-95-95 target:

- 95% of people living with HIV know their HIV status;
- 95% of people who know their HIV-positive status are on treatment; and
- 95% of people on treatment with suppressed viral load.

In addition to 95-95-95, the 2021 Political Declaration calls for a combination of approaches to reduce the annual number of new HIV infections and AIDS-related deaths to fewer than 200,000 by 2030 and achieve the goal of zero discrimination.

End AIDS as a public health threat by 2030 (Sustainable Development Goals). The Vision is to have

- Zero discrimination
- Zero new HIV infection
- Zero AIDS-related deaths

Political commitment

The UN Political Declaration on HIV and AIDS (2021) declared its commitment on the fast track to accelerate the fight against HIV and to end the AIDS epidemic by 2030².

Tuberculosis

In 2019, globally, about 10 million people fell ill with tuberculosis-the South-East Asia Region of the WHO had 4.4 million cases. Amongst the countries of the South-East Asia Region, India accounts for 2.6 million, Indonesia 850,000, Bangladesh 361 000, Myanmar 174,000, and Thailand 105,000.

Bangladesh, India and Myanmar find a place in the list of top 20 countries having a large burden of tuberculosis:

Characteristics	BAN	IND	MMR
The top 20 countries with the highest estimated number of incident (new) case	✓	✓	✓
The top 20 countries with the highest estimated number of incident TB cases		✓	✓
The top 20 countries with the highest number of incident MDR-TB cases	✓	✓	✓

Source: Global TB Report 2020

SEA Region, with only 26% of the world's population, has the highest TB incidence than other country on the WHO region. In the year 2019, in SEA Region, about 4.3 million persons developed TB disease and 0.65 million persons died due to the disease. These numbers constitute ~43% of the global TB incidence and 46% of the global TB deaths. SEA Region also has the highest proportion (30%) of people with a tuberculosis infection.

SEA Region countries have made commendable progress towards reducing the TB burden by increasing the number of TB patients diagnosed and treated from ~2.6 million in 2015 to ~3.6 million in 2019 (a 38% increase). Close to 70,000 rifampicin-resistant/ multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) patients were detected in 2019, more than double the number (32,000 patients) detected in 2015.

Elimination Targets

The following targets need to be achieved by 2035 compared to 2015 as a baseline:

- 95% reduction in the number of TB deaths
- 90% reduction in the TB incidence rate
- Zero TB-affected families facing catastrophic costs due to TB.

To reach these targets, the annual decline in global TB incidence rates must accelerate from 1.5% annually in 2015 to at least 10% annually by 2025. In addition, the proportion of people with TB who die from the disease must decline from the current rate of 15% in 2015 to 6.5% by 2025. These targets are aligned with the SDG target of reducing the TB incidence rate by 80% by 2030. India has taken a decision to end tuberculosis by 2025 – five years ahead of the global target.

Myanmar is on track to achieve the milestones for mortality and incidence. Bangladesh and Thailand are on track to reach the milestone for mortality. In 2018, the region notified at least 750,000 more cases than in 2015, indicating a 20% increase in treatment coverage. The region detected more than double the number of RR/MDR-TB cases.

Political commitment

2017: Delhi Call for Action to End TB in the WHO South-East Asia Region that reaffirms the highest level of commitment by the Member States.

Malaria

In 2019, there were approximately 229 million cases of malaria. Twenty-nine countries accounted for 95% of cases. The WHO African Region, with an estimated 215 million cases, accounted for about 94% of cases. Malaria is endemic in 9 of the 11 countries in the South East Asia region; it has almost 6.3 m estimated cases (accounting for about 3% of global cases). Three countries in the region accounted for 99.5% of cases – India contributing 87.9%, Indonesia 10.4%, and Myanmar 1.2%. No indigenous case was reported by Bhutan and Nepal. Recent reports indicate that in 2020 Bhutan had 22 and Nepal 71 indigenous malaria cases. Two countries in the region Maldives in 2015 and Sri Lanka in 2016 were certified as malaria-free, while three other Member States – Bhutan, Nepal, Timor Leste, have been identified as having the potential to eliminate malaria by 2020 (of 21 countries termed as “E-2020 countries” by WHO).

All member states of the region have committed to malaria elimination by 2030 at the latest.

Elimination Targets

The Global Technical Strategy for Malaria (GTS) 2016-2030, endorsed by the World Health Assembly in 2015, has fixed targets of reducing both malaria mortality and case incidence globally by at least 40% by 2020 compared to 2015, by at least 75% by 2025 and by at least 90% by 2030, and to eliminate malaria from at least ten countries by 2020 and 35 countries by 2030.

The proposed interim goals are:

- reduce mortality and morbidity due to malaria in the South East Region by 50% by 2020 and by 90% by 2025 (2015 baselines);
- accelerate malaria elimination;
- maintain malaria-free status and
- prevent re-introduction of malaria in areas and countries where malaria transmission has been interrupted.

Political commitment

2017: Ministerial Declaration on Accelerating and Sustaining Malaria Elimination in the South-East Asia Region,

2018: Ministerial Call for Action to Eliminate Malaria in the Greater Mekong Subregion before 2030

Visceral leishmaniasis (Kala-azar)

It is estimated that 50,000 to 90,000 new cases of VL occur worldwide, but only 25-45% get reported to the WHO. In 2020 of the 14 endemic countries, 9 reported 4311 cases of visceral leishmaniasis to the WHO. The region of Africa reported 34% of these cases, the Eastern Mediterranean 29% and South East Asia 18%. Three countries in SEA (Bangladesh, India, and Nepal) reported 2295 (18%) autochthonous cases. India's contribution was 2033 (88.58%), Nepal 215 (9.36%) and Bangladesh 47 (2.04%). Since 2011, the SEA region has seen a sharp decrease in the number of cases to less than 2500 in 2020- a decrease of 94%. The disease is endemic in 109 districts in the region – 52 blocks in India, 45 upazilas in Bangladesh, and 12 districts in Nepal. Three countries in SEA (Bangladesh, India, and Nepal) reported 2295 (18%) autochthonous case. India's contribution was 2033 (88.58%), Nepal 215 (9.36%) and Bangladesh 47 (2.04%). Since 2011, SEA region has seen a sharp decrease in number of cases to less than 2500 in 2020- a decrease of 94%. The disease is endemic in 109 districts in the Region – 52 blocks in India, 45 upazilas in Bangladesh, and 12 districts in Nepal.

Source: *Weekly Epidemiological Record*, 96: 35 401–420, 2021

The distribution patterns of the disease are changing, and new foci are emerging from regions not covered under elimination programmes, such as mountains, valleys and even urban areas. Although endemic regions in the three countries are confined to the Lower Gangetic plains – north-eastern India, south-eastern lowland of Nepal and the Ganga delta in Bangladesh – localized transmission has also been reported from hilly areas in India and Nepal, perhaps due to the effects of climate change.

Post-Kala-azar Dermal Leishmaniasis

In 2020, a total of 778 PKDL cases were reported from 7 countries, with significant variations in their contribution to the total: 96% (617/778) from India, 10% (78/778) from Sudan, 7% (57/778) from Bangladesh, 2% (12/778) from South Sudan and 1% (4/778) from Ethiopia.

PKDL poses a significant threat to the VL elimination program in the Indian subcontinent. While VL cases drive transmission when VL incidence is high during the peak years of an epidemic, the contribution of PKDL to transmission increases as VL prevalence decreases and PKDL prevalence increases in the downward phase of an epidemic. PKDL may serve as a source of infection through sandfly and thus maintain transmission. This mirrors the current situation in Bangladesh and India, where VL incidence has been decreasing since 2011 but reported numbers of PKDL cases to suggest PKDL prevalence is higher than VL prevalence in some areas. Effective reporting of PKDL cases and interventions are needed to ensure an effective treatment in endemic areas.

While the endemic regions are in three different countries, geographically, these areas are contiguous, with the movement of people across borders underscoring the importance of cross-border surveillance³.

Elimination Targets

The SEA is the only region to have a programme to eliminate VL. The target is to reduce the incidence of the disease to less than one case per 10,000 population at the sub-district level (upazila in Bangladesh, block in India) and at the district level in Nepal. These targets were initially to be achieved by the end of 2015. The target for India is 2021. The region is poised to achieve the target with the countries aiming to have WHO validate elimination by 2023.000 population at sub-district level (upazila in Bangladesh, block in India) and at district level in Nepal.

Political commitment

2005: A MoU was signed by Health ministers from Bangladesh, India and Nepal for the elimination of Kala-azar by the end of 2017 or before.

2014: MoU signed by Health Ministers from Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Nepal and Thailand to collaborate in the elimination of Visceral Leishmaniasis (Kala-azar) from their countries.

DISEASE BURDEN IN THE BORDER DISTRICTS

Cross-border Malaria

Cross-border malaria refers to malaria transmission and cases that cross international boundaries. There are two types of cross-border malaria: transnational and border malaria.

1. **“Transnational malaria”** refers to imported cases of malaria that cross a border or enter a country through air or seaports but do not necessarily affect transmission within the border area per se. Transnational malaria can originate from any malaria-endemic country and can be received by any malaria-endemic or non-endemic country. The countries of origin and destination of the infection in transnational malaria may or may not be adjacent, and the infection may be received in any location of the recipient country. These malaria infections may or may not generate onward transmission.
2. **“Border malaria”** is malaria transmission or potential for transmission that takes place across or along borders between countries sharing a land border. Border malaria can extend up through the adjacent administrative areas along the international border or up to a specified distance from an international border. Border malaria is often a malaria transmission focus that crosses international borders, but it may also occur due to limited or no access to malaria prevention, diagnosis and treatment interventions and sub-optimal surveillance response as a result of the remoteness and/or political complexity of border areas.

Features of border malaria

A country’s border areas may include diverse features that both facilitate and require specific attention, including:

- i. Contiguous areas often share a common ecology, related human populations, and related malaria parasites and vectors.
- ii. Border areas tend to have the least-developed health systems of the nation.
- iii. A substantial health service system and malaria transmission gradient may exist between the adjacent areas across a border.
- iv. As a country seeks elimination, the last remaining infection foci often occur along international borders, suggesting that countries should address border malaria early in their elimination efforts.
- v. Local cross-border engagement for enhanced communication, data sharing, and coordination of malaria interventions (such as common timing of vector-control activities and common policies for malaria case management) may lead to a substantial impact against malaria.

Examples of potential contributors to border malaria are numerous:

- i. Border areas are remote, less developed, sometimes more forested and likely to have weak health systems.
- ii. The level of surveillance is low and insufficient to cover mobile and migrant populations, nomadic and indigenous populations, or minorities who normally gather or reside along borders.
- iii. Treatment-seeking behaviour of underserved populations at borders – such as self-medication and poor quality of treatment with counterfeit and substandard medicines – may contribute to the development of drug resistance.
- iv. Population movement across borders to seek malaria treatment for economic, security or access reasons is commonly seen and likely contributes to transmission. Differences in national malaria policies (such as for primaquine) can lead to incomplete adherence, and

- v. Risks associated with occupational activities such as farming, mining, logging or smuggling contribute to border transmission.
- vi. Civil unrest can foster the settlement of refugees or internal-displaced populations coming from malaria-endemic areas at borders.
- vii. Unstable political and social environments at borders can hamper the deployment of interventions.
- viii. The illegal status of some populations along borders makes it difficult to access prevention, diagnosis and treatment.
- ix. Sometimes cultural differences and language barriers on both sides of the border complicate diagnosis, follow-up of treatment and implementation of prevention activities.
- x. The heterogeneity of malaria prevalence and the unknown malaria reservoir complicate elimination in border areas.

Risk groups include

- i. Male travellers –
 - a. mostly traders,
 - b. forest workers,
 - c. military men,
 - d. local farmers and
 - e. rural migrants who have myriad economic pursuits across the various border settings.
- ii. Inhabitants of villages near borders,
- iv. Indigenous populations and others.

Because border malaria generally cannot be solved unilaterally, functional border coordination, where relevant, is one of the prerequisites for eliminating malaria and preventing re-establishment of malaria transmission, according to WHO criteria for certification of malaria elimination.

Border or cross-border malaria is a frequently cited challenge to malaria elimination. At the first Global Forum of malaria-eliminating countries, 15 of the 20 E-2020 countries identified border or cross-border malaria as a major issue in achieving elimination⁴.

The significance of malaria along borders is reflected in the growing number of cross-country collaborations to mobilize specific resources to reduce malaria in neighbouring countries where migrants originate, mount coordinated efforts to control malaria at borders and enhance surveillance among migrants or local residents at borders.

Malaria in Migrant populations

Migration on its own is not a risk factor for increased malaria transmission. However, movement into malaria-endemic regions, as a result of infrastructure and rural development, deforestation for logging and economic farming, political movements and natural disasters can make migrant populations more vulnerable to malaria. Malaria is endemic in five of the six GMS countries (Cambodia, Lao People's Democratic Republic, Myanmar, Thailand and Vietnam). The Thai–Myanmar border and some provinces in Cambodia are the areas with the highest prevalence of malaria. In the WHO SEA Region, other than the two countries that have already eliminated malaria (the Maldives and Sri Lanka), the remaining nine countries are endemic for malaria. The region, the second most heavily malaria-affected after sub-Saharan Africa, has several countries that are rapidly progressing towards elimination – including Bhutan, Nepal and Timor-Leste – and have the potential to eliminate local malaria transmission by 2020. Imported malaria through migration from neighbouring high-burden countries is increasingly a challenge for them as well as for the two countries that have eliminated malaria to prevent re-introduction.

Bangladesh

India and Bangladesh share a 4,096-kilometre-long international border, the fifth-longest land border in the world, including 262 km in Assam, 856 km in Tripura, 318 km in Mizoram, 443 km in Meghalaya, and 2,217 km in West Bengal. A number of pillars mark the border between the two

states. Only around 1,500 km is fenced. Bangladesh also shares about 300 kms border with Myanmar, adjoining the districts of Bandarban and Cox's Bazar.

Bangladesh's all 13 endemic districts have an international border with India or Myanmar. 41, out of 72 endemic sub-districts have an international border, 34 with India, 5 with Myanmar, and 2 with both India and Myanmar.

Annual Incidence of malaria in Bangladesh by *upazilas* 2020

Bangladesh has seen a 93% case reduction in 2020 compared to 2008. There were only 6,130 cases in 2020 (compared to 84,690 in 2008). Deaths had also reduced by 94% in 2020; 9 deaths were reported in

2020 as compared to 154 in 2008.

Malaria transmission in Bangladesh has become highly focal; cases are confined mainly in areas near international borders with India. There is a substantial number of border crossing points in India-Bangladesh borders.

Accessibility to malaria services in the bordering areas:

House to House mobile services (EDPT) by CHWs; covers ~80% of malaria cases. Community Clinics (CCs) for EDPT: 1 CC per 6 000 population; about 200 CCs across the borders of 41 upazila. There are also Union Sub-Centers and Family Welfare Centers in between the Community and upazila level. Upazila Health Complex (UHC) at the upazila level for malaria indoor and outdoor services. At the district level, there is a District hospital and medical college hospitals.

There is a strong involvement of BRAC led NGOs with a large number of trained community health workers engaged in EDPT and surveillance (in malaria control areas). The LLIN distribution is a core preventive vector control intervention. Over 90% of the population slept under LLIN in all surveyed upazilas (endemic areas). The LLIN distribution has nearly reached universal coverage with at least 2 LLIN/households (endemic areas).

Results of a survey of over 100 border crossing points in 35 upazilas in Bangladesh indicate that informal crossing points far outnumber formal. All upazilas in the elimination phase reported an increasing proportion of imported cases during 2017-19, and most of the imported cases were of

P. falciparum. During 2018-2019 all the reported malaria cases (9) in Durgapur were imported, and similarly, all cases reported in Kalmakanda (69) were imported. Despite fences and border guards, people use the unmanned and unfenced portion of the border for crossing; hence there is a potential risk of malaria importation.

A study reviewed the situation of imported malaria in Netrokona, a border district of Bangladesh, where the malaria burden has reduced by 91% between 2008 and 2018, and elimination of the disease by 2021 is the goal. It borders the Meghalaya State of India. Between 2013 and 2018, imported cases contributed 60% to the 95% malaria burden in the Netrokona district. The mean age of these imported cases is 32 years, and most of the cases (82%) were between 15 and 49 years old. The distribution of these imported cases by population type showed an overall 93% (88% to 95%) contribution by the cross-border workers. All the imported cases occurred in populations of bordered (with Meghalaya, India) where the people from the district go to find work as coalmine-labourers in winter and wood-cutters in the rainy season on a contract basis.

The higher reduction of indigenous (97%) infection, compared to imported (56%) cases between 2013 and 2018, results in the increased portion of imported malaria burden of the district over the years. Like other elimination settings, imported malaria in this district is mostly contributed by adult males. Due to the geographic location of the area nearby the international border (between Bangladesh and India), the population has very little scope of work within the national boundary. Based on the accessibility and scope of work in the bordering area of Meghalaya, the number of cross-border workers and their contribution to the imported cases differ in the bordering unions of the district⁵.

Bhutan

India-Bhutan border is 699 km long and adjoins the Indian states of Assam (267 km), Arunachal Pradesh (217 km), West Bengal (183 km), and Sikkim (32 km). India and Bhutan share open borders. Nationals from both countries can cross freely without visa requirements. India and Bhutan share open borders. Nationals from both countries can cross freely without visa requirements.

Border districts of India with Bhutan

There are two districts in Bhutan where indigenous transmission has been detected between 2018-2020. The situation of malaria in the two endemic districts is in Table.

Districts	Population	2019		2020	
		Cases	Deaths	Cases	Deaths
Sarpang	49,472	27	0	44	0
Samdrup Jonkhar	35,001	5	0	1	0

World Health Organization. Regional Office for South-East Asia. (2021). Cross-border collaboration for elimination of Kala-azar and malaria along the India international border with Bangladesh, Bhutan and Nepal from 28 to 30 September 2021. WHO Regional Office for South-East Asia.

It is estimated that there are approximately 45,000 - 50,000 immigrants in Bhutan and a vast majority of them are of Indian origin, mostly coming from the states of West Bengal and Assam and some from the states of Uttarakhand, Bihar and Uttar Pradesh. Most of the immigrants are employed as construction workers at hydroelectric power projects sites and housing projects. They generally stay for a few months and then return to native districts in India. Many workers cross the border in the morning hours, engage in occupational activities during the day and return to their homes by evening. A total of 16,057 day workers were enumerated on the national census day in 2017. Since 2014, an increasing number of malaria cases have been detected in non-Bhutanese as compared to the Bhutanese, most of whom are of Indian nationality.

Royal Government of Bhutan. *Strategic Plan for Elimination of Malaria and Prevention of Re-Introduction in Bhutan 2020-2025. Vector-borne Diseases Control programme, Department of Public Health, Ministry of Health 2020*

Bhutan shares a porous land border with the Indian States of Assam and West Bengal, which are endemic to malaria. Considering the proximity and human settlement, the risk is even higher. Over the past years, malaria cases in the country have been confined to international border areas, posing a

considerable threat not only in achieving our malaria elimination goal but also sustaining the prevention of re-introduction. Therefore, reducing malaria incidences across the border remains very fragile unless the cross-border initiatives are well instituted and established⁶.

India

India has 15,106.7 km of land border with its various neighbours. The length of its land borders with neighbouring countries in the region being studied is Bangladesh of 4,096.7 km, Nepal of 1,751; Myanmar of 1,643; Bhutan of 699kms.

Government of India. Ministry of Home Affairs. International land border.

<https://www.mha.gov.in/sites/default/files/BMIntro-1011.pdf>

In 2020 there were 186,532 cases and 93 deaths, showing a decline of 84% in cases as compared to 2015 (1,169,261 cases) and 76% in deaths (in 2015, there were 384 deaths). Among the ten states which have an international border, 5 have an API of more than 1.

Meghalaya has two districts (South Garo Hills & East Garo Hills) which have an API of more than 1. Mizoram has 4 (Lunglei, Saiha, Mamit & Laungtlai), Tripura has 2 (Dhalai Tripura & South Tripura), Uttar Pradesh has 2 (Badaun & Bareilly), and West Bengal has 1 (Kolkata Municipal corporation)

There were 3269 cases of Kala-azar (KA) in 2019 with 43 deaths, and 2047 cases and 37 deaths in 2020. The number of KA cases decreased by 97% in 2020 as compared to 2015. Six hundred sixteen cases of PKDL were reported in 2020.

Of the endemic states, Bihar reported 73% of KA cases and 58% of PKDL cases in 2020. Till 2020, out of 633 KA endemic blocks, 617 (97.5%) blocks have achieved the elimination target. Twelve in Jharkhand and 4 in Bihar have reported >1 Kala-azar case per 10000 population.

Myanmar

India–Myanmar border is 1,643 km in length. Four Northeast Indian states share the border with Myanmar: Arunachal Pradesh (520 km), Nagaland (215 km), Mizoram (516 km), and Manipur (398 km). Myanmar also shares its border with Bangladesh.

The India–Myanmar border has a Free Movement Regime (FMR), which allows tribes living along the border to travel 16 km across either side of the border without visa restrictions. There are over 250 villages with over 300,000 people living within 10 kilometres of the border who frequently cross the border through 150 small and large formal and informal border crossings.

The incidence of malaria in Myanmar has reduced significantly in recent years, falling by over 80% from a reported 1341.8 cases per 100,000 population in 2005 to 253.3 cases per 100,000 population in 2014. Similarly, malaria mortality fell by over 90%, from 3.79 deaths per 100,000 to 0.25 per 100,000 over the same period. Along with the rest of the Greater Mekong Sub-region (GMS) countries, the Myanmar national malaria control programme (NMCP) has drafted a strategy to eliminate malaria by 2030⁷.

Of the 52 million population residing in the country, 22.5 million (43%) reside in endemic areas, whereas 21.4 million (41%) live in areas with receptivity and vulnerability risk of malaria. A total of 182,616 malaria cases were reported in 2015. At present, falciparum malaria accounts for around 64% of cases. Thirty-seven malaria-related deaths were reported amongst hospital in-patients in 2015.

Map showing incidence of malaria in the border districts of Myanmar-India-Bangladesh, 2016

Mobile and migrant populations have been identified as having a high risk of malaria, which includes transient or mobile camps associated with commercial projects (road/pipeline construction, large-scale logging, deep seaport projects), and formal and informal cross-border migrant workers (Legal and illegal workforces). Migrants, both national and international, are a particular concern in that they could potentially contribute to the spread of artemisinin-resistant malaria parasites. Providing a comprehensive package of services to these high-risk mobile population groups is an important focus of the strategy. These are a diverse mobile population who cross the border for work, both legal and illegal. Some are long term or permanent migrants, while others cross the border often or even daily.

According to the International Organization for Migration, there are an estimated 2 million Myanmar nationals based in Thailand at present and about 200,000 in Bangladesh. While many of these spend their time abroad in urban or other non-endemic areas, others, particularly seasonal agricultural workers (see above), are based in areas where the transmission does occur. There is a possibility that cross-border workers returning from parts of the GMS could introduce multi-ACT resistant *P. falciparum* to receptive areas of Myanmar. As the quality of surveillance improves, the stratification will evolve to distinguish between endemic villages and villages where all cases are imported.

Nepal

The India–Nepal border is about 1751 km long and is shared by five Indian States – Uttarakhand (263 km), Uttar Pradesh (560 km), Bihar (729 km), West Bengal (100 km) and Sikkim (99 km). As a result of a bilateral friendship treaty signed between India and Nepal in 1950, citizens of both countries can travel and work freely across the border. The India–Nepal border is porous. Indian and Nepali nationals do not need passports or visas to enter each other’s countries, and tens of thousands of people cross the border every day for tourism and commerce. Since there are no fences along the border, there are several smaller official and unofficial border crossings. The India–Nepal border is porous. Indian and Nepali nationals do not need passports or visas to enter each other’s countries, and tens of thousands of people

cross the border every day for tourism and commerce. Since there are no fences along the border, there are several smaller official and unofficial border crossings.

Imported cases contribute to more than 50% per cent of the total malaria cases reported in the country. Seasonal migrant workers arrive from high-risk areas of India, especially during the festival seasons. There is significant unchecked population movement across Nepal's long and porous border with India. Health desks have been set up at major locations for screening of the migrants; however, they have not been effective due to inadequate human resources, budget and infrastructure.

A high-level meeting was held between India, Nepal, Bangladesh and Bhutan to discuss regional collaboration for cross border control of malaria. A joint MoU exists between India and Nepal for control of the communicable disease. Cross border collaboration still needs further strengthening and ensuring access to diagnosis and effective management to migrant and mobile populations across borders and information sharing between the countries.

Source: World Health Organization. Regional Office for South-East Asia. (2021). Cross-border collaboration for elimination of Kala-azar and malaria along the India international border with Bangladesh, Bhutan and Nepal from 28 to 30 September 2021. WHO Regional Office for South-East Asia

A large number of Nepalese migrate outside the country for work, some as long-term workers, while others as seasonal workers in search of better opportunities as labourers, agricultural & forest workers, and security guards to high malaria endemic states of India like Assam, Gujarat, Maharashtra and West Bengal. Imported malaria through these returning migrant and mobile population groups contribute to the changing epidemiological situation in the country. The imported cases contribute to 60 per cent of the total malaria burden in the last three years.

Source: Government of Nepal. National Malaria Strategic Plan 2014-2025 (updated) 2020. Ministry of Health and Population, Department of Health Services, Epidemiology & Disease Control Division, Kathmandu, Nepal 2020.

As indigenous malaria cases in Nepal have declined in recent years, the number of imported cases, largely from India, has increased. Migrant labour is the primary source of importation, with greater numbers of Nepalese workers crossing into India for economic opportunities and returning with malaria infection. In the context of the increasing trend of imported cases of malaria transmission in Nepal, it is important to understand the nature of imported cases of malaria and their vulnerability.

One study that explored the association of vulnerability characteristics transmission of malaria among migrants was done in five high and moderate risk districts located in province 5 of Nepal; they are Banke, Bardiya, Dang, Kapilbastu, Nawalparasi west and Rupandehi located in Terai, the southern part of Nepal bordering India, where major malaria transmission was reported. One hundred fifty-seven migrants returning to Nepal were tested for malaria. Most of the migrants (95.6%) were coming from India, 40.8 per cent from Maharashtra, 27.6 per cent from Gujarat and 13.2 per cent from Uttar Pradesh. The majority of patients (88.7%) were infected with Plasmodium Vivax. The study highlights the fact that migrants bring infection from far and wide and can cause a local transmission cycle if not detected and treated before entering the country. This becomes critical when the country is aiming at elimination.

Employing SaTScan software to detect spatial variation in temporal trends and to generate their spatial-temporal clusters, a study found that in Nepal, most clusters of imported Malaria had an increasing trend. The most prominent cluster included Kathmandu, the capital, where Imported Malaria increased by 156.22%. Though the overall malaria burden is decreasing in Nepal, as the country, however, several spatial-temporal clusters show an increasing trend of malaria incidence⁸.

KALA-AZAR

To eliminate VL as a public health problem, the SEA Region must reduce the incidence of the disease to less than one case per 10 000 population at the sub-district level (upazila in Bangladesh, block in India) and at the district level in Nepal. Across the region, the number of cases has declined substantially, from 50 898 cases in 2007 to 8138 cases in 2015 – a drop of 83%. In 2015, fewer than 10 000 cases were reported in the SEA Region for the first time in 40 years. The region has reached the elimination 714 of the 7 in 2020, only 18 of 756 (2%) implementation units (IU) (sub-district in Bangladesh and India and district in Nepal) were above the elimination threshold. In 2015, fewer than

10 000 cases were reported in the SEA Region for the first time in 40 years. The Region has reached the elimination target in 714 of the 751 endemic units (95%) by 2019. In 2020, only 18 of 756 (2%) implementation units (IU) (sub- district in Bangladesh and India and district in Nepal) were above the elimination threshold.

Bangladesh

Kala-azar is endemic in 100 upazilas of 26 districts (>38 million people are at risk of Kala-azar), Predominantly Kala-azar (VL) and PKDL; there is no transmission of cutaneous leishmaniasis.

Bangladesh achieved KA elimination as a public health problem in 2016. Updated NSP to achieve interruption of transmission by 2025 & KA free status by 2030, preparing for WHO validation process. Cross-border collaboration is one of the pre-conditions for WHO validation.

Bangladesh achieved elimination in 100% of its IUs in 2017 and has sustained elimination since then. Bangladesh reported 569 new cases in 2015 –the lowest level in the past 20 years – with a mortality rate below 1%. Bangladesh has achieved the elimination target in over 96% of endemic *upazilas*. In Bangladesh, all the 100 VL-endemic *upazilas* reached the elimination target in 2016 and has been sustained. VL cases have declined from 87 in 2019 to 28 in 2020 and PKDL from 94 to 36 in the same period. No relapses were reported in 2020. Non-endemic *upazilas* have reported 7.3% of total confirmed cases in 2019, while for 2020, the figure is 6.5%.

There are no operational plans, and no activities are implemented to address cross border risks for Kala-Azar. There is no Kala-azar prevention, diagnosis and treatment services provided to cross border migrants /refugees/informal migrants.

Bhutan

Bhutan had reported 2 VL cases. The mean number of cases reported in the last five years has been 3. The emergence of PKDL cases has also been reported from Bhutan.

For Bhutan to successfully declare the elimination of leishmaniasis, the country needs to address the current gaps in diagnosis, treatment, vector control, implementation and those within the health systems. To identify the gaps, there should be an urgent external review of the current status of

leishmaniasis elimination in Bhutan. The review should focus on current epidemiology, institutional capacity to diagnose, treat, prevent and control activities and also systems to prevent resurgences. Further, the country needs to invest in operational and implementation research. Early diagnosis and effective treatment of both VL and PKDL are important to decrease the infection reservoir and contain the spread of infection.

India

India continues to move towards the elimination target, with 98% of IUs achieving elimination. In India, the reported number of new cases has dropped by 78% and the number of deaths by 95% between 2011 and 2015. India has achieved elimination in about 72% of sub-districts (blocks). In India, 37 blocks have yet to reach the target area in Bihar (21) and Jharkhand (16). There were 3269 cases of KA in 2019 with 43 deaths, and 2047 cases and 37 deaths in 2020. The number of KA cases decreased by 97% in 2020 as compared to 2015. Six hundred sixteen cases of PKDL were reported in 2020. Of the endemic states, Bihar reported 73% of KA cases and 58% of PKDL cases in 2020.

Till 2020, out of 633 KA endemic blocks, 617 (97.5%) blocks have achieved the elimination target. Twelve in Jharkhand and 4 in Bihar have reported >1 Kala-azar cases per 10000 population. Progress in KA elimination in India is reviewed at the highest level of administration, i.e. the office of the Prime Minister, through the Proactive Governance and Timely Implementation (PRAGATI) portal.

Three major forms of leishmaniasis are found in India: cutaneous, visceral and PKDL. Cutaneous leishmaniasis is confined to the north-western part of the country (Himanchal Pradesh, Rajasthan). In contrast, KA is endemic in 4 states, Bihar (33 districts, 458 blocks), Jharkhand (4 districts, 33 blocks), West Bengal (11 districts, 120 blocks) and Uttar Pradesh (6 districts, 22 blocks), of which contain approximately 10% of the total population at risk in India (136.5 million). In Uttar Pradesh, five more districts are categorized as previously endemic. A few sporadic and imported cases are reported in other parts of the country (Assam, Delhi, Kerala, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and Uttarakhand). Blocks (third subnational level) are the lowest administrative implementation units covered by the KA elimination programme.

The number of KA cases has decreased by 97% (2048 cases in 2020) since the start of intensified KA activities in 1992 (77,102 cases), and the number of deaths has been reduced from 1419 in 1992 to 58 in 2018 and further decreases to 43 in 2019 and 37 in 2020 (provisional). The case fatality rate was 1.3% in 2019 and 1.8% in 2020. More KA cases are found among males (57–60% of cases) and socially disadvantaged classes (40% of cases). The proportion of KA-affected children (≤ 15 years) among all KA cases has decreased from 39% in 2013 to 27% in 2020. Of all the endemic states, only Bihar reported 73% (1500/2048) of KA cases and 58% (361/617) of PKDL cases in 2020.¹⁴ Data on patient follow-up and cure rates were not available before 2015; however, improved surveillance shows that, in 2019, a total of 3024 patients were followed-up in Bihar and Jharkhand, of whom 2946 were cured (97%). Some of the key challenges in cross border activities include:

1. Cross border notification of diagnosed cases and follow-ups
2. Non-existent systems communications and collaborations
3. Integrated and synchronized approach for implementation of interventions for case management, entomological surveillance, vector control and monitoring and evaluation
4. Joint frameworks for eliminations across countries
5. Involvement of civil societies and local leadership across borders
6. Outbreaks reporting with effective surveillance and warning systems

Nepal

In 2019, 5 districts in Nepal were confirmed to have local transmission and increased their IUs from 18 to 23. In 2020, 2 IUs in Nepal crossed the elimination threshold; Nepal has made significant progress, having eliminated VL at the district level and sustaining these gains for three years, will move to the validation process. In 2019 Nepal had 186 cases in 50 of the 77 districts. No endemic districts were above the elimination threshold^{9 10 11}.

VL has been reported in Nepal since 1980, but CL was reported very recently. From 2016 to 2019, 42 CL cases were reported from 26 different hospitals to EDCD, which had been diagnosed on the basis of clinical presentation and laboratory findings.

Map of Nepal showing visceral leishmaniasis (VL) endemic, endemic doubtful and non-districts with reported CL cases. Red color shows the VL-endemic districts (n = 18), green color shows non-endemic districts (n = 9) while the rest are endemic doubtful districts (n = 50). Numbers indicate CL cases distribution by district (n = 26) in the present study. Asterisk shows newly added endemic districts (n = 6)

This study has highlighted the issue of important neglected diseases, and it is expected that it will draw the attention of the policymakers to formulate a protocol for the effective surveillance, management and control of leishmaniasis. If CL cases are increased, it will adversely impact the leishmaniasis elimination in the Indian subcontinent due to open borders shared with Nepal. Such a growing number of CL cases from a country embarking on leishmaniasis elimination is certainly a regional concern too.

TUBERCULOSIS

Bangladesh

Bangladesh is ranked seventh amongst the 30 high TB-burden countries and accounts for 3.6% of the global total, and among the high multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) burden countries, Bangladesh is ranked 14th. The estimated incidence of TB per 100,000 is 221 in Bangladesh, with a mortality rate of 24 per 100,000 population. Approximately 80% of all TB cases in Bangladesh are pulmonary TB. The Global TB Report 2020 estimated that 0.7% of new cases and 11% of previously treated patients are found to be positive for multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB), which has an incidence rate of 2.0 per 100,000 population in Bangladesh.

TB treatment coverage increased to 81 per cent in 2019; deaths among TB/HIV-negative patients decreased to 24 per 100,000 in 2019, and a high treatment success rate of more than 90 per cent for drug-susceptible TB (DS-TB) cases has been maintained. However, while there has been an increase in TB treatment coverage, an estimated 70,000 TB patients remain undiagnosed each year.

Additionally, only an estimated 40 per cent of drug-resistant TB (DR-TB) cases are being enrolled on proper treatment regimens. In 2020, an estimated 360,000 people developed tuberculosis, and close to 130,000 people with tuberculosis could not be identified -missing; 710 people who developed tuberculosis were co-infected with HIV; 84 were diagnosed with both HIV infection and tuberculosis disease, and close to 44,000 people died because of TB^{12 13}.

Bhutan

Bhutan is considered a relatively low Tuberculosis (TB) burden country in the South-East Asia Region with an estimated incidence rate of 149 per 100,000 population. The sustained efforts of the government towards TB control have led to a substantial increase in TB notifications and improvement in diagnostics, adherence, and treatment outcomes. The treatment success rate for all forms of TB was 95% in 2018 and 98% for Multi-Drug Resistance TB (MDR-TB) for the 2017 cohort, comparatively higher than many countries in the region. However, with high case detection gaps and an increasing number of MDR-TB, controlling TB continues to be a major public health concern in Bhutan. The prevalence of MDR-TB was reported at 13% in new cases and 20% amongst the retreatment cases in 2018, which are high than WHO estimates. In 2020 an estimated 1,300 people developed tuberculosis, eight developed tuberculosis and were co-infected with HIV, six were diagnosed with both HIV infection and tuberculosis¹⁴.

India

India accounts for about one-quarter of the global TB burden. Among the 30 high TB and high multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) burden countries, India is ranked first in World Health Organization's Global Tuberculosis Report, 2019. In 2019, the estimated TB incidence was 2,640,000, and an estimated 436,000 people died from TB, including about 10,000 HIV-positive people with TB. In 2019, India notified 2,162,323 TB cases—a 13 percent increase from 2018—with a large proportion (31 percent) coming from private sector notifications. While significant progress has been made, if India is to eliminate TB and detect the approximately 478,000 'missing' cases, it will need to accelerate that progress even further¹⁵.

In 2020, about 2,590,000 (estimated) people developed tuberculosis, and close to 970,000 were missed. Nearly 53,000 people who developed tuberculosis were also co-infected with HIV, and about 30,500 people were diagnosed with both HIV infection and tuberculosis disease. Close to 493,000 people had died due to tuberculosis¹⁶.

Myanmar

Among the 30 high TB burden countries, Myanmar is ranked tenth; and among the high multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) burden countries Myanmar is ranked ninth. The most recent TB prevalence study, conducted in 2017-2018, indicates that the overall TB prevalence declined by 35 percent since 2009-2010. Burma is the only Asian country on track to achieve the World Health Organization's (WHO) 2020 End TB strategy incidence reduction milestone of 20 percent, with an annual reduction of TB incidence of 4.5 percent between 2015-2020. TB remains a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in Burma. In 2019, of the estimated 174,000 TB cases, 134,501 cases (77 percent) were notified to the NTP; and of the estimated 10,000 MDR-TB cases, only 3,232 MDR-TB cases were notified, of which 2,915 MDR-TB cases were enrolled in treatment. Of the total notified TB cases less than one percent are TB/HIV co-infected. The number of MDR-TB cases detected remains far below the estimated incidence. While case detection has increased in recent years to as high as 77 percent of the estimated incidence, the number of missing cases remains significant. An estimated 4.9 percent of the new TB cases and 18 percent of the retreatment cases are rifampicin-resistant (RR-TB) or MDR-TB. The treatment success rate (TSR) in Burma reaches 88 percent for drug-susceptible TB (DS-TB) and 79 percent for MDR-TB. Only 45 percent of TB cases notified were bacteriologically-confirmed cases in 2019. Overall, the TB case fatality ratio is 13 percent^{17 18}.

Nepal

Nepal has completed the first-ever nationally representative tuberculosis (TB) survey to understand the actual disease burden (data on how many are suffering from the disease) in the general population. The survey showed around 117,000 people are living in Nepal with TB. The TB incidence (new cases) was found to be higher (1.6 times) than previously thought. Also seen was an estimated annual reduction of new TB cases (by 3% in the last decade), and this decline is better than the global annual decline rate (1.5%-2%).

In 2020, 69,000 estimated number of people developed tuberculosis, only 32,474 cases were reported, around 54% of cases were missed to be diagnosed and treated. An estimated 1,400 people who developed TB were co-infected with HIV infection, and 123 people were diagnosed with both HIV infection and TB disease. An estimated 16,000 people died because of TB¹⁹.

TB in Migrant populations

Migrants currently play an important role in determining the current epidemiology of TB in countries where they are settled. The incidence in the countries of origin is the strongest predictor of TB incidence in migrants. Migrants have a high risk of acquiring TB before migration as they are exposed in their country of origin to several risk factors for TB infection and progression. TB may occur in migrants as a consequence of a reactivation of a Latent TB Infection (LTBI) acquired in the country of origin but may also occur because of a new infection acquired in the host country after resettlement or during travel in the country of origin. Moreover, after migration, migrants are exposed to additional risk factors for acquiring or re-activating TB infection, such as poverty, stressful living conditions, social inequalities, over-crowded housing, malnutrition, substance abuse, and limited access to health care. An increased risk of TB is still present in second-generation migrants, in whom a link to endemic countries persists after migration through social networks or travel in the country of origin²⁰.

Migration is giving rise to a growing proportion of TB patients of foreign origin in many countries of the WHO SEA Region, and this may jeopardize the attainment of the WHO's End TB strategy targets for 2030 in the region.

The WHO emphasizes that all migrants, regardless of legal status, should have full access to quality services for TB prevention, diagnosis and care, stressing that persons diagnosed with TB should be promptly treated and that migrants from high- to low-incidence countries should be considered for systematic TB screening.

The number of Nepali who migrate to India to work continues to grow each year, in part due to the ease of crossing the open border between Nepal and India and the relative affordability of travelling there. Reliable information on cross-border mobility is not available as there is no proper reporting system, but estimates suggest that 1.6 million Nepali work in India as seasonal labourers. Some studies have documented that Nepali migrants in India are vulnerable to many health problems, including infectious diseases such as HIV, tuberculosis (TB), and malaria^{21 22}.

There is very little literature available on tuberculosis in migrants across the borders in focus five South Asian countries in this review. Studies have been done in Europe and the USA to assess the burden in the migrants, especially those coming from high to low burden countries.

For undocumented migrants, the International Union against Tuberculosis and Lung Disease specifically recommends that easy access to TB diagnosis is ensured and that no deportation takes place until the end of treatment. In some countries, however, denial of entry of TB suspects is enforced, and if vulnerable individuals, such as asylum seekers or undocumented migrants, are diagnosed with TB, they may be extradited without continuity of TB treatment. For TB patients crossing national borders, there is often a lack of continuity of treatment due to a lack of patient-centred approaches and/or availability of sound transfer mechanisms.

Cross-border control in Europe

Countries of the WHO European region face an array of challenges in cross-border TB control. These include limited access to early TB diagnosis, a lack of continuity of care for TB patients when they move to another country, and no or little information to the health providers in the countries of transit, destination and return. In addition, there is often a lack of appropriate and/or adequate information for patients as to their rights, availability of health services, coverage entitlements and accessibility of services. In some countries, there is no provision for the coverage of the costs of TB diagnosis and treatment, which mainly rely on individual payment. Accessing healthcare can be a special challenge for migrants. These are further complicated by cultural and language barriers, stigma and fear of deportation. The fear of discrimination and, furthermore, of deportation because of TB may result in the hiding symptoms and delay in diagnosis, the commencement of self-treatment or even a treatment already started to be discontinued, which can eventually lead to the development of (multi) drug-resistant TB. Deporting migrants can cause the discontinuation of their treatment.

The shortcomings of TB care across borders stem from lack of coordination between the member states of the WHO European region, inadequate legal framework and insufficiencies of health systems to deal with cross-border TB control and care, including accurate and adequate data collection.

In spite of the information available on TB cases notified among migrants in Europe (both in terms of absolute numbers and proportions) obtained through the country, surveillance and on the net migration rate in Europe, not much is known about cross-border TB control.

Although TB is not listed on the group of diseases that constitute a public health emergency, the network developed for IHR could be used in promoting the continuum of care of TB patients. IHR is generally applicable to trans-national TB transmission; thus, notification of TB to WHO could be considered if the episode raises an important concern to international public health²³.

HIV

Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, there were an estimated 14000 (12000-160000) PLHIV in 2018, with an adult (15–49 years) HIV prevalence of <0.1% (<0.1-<0.1%). This includes less than 500 Children Living with HIV (CLHIV, 0-14), accounting for 3.5% of the total PLHIV estimates. There were 4800 (7600-9900) women living with HIV (15+ years), constituting around 34% of the total estimated PLHIV. There were 1600 (1400-1800) new HIV infections in 2018. There were 580 (<500-680) AIDS-related deaths in the year 2018. HIV incidence was estimated at 0.01 per 1,000 populations in 2018. In the year 2019, there were 53 Percent of people living with HIV who knew their status, and 31 Percent of people who knew their status were on ART. 84 Percent of people were on ART who had achieved viral suppression in the year 2019. One of the challenges is to start a prevention program with migrants.

Bhutan

In Bhutan, there were an estimated 1300 (670-2700) PLHIV in 2018 (Figure 13), with an adult (15–49 years) HIV prevalence of <0.3% (0.1-0.5%). There were less than 500. (<500-750) women are living with HIV (15+ years), constituting around 38% of the total estimated PLHIV. There were <100 (<100-<500) new HIV infections in 2018. There were <100 (<100-<200) AIDS-related deaths in the year 2018. HIV incidence was estimated at 0.11 per 1,000 populations in 2018. In the year 2018, there were 47 Percent of people living with HIV knew their status and 37 % of people who knew their status were on ART.²⁴

India

As per the recently released India HIV Estimation 2020 report, overall, the estimated adult (15–49 years) HIV prevalence trend has been declining in India since the epidemic's peak in the year 2000 and has been stabilizing in recent years. The estimate for this indicator was 0.22% (0.17–0.29%) in 2020.

In the same year, HIV prevalence among adult males (15–49 years) was estimated at 0.23% (0.18%–0.31%) among males and among adult females at 0.20% (0.15%–0.26%).

At the sub-national level, three states with the highest adult HIV prevalence were from the north-eastern part of the country, namely Mizoram (2.37%), followed by Nagaland (1.44%) and Manipur (1.15%). Andhra Pradesh (0.66%) also has an estimated adult HIV prevalence higher than the national average. Nationally, there was an estimated 23.19 lakh (18.33 lakh– 29.78 lakh) PLHIV in 2020. Nationally, 51,000 (34,800–77,200) deaths among PLHIV in 2020 of which 63 % AIDS-related deaths were estimated in the year 2020²⁵.

In India, there were estimated 23.19 lakh (18.33 lakh– 29.78 lakh) PLHIV in 2020, with an adult (15–49 years) HIV prevalence of 0.22% (0.17–0.29%). This includes around 79,000 CLHIV, accounting for 3.4% of the total PLHIV estimates. There were 9,94,000 women living with HIV (15+ years), constituting around 44% of the total estimated 15+ years PLHIV. There were 69,22,000 (37.03 thousand–121.50 thousand) new HIV infections in 2019, which has declined by 37% since 2010. There were 58.96 thousand (33.61 thousand – 102.16 thousand) AIDS-related deaths in the year 2019, which has declined by 66% since 2010 and by 78% since attaining its peak in 2005. HIV incidence was estimated at 0.05 per 1,000 uninfected populations in 2019. Around 20.52 thousand (14.98 thousand – 28.13 thousand) pregnant women were estimated to be in need of PMTCT. In the year 2018, there were 79.4 Percent of people living with HIV who know their status, 82 Percent of people who know their status who are on ART and 68 per cent of people on ART who achieve viral suppression.

Myanmar

Around 240,000 people were living with HIV in Myanmar in 2019. In the same year, an estimated 7,700 people died from AIDS-related illnesses. The increased antiretroviral treatment coverage has seen the number of people dying of AIDS-related illnesses fall by a third between 2010-2018. The number of new HIV infections has also fallen by a similar proportion during this time.

After Thailand, Myanmar has the second-highest HIV prevalence in Southeast Asia at 0.7%. Myanmar is one of 35 countries that together account for 90% of new infections globally. The severity of the country's HIV epidemic resulted in UNAIDS classifying it as a 'fast-track' country in 2014 in order to help catalyse the rapid scale-up of its HIV prevention, testing and treatment programmes, although progress in these areas has been uneven.

In 2018, Myanmar reported 10,000 new infections. Although this number remains steady compared to the years before, observations show the annual rate of infections is no longer declining at the same rate it did between 2000 and 2010. Although official testing, treatment and viral suppression target data for UNAIDS' 90-90-90 targets is incomplete, the current estimates suggest around 76% of all people living with HIV in Myanmar were on treatment as of 2019. Of those on treatment, 95% are virally suppressed, equivalent to 72% of all people were living with HIV.

Nepal

In Nepal, there were estimated 30000 (26000-34000) PLHIV in 2019 (Figure 24), with an adult (15–49 years) HIV prevalence of 0.1% (0.1-0.1%). This includes less than 1200 Children Living with HIV (CLHIV, 0-14), accounting for 4 % of the total PLHIV estimates. There were 11000 (10000-13000) women living with HIV (15+ years), constituting around 37% of the total estimated PLHIV. There were 790 (700-870) new HIV infections in 2019. There were 740 (570-1000) AIDS-related deaths in the year 2019. HIV incidence was estimated at 0.03 per 1,000 populations in 2019. In the year 2019, there were 78 Percent of people living with HIV who knew their status, 63 Percent of people who knew their status who were on ART and 55 percent of people on ART who achieve viral suppression²⁶.

Migration and HIV

The role of migrants and mobile populations (MMPs) in the spread and control of HIV is increasingly being recognized and understood. While migration does not automatically equal HIV vulnerability, and not all MMPs are at increased risk of HIV as a result of their mobility, in many contexts, MMPs are exposed to a unique set of socio-cultural, economic and environmental factors that render them more vulnerable to HIV including lack of access to health services, information and environments that are conducive to engaging in high-risk behaviour. Many of the underlying factors sustaining mobility, including unequal distribution of resources, unemployment, socio-economic instability and political unrest, are also determinants of increased risk of HIV.

Challenges in addressing HIV vulnerabilities among MMPs include lack of migrant-specific data to inform decision-making, continued stigma and discriminatory attitudes towards migrants, including limited access to services based on legal and/or HIV status, lack of recognition of migrants in national AIDS strategies, and inadequate comprehensive services reaching mobile populations²⁷.

HIV among Migrants

Myanmar is home to over 100 different ethnic groups and shares its borders with two of the most populated countries in the world, India and China, in addition to Bangladesh, Laos and Thailand. The census in 2014 estimated that over 11 million residents (approximately 20% of the population) had migrated internally or externally. There is little comprehensive information available on HIV prevalence or risk behaviours associated with the migrant population.

In 2014, the UN's International Organization for Migration's data project found that 18% of people identifying as migrants in Mon and Kayin states were HIV positive – although it is difficult to assess if the point of infection happened within the country. However, it is broadly assumed that migrants might face residency and social restrictions that limit their access to HIV programme services, as well as other forms of healthcare. Since 2014, HIV awareness campaigns that target large migrant populations have been created to address these issues. At that time, it was proposed to develop specific packages for people near transit points, in addition to cross-border referral mechanisms and agreements to strengthen access to health services in destination countries.

Since August 2017, almost a million Rohingya people have migrated to neighbouring Bangladesh, fleeing from internal unrest. Most are now living in the Cox's Bazar district of Bangladesh, where they are particularly vulnerable to HIV and other STIs due to multiple and overlapping forms of discrimination and abuse. Sexual violence and exploitation are common, and the area is also a drug trafficking route, all of which increases people's vulnerability to HIV. As of March 2019, around 320 in the Cox's Bazar refugee camp had been diagnosed with HIV, and it is likely more people are living with HIV but are undiagnosed. Of those diagnosed, 277 are being followed, and 19 have died²⁸.

Migrants may acquire HIV in their country of destination or while in transit and face specific vulnerability to HIV related to their status as a migrant. In South-East Asia, HIV prevalence among migrants to Thailand from Cambodia, Myanmar, southern China and Vietnam is up to four times the HIV prevalence among the general population. The highest prevalence among migrants in Thailand was found in the fishing industry, with rates of 2% among fishers and 2.3% among fishery workers, compared to an HIV prevalence of 1.1% and 0.74% among factory workers and farmworkers, respectively. Studies indicate that women who have been internationally trafficked and forced into sexual exploitation also have a significantly higher HIV prevalence and an increased vulnerability and exposure to violence. In Mumbai, India, almost a quarter (22.9%) of sex-trafficked women and girls are HIV-positive. HIV prevalence is 38% among sex-trafficked women and girls returning from India to Nepal^{29 30}.

POLICY AND PROGRAMMES FOR CROSS-BORDER CONTROL OF PRIORITY INFECTIOUS DISEASES AND ACCESS TO HEALTH-CARE

MALARIA

The Global Technical Strategy for Malaria 2016–2030 sets the target of reducing the global malaria burden by 90% by 2030. The strategic framework comprises three major pillars, with two supporting elements: a robust enabling environment. Multisectoral approaches and cross-border and regional collaborations are essential components of enabling an environment. It advises that effective cross-border collaboration between national programmes must be initiated and strengthened to ensure optimal intervention coverage in the border areas.

Regional Action Plan 2017–2030. Towards 0. Malaria-Free South-East Asia Region

The Regional action plan has five objectives. Creating and implementing mechanisms for cross-border control of malaria will be able to contribute to all five goals. Cross-border migration (which is often uncontrolled) between malaria-endemic and -receptive areas is a key issue in the South East Asia Region, both for malaria elimination and for the prevention of the spread of multi-drug resistant *P. falciparum* parasites. Meaningful intercountry coordination and cooperation should therefore be promoted as a priority. A variety of measures might be appropriate, including:

- i. regular exchange of all malaria-related information of mutual interest (information exchange could be facilitated through an innovative information technology platform, which links countries and allows them restricted access to key information from around the Region);
- ii. prompt notification of any unusual malaria situations related to cross-border movements;
- iii. regular border meetings both at district and national levels;
- iv. joint mapping of malaria-relevant cross-border migration patterns;
- v. joint development of special evidence-based interventions for high-risk cross-border migrant populations and border-related situations; and associated interregional training.

Real-time monitoring and rapid sharing of information, particularly between neighbouring countries, will help to ensure a coordinated regional approach to any malaria-related issues that have cross-border implications. Providing services for mobile and migrant populations is essential. Provincial-level malaria units should include mobile teams for managing malaria in mobile and migrant populations, and ideally, these teams should be authorised to work across borders when necessary³¹.

Bangladesh

“National Strategic Plan 2015-2020” of Bangladesh aims at achieving the goal of malaria elimination- ‘zero cases and zero death’ by 2020 in the country. It provides the framework and technical guidance for the National Malaria Control Programme (NMCP) to plan and implement interventions for achieving pre-determined goals, objectives and targets.

The strategy identifies the border-belt areas in the north and northeast of the country to have an epidemic potential for malaria. The similar terrain and geophysical condition across the borders have posed an increased threat to malaria transmission due to trans-border population movements. It also acknowledges that the World Health Organization (WHO) has been extending continued technical backstop services in matters related to developing and updating normative guidelines, tools and strategies, and more critical areas of drugs and insecticide resistance monitoring, programme evaluations, and international and cross-border collaboration.

It identifies traditional *Jhum cultivators*, forest-dwellers, refugees, travellers from non-endemic areas, and mobile populations, the most at-risk groups due to lack of adequate protection for mosquito bites and adoption of personal protection measures. They are also at a higher risk of malaria transmission in the border areas due to cross-border movement/migration across international boundaries with the

eastern states of India and part of Myanmar. It has also budgeted for cross border collaboration and tracking of the mobile population³².

Bhutan

Bhutan's revised plan conforms with the WHO Global Malaria Programme (GMP) and Southeast Asia Regional Malaria elimination action plan. It calls for strengthening actions oriented to improve cross border coordination and collaboration at all levels. Bhutan and India have always enjoyed an exemplary friendship and also conducted regular meetings to enhance peace and security across the borders, both at the local and central levels. These platforms can be expanded to address public health-related diseases of cross-border origin. There is a need to have the joint bilateral initiative in addressing cross border malaria through the proper exchange of information, researches and other malaria control interventions.

Action plans:

- i. Consultative and coordination meeting between Bhutan and India for planning bilateral collaboration and coordination for malaria elimination interventions across the border
- ii. Establish joint bilateral coordination mechanism for addressing cross border malaria elimination issues and information sharing network
- iii. Incorporate malaria elimination agenda in the existing forums such as WHO, SAARC & Indo-Bhutan Friendship Association
- iv. Advocacy with MoFA and MoHCA to initiate discussion on cross border collaboration
- v. Putting malaria agenda in local government cross-border coordination meetings
- vi. Explore and initiate institutional linkage for collaboration with NGOs like Rotary Club, Lions Club and Red Cross Society in the border areas
- vii. Study visits to the collaborating institutions for malaria networking
- viii. Meeting of a national program of two countries months to share data and experiences and to strategically plan joint control/elimination activities across the border³³.

India

India's National Framework for Malaria Elimination (NFME) 2016–2030 identifies the following activities for cross border collaboration:

1. Screening of populations at international border crossings.
2. Training of security personnel at international border crossings with the provision of diagnostic and treatment facilities.
3. Implementation of a mechanism for monthly data collection from international border areas and integration into national MIS.
4. Joint planning and implementation of malaria prevention and control activities with neighbouring countries.
5. Sharing of information and policies for malaria prevention and control with neighbouring countries.
6. Harmonisation of policies and synchronisation of activities for malaria elimination in bordering countries.
7. Support from multilateral agencies to facilitate cooperation and information sharing between countries.

Myanmar

Myanmar's malaria control strategy is in accordance with the Global Malaria Control Strategy promoted by WHO. They also reflect the Regional Strategy for Malaria Control in the WHO Region for South- East Asia (WHO/SEARO 2005).

Myanmar, in its NSP, has emphasised the mobile and migrant population. NSP mentions cross border control of malaria in its supporting element: Strengthening the enabling environment by multisectoral approaches and cross-border and regional collaborations. Key factors leading to inaccessibility to healthcare have been considered, including language (often only a small proportion of people from ethnic minority groups speak the national language making communication of health messages problematic); remoteness (malaria transmission tends to be most intense in remote areas, commonly

along borders, where access to both public and private sector healthcare services is relatively limited); poverty (the populations living in or passing through these remote areas are generally some of the poorest in the country); marginalisation (ethnic minority groups and migrants are amongst the most marginalised groups in the country); and mobility (the high mobility of some individuals means that they may have moved to non-endemic areas, where health workers are less likely to be familiar with malaria when symptoms first appear).

Therefore, well-targeted malaria control efforts by their nature cater to the needs of some of the least privileged^{34 35} areas, where health workers are less likely to be familiar with malaria (when symptoms first appear). Well-targeted malaria control efforts by their nature, therefore, cater to the needs of some of the least privileged^{36 37}.

Nepal

Imported malaria is one of the main threats to achievement and maintenance of elimination, with the greatest risk for countries neighbouring high-endemic areas such as Nepal with an open border with India. Nepal has instituted screening at checkpoints, cross-notification of cases, coordination of entomological monitoring and vector control measures, harmonised IEC/BCC for migrants, etc. are being put in place to address the cross-border issue of malaria in Nepal.

Its strategy proposes to strengthen existing border check posts to prevent the importation of malaria cases. It aims to provide adequate human resources at the border check post and make them functional during the transmission season and outbreaks across the border. Some of the components include:

- i. Operational research to map migrant and mobile populations will be conducted along with social networking,
- ii. Developing awareness through IEC about malaria prevention and increase in early health-seeking behaviours,
- iii. Enhanced surveillance and increase in healthcare access through Malaria Mobile Clinics in high and moderate risk areas
- iv. Cross-border meeting to exchange information and develop a joint operational plan
- v. Monitoring of joint operations across borders³⁸.

KALA-AZAR

The SEA Region is the only WHO region to have a Kala-azar elimination strategy globally. The Regional document, while laying down the strategic framework for eliminating Kala-azar, points out that not much progress has been made on cross-border collaboration, where about 40% of cases of Kala- Azar occur. It stresses the strong need for urgent cross-border collaboration.

It recommends signing a memorandum of understanding for intercountry cooperation and cross-border collaboration; and WHO to assist in intercountry Task Force Meeting, cross-border meetings, and coordination with partners³⁹.

Bangladesh

Its strategic guidelines mention cross border collaboration in IRS operations to interrupt the transmission of the disease. Simultaneously, IRS operations can be mounted since the areas under the South-East Asia Regional Kala-azar elimination programme have similar seasonal factors.

There is no reference to treatment to be offered to migrants.

India

The Govt of India launched an Accelerated Plan for Kala-azar Elimination, 2017, which emphasizes diagnosis of Kala-azar, treatment of patients, and the elimination strategy. The national strategy is a multi-pronged approach that is in line with the WHO Regional Strategic Framework for the elimination of Kala-azar for the SEA region. But does not identify actions on cross border collaboration or access to treatment for migrants⁴⁰.

However, in its report, the Independent Assessment Mission of Kala-azar programme in India, 2019 emphasises that one of the pre-conditions to be fulfilled by endemic countries is cross border coordination. The team did not observe any mechanism of border surveillance and cross border notification in any state. The Mission's report cautioned that the whole region is very vulnerable, and the risk of re-introduction of the disease is huge where it has been eliminated. There are many examples of imported cases of KA and recent introductions in countries that were previously free of KA, like Bhutan, where the first case was detected in 2009. Although the trans-border issue has been recognised systematically in most meetings and documents, few high-level meetings have already happened in practice. As a result of the lack of agreements between countries, cross-border cases have minimal data sharing.

The KAMIS can record KA and PKDL cases through cross-border information. The report has suggested short and medium-term measures to strengthen cross border collaboration in any state. The Mission's report cautioned that the whole region is very vulnerable, and the risk of re-introduction of the disease is huge where it has been eliminated. There are many examples of imported cases of KA and recent introductions in countries that were previously free of KA, like Bhutan, where the first case was detected in 2009. Although the trans-border issue has been recognised systematically in most meetings and documents, few high-level meetings have already happened in practice.

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Nepal

Nepal's Strategic Guidelines on the Kala-azar Elimination Programme, 2014 mentions the need for Cross border collaboration in IRS operations, as it can interrupt the transmission of the disease. It has been suggested that for this, simultaneous IRS operations can be mounted since the areas under the have similar seasonal factors⁴¹.

No strategy documents could be accessed for Bhutan and Myanmar.

TUBERCULOSIS

WHO

Policy Framework

The WHO Stop TB Strategy calls for more concerted efforts by Member States, national TB control programmes (NTPs) and development partners to protect poor and vulnerable subgroups from TB, TB/HIV, and multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB). The WHO Regional Office for the Western Pacific, in consultation with key stakeholders, has adapted the consensus-based global framework on migrant health for migrant TB control. It offers a direction for countries to gradually move towards, subject to their existing national laws and regulations. It is the product of a regional consultation of health and immigration officials from the Region. The policy and legal framework state that:

- i. National TB control policies should promote universal and equitable access to TB diagnosis and treatment for all TB patients regardless of residential status, nationality or legal status, subject to national laws and resource constraints.
- ii. National TB guidelines and manuals should endeavour to consider the specific needs of the migrant populations.
- iii. TB status should not affect a patients' legal or contractual status to the extent allowed by national laws and regulations.

The key action suggestions are:

- a. Conduct advocacy and public education efforts to build support among the government and other stakeholders, including private medical providers and employers, on the importance of ensuring access to TB care for migrant populations.
- b. Promote the availability of adequate resources for migrant TB policy development, formulation of strategies and programme implementation subject to national laws and regulations.
- c. Encourage policy coherence between NTPs and other relevant sectors (for example, immigration, labour)⁴².

SAARC

The SAARC Tuberculosis and HIV/AIDS Centre (STAC), a Regional Centre of SAARC Kathmandu, Nepal, has developed a SAARC Regional Strategy for Elimination of TB. The only reference it makes to the migrant population is that access to health care can be affected by social and political factors such as stigma and discrimination, and the availability of cross-border services for migrants, and economic barriers such as the cost of transport, hence efforts be made to improve access⁴³.

Bangladesh

Plan for TB control could not be accessed. A document of Public-Private Mix for the treatment of tuberculosis focuses on integrated, patient-centred care and prevention, bold policies and supportive systems, and intensified research and innovation as defined in the WHO Global Tuberculosis Report, 2020⁴⁴.

Bhutan

Bhutan's National Strategy Plan, 0227-2023, provides free of cost services for TB diagnosis, treatment and care to migrant groups (vulnerable groups) be provided. Since the number of migrant workers in districts bordering India and in road construction and hydropower projects is rapidly increasing, there is an urgent need to develop appropriate risk assessment interventions. Further, it is not always possible to establish a diagnostic centre in remote areas with small pockets of populations. Such populations will be screened using clinical methods, and all presumptive cases will be offered chest X-rays and rapid molecular tests at the nearest centre⁴⁵.

India

As per the *National Strategic Plan to eliminate TB in India*, several strategies have been put forward for intensifying TB control activities in key border areas:

1. Mapping and identification of priority populations (migrants) across the country: Establishment of TB surveillance system at district, state and national level in the border areas; Strengthen existing mechanism of registration of TB patients; Enlist migrant camps and locations; Capture data on systematic screening in such risk groups; Studies to explore vulnerable groups for TB to facilitate targeted interventions (Drivers, migrants, miners etc.).
2. Developing interventions for a sustainable disease-free environment for migrant labourers in the industry
3. Customised advocacy and communication for the defined priority population.
4. Barriers to utilisation of RNTCP services in high-risk populations be addressed, including migrant groups⁴⁶.

Myanmar

Myanmar is the only Asian country on track to achieve the WHO's 2020 End TB strategy incidence of 20 % reduction milestone. Myanmar's national strategic document specifies cross border TB control to be a part of essential interventions for migrants.

- i. Map partners/actors with access to known migrant populations, including internally displaced. Establish a plan to reach all migrant communities, including building capacity for TB screening and referral and potentially treatment support, by partners. Partners will include non-state and non-health actors having gained the trust of the local communities, e.g. ethnic health committees and

faith-based organisations. Tap into partnership network used for malaria control to expand capacity for TB. Aim for national coverage using a network of partners linked to the NTP.

- ii. Expand the sites for regularly scheduled ACF using mobile clinics. Identify and prioritise townships not routinely reached by NTP and where partners can support screening and treatment follow-up.
- iii. Develop a strategy to address cross-border TB, mapping partner engagement to ensure full coverage of the border populations and migrant workers. Conduct a study of care-seeking among border populations to understand the complexities and needs for services.
- iv. Develop and implement an information, education and communication strategy to raise awareness among migrant communities, partners working with them, and surrounding health workers (public and private)
- v. Develop “migrant friendly” approaches to be implemented by BHS, Voluntary Health Staff (VHS), including CHWs and Auxiliary Midwives (AMW) as part of an outreach in migrant communities. Build awareness and knowledge of health staff regarding the care practices and needs of migrant communities.
- vi. Strengthen referral mechanisms between townships for migrants. Develop a mobile application/tool for supporting the transfer of migrant patients between care sites.
- vii. Strengthen the recording and reporting system to capture migrant status⁴⁷.

Nepal

The National Strategic Plan for TB prevention could not be accessed.

HIV-AIDS

Bangladesh

Bangladesh’s National Strategic Plan for HIV and AIDS response 2018-2022 will continue to allocate funds to prevention among key populations and international migrants and care, treatment and support for PLHIV to minimise the spread of HIV and the impact of AIDS on the individual, family, community, and society so that HIV is ended in Bangladesh by 2030. The plan recommends responding to emerging risk groups which include international migrant workers. Migrants and their spouses comprise a significant portion of all detected cases, and effective interventions for this group are urgently needed. Reaching migrants is a priority focus group for HIV prevention. The migrants include international as well as cross- border⁴⁸.

Bhutan

Bhutan’s HIV NSP highlights that people who are mobile may not receive appropriate HIV services due to their specific characteristics of being away from their communities for most of the year. It focuses on identifying and reaching mobile, floating and migrant populations, including nomads, with a targeted prevention intervention package of services⁴⁹.

India

Recognising the importance of migrants in the spread of HIV, India’s National AIDS Control Organization (NACO) had in 2010 issued a policy, strategy and operational plan for HIV interventions for migrants, which also included a strategic framework⁵⁰.

India’s National Strategic Plan, 2017-2024, recognises migrants as ‘key populations. It suggests revitalising IEC strategies by shifting to interactive formats, harnessing channels for specific audience segments such as migrants, upgrading the IEC material and making it relevant to the changing context and new programme guidelines. It aims to provide targeted interventions (TIs) among KP and others ‘at risk groups.

It recognises that the linkage of sub-set of populations to treatment had been weak. ART adherence among KPs is a major challenge⁴⁵. Additionally, the HIV and TB co-infection rates are higher with low uptake of services. The existing NACO database on migrants called Migrant Service Delivery System (MSDS) may also be mined for providing differential prevention and care services to population groups within the broad migrants' category. Testing, treatment and follow-up are all provided under the Programme are free of cost⁵¹.

Myanmar

Migrants are included in 90% of the priority population in policy programmes. No comprehensive information on HIV prevalence or risk behaviours in migrants and mobile populations in Myanmar, but programme data suggest that HIV is an issue among migrant groups. It recommends expanding testing and scaling up HIV combination prevention interventions for priority populations, including migrants. It recommends linking enrolment with TB services, developing and implementing a system to initiate or continue ART for returned migrants living with HIV and formalising links with cross-border initiatives in key areas (Myanmar–Thailand border).

Myanmar has implemented different models to improve ART enrolment and retention for each key and priority population. Integrate TB–HIV testing and treatment programmes for all priority populations, including prisoners, miners and migrants. The national strategic plan document recommends reviewing/monitoring the HIV situation in special economic zones and industrial zones, which attract a large influx of migrants/workers and direct resources to provide services as necessary (including through mobile vans, at factory clinics/sites/referrals). Support Myanmar's participation in regional coordination (i.e., ASEAN), particularly with countries that share border areas, particularly in areas with migrant flows, Myanmar's collaboration with neighbouring countries to strengthen internal and cross-border referral mechanisms and data sharing will be a priority.

This will help address gaps in referral systems for migrants and facilitate the initiation or continuation of ART for returned migrants (including deported migrants) living with HIV. This will be supported by increased awareness and uptake of existing social security and health insurance schemes in countries of origin and destination, including by addressing barriers at the point of care, such as discrimination. In addition, collaboration among the Ministry of Health and Sports, the Ministry of Labour, Immigration and Population services, and sending and receiving governments, to simplify and improve access to formal migration mechanisms that guarantee decent work, labour rights and comprehensive health entitlements for all migrants, and improve referral mechanisms for migrants⁵².

Nepal

The national AIDS strategy guides Nepal's response to HIV and sexually transmitted infections. The goal is to focus and intensify good quality services for the key population in key locations, adopting zero tolerance to discrimination, ensuring an adequate HIV response, including addressing migration and mobility and eliminating vertical transmission of HIV and keeping mothers alive and well.

The National HIV Strategic Plan recommends institutionalising, identifying, reaching, recommending, testing, treat and retaining. With and for all key populations to minimise HIV transmission. Due to the significant number of infections among migrants, it is important to assess and improve the current programmes to better prevent HIV transmission related to migrants and other mobile populations. It is also important to promote testing of intimate sexual partners of people at high risk and to consider whether pre-exposure prevention settings may be a beneficial option.

There are examples where HIV programmes have been able to reach spouses of male labour migrants with awareness programmes in the far and mid-west of Nepal, where most mobile and migrant populations going to India live or originate. Of labour migrant populations, especially those going to India. As not all migrants, mobile and displaced persons face the same risks, identifying those at higher risk as a priority is necessary. It is also important to address structural barriers, such as the lack of identity cards⁵³.

MIGRANTS' ACCESS TO HEALTHCARE IN THE SEA REGION

The body of 'white' and 'grey' literature reviewed highlights that migrants' health status is affected by multiple factors that influence migrants' ability to access healthcare. Many studies dealing with the migrants' pattern of use of healthcare fail to clarify whether the migrants and internally displaced persons have come across the border. Also, a distinction needs to be made between irregular migrants and asylum seekers. As soon as irregular migrants applied for asylum, their presence in the country became legal. This changes their entitlement to healthcare. The problems to access to health care are also different depending upon whether the migrants are in the border districts or have moved deeper into the country or maybe in a metropolitan city. Dealing with the migrants' pattern of use of healthcare fail to clarify whether the migrants and internally displaced persons or who have come across the border. Also, a distinction needs to be made between irregular migrants and asylum seekers. As soon as irregular migrants applied for asylum, their presence in the country became legal. This changes their entitlement to healthcare. The problems to access to health care are also different depending upon whether the migrants are in the border districts or they have moved deeper into the country or maybe in a metropolitan city. These include legal entitlement, knowledge of the health system in a new country, previous experience of healthcare; language and cultural barriers; health beliefs and attitudes; and the structure of the health system itself in the new country, adequacy of infrastructure in the border districts⁵⁴.

Health infrastructure in the border districts is usually inadequate in terms of workforce, quality, and supply is often irregular, interrupted and short. Border districts are in disadvantaged terrain, primarily hilly and forested, difficult to approach with few pockets reachable only by foot which is hazardous and time-consuming. The majority of the people living in border areas belong to low-income groups, with all the disadvantages associated with poverty, illiteracy and ignorance. The absence of opportunities for gainful employment round the year in local areas forces people to look for income-generating activities outside the districts, often migrating to neighbouring countries.

Over the past few decades, India's growing economy and demand for labour have attracted people from Nepal and Bangladesh's neighbouring countries. The nature of migration from Bangladesh and Nepal to India is not quite the same. The Indo-Nepal Treaty of Peace and Friendship (1950) enables Nepalese citizens to move freely across the border without a passport or visa, live and work in India, and own property or do business in India. However, it does not afford them certain rights, including voting and access to government schemes, such as ration cards. The situation is quite different for Bangladeshi citizens: India has a closed border with Bangladesh, and Bangladeshis can travel to India only after obtaining a valid passport and visa.

Nonetheless, evidence from official and unofficial sources indicates that many Bangladeshi migrants arrive in India by crossing the porous border through unofficial transit points. Sources also confirm the existence of many Nepali migrants in the metropolitan cities of India. According to the Census of India 2011, there were approximately 3.128 million migrants from Bangladesh, Bhutan, Myanmar and Nepal. 74% are from Bangladesh, and 25% are from Nepal.

Reasons for lack of access to healthcare services – Nepalese experiences

Migration to India is a common livelihood strategy for poor people in remote Western Nepal. Little research has explored the degree and nature of healthcare access among Nepali migrant workers in India. A study was done in 2017 to examine the experiences of returnee Nepali migrants with regard to accessing healthcare in India, in addition to other objectives. To explore the experiences of returnee Nepali migrants with regard to accessing healthcare in India, in addition to other objectives.

The returnee migrants who worked in 15 of India's 29 states were interviewed as daily-wage labourers. Most were from among the lowest castes so called-Dalits. The majority of migrants had had difficulty accessing healthcare services in India. The major barriers to access were the lack of insurance, low wages, not having an Indian identification card tied to individual biometrics, so-called: Aadhaar card. Other barriers were unsupportive employers, discrimination at healthcare facilities and limited information about the locations of healthcare services.

The study identifies three kinds of barriers: finance/cost, structural/political barriers and lack of knowledge. First, access to healthcare is related to the kind of employer or company a person works for and the insurance coverage they are provided. In terms of finance, it is less likely that a small company will provide insurance coverage and cover the costs of healthcare during an illness than a big company. Thus, migrants employed by small companies are less likely than those working for larger big companies to get health services in India. Not having an Aadhaar card was one of the structural barriers to accessing healthcare services in India⁵⁵.

A qualitative study carried out in two cities of Maharashtra State in 2017 showed that Nepali migrants have limited access to health care facilities due to their inability to prove their identity. The Health System of India also discriminates as some treatment is restricted to Indian nationals. The participants mentioned poor access to hospitals, the need for identification documents for treatment, and the quality of available service with better treatment to be found in private hospitals. This is in line with other studies in different geographical settings. Among the other reasons migrants were dissatisfied with the quality of health services in India were difficulty in communicating with medical staff, discrimination and delayed treatment.

There was also an issue of language; some failed to understand the language used during their consultation⁵⁶. Treatment and the quality of available service with better treatment to be found in private hospitals. This is in line with other studies in different geographical settings. Among the other reasons migrants were dissatisfied with the quality of health services in India were difficulty in communicating with medical staff, discrimination and delayed treatment. There was also an issue of language; some failed to understand the language used during their consultation.

Access to malaria services for Indian Migrants in Bhutan

Bhutan is in a critical stage of malaria elimination. The number of malaria cases is more in non-Bhutanese compared to its citizens. Therefore, cross-border malaria initiatives are crucial for malaria elimination and the prevention of reintroduction in Bhutan. Recognising the challenge and importance of cross-border malaria, the Bhutan government has already put in some measures to prevent and control cross border malaria in the country. All foreign labourers (almost all are Indians) bound for employments in the country are mandated to undergo malaria testing as part of medical screening. The screening is conducted by the hospitals located in the border districts and private diagnostics centres in the country. Since its implementation, the screening activities conducted by the hospitals at these entry points has seen an increasing number of labourers being screened over the years.

Further, proactive surveillance is conducted regularly and targeted at high-risk areas like Mega hydropower projects sites. The screening program has detected both PF and PV cases in migrant labourers. Although the cases detected are few, considering the existence of conducive climatic conditions and the presence of vectors, this poses a potential risk for reintroduction and establishment of malaria transmission in the locality. Hence, screening for the malaria parasite among this group is a very important part of the overall malaria elimination program that needs to be continued⁵⁷.

Access to HIV treatment in India – experiences of Migrants from Bangladesh and Nepal

A review of studies conducted among migrants from Bangladesh, India, and Nepal suggests that the association between migration and HIV has been well studied. The results demonstrate that the risk of contracting HIV is higher among migrants than non-migrants (i.e., the native population). Male migrant workers, in particular, are a high-risk population, as many become infected through transactional sex in high-epidemic regions^{58 59 60 61 62}.

A 5-year project, ‘Enhancing Mobile Population’s Access to HIV and AIDS Information (EMPHASIS), Services and Support’, provides insights into AIDS-related vulnerabilities of cross-border populations moving between Bangladesh, India, and Nepal.

The project explored the experiences of people living with HIV (PLHIV) as they migrate. Drawing on small-scale qualitative studies in Bangladesh, India and Nepal, it explored their migration experiences

and their patterns of HIV diagnosis and treatment, provided examples of the barriers they face in accessing health services (including antiretroviral therapy, care and support services) at source and destination.

There were three common scenarios for Bangladeshis and Nepalese people living with HIV (PLHIV) regarding HIV infection and seeking health services. One group of respondents returned to their home country with persistent illness. They approached different health facilities to identify the cause of their illness, and after many hurdles, they found out about their HIV status. This group is now linked with treatment, care and support services in their home country. The second group of respondents sought health care at their destination and has approached private facilities. This group was identified as HIV-positive in India but later returned to their home (in either Bangladesh or Nepal) and has sought treatment services at home. The third group of respondents also had a persistent illness, and they sought health care in India. This group was later diagnosed in India, and now they are accessing treatment facilities in India. The fourth group of respondents are Nepalese migrants diagnosed in Nepal and who came back to India but still access ART from Nepal. This group of respondents has experienced getting an ART transfer from Nepal to India.

In Bangladesh, care and support services to PLHIV used to be implemented by PLHIV self-help groups through a funded program. From December 1, 2012, these services, including ART distribution, were supposed to be rendered through government hospitals. Despite this, the service modality has not changed. The absence of a sustainable service system is the primary challenge for treatment, care and support for PLHIV in Bangladesh. Additionally, misconceptions and stigma around HIV transmission are high among service providers in Bangladesh. The study shows many PLHIV attempts to conceal their HIV status to service providers.

In Nepal, treatment care and support services have been scaled up under universal care and support at government health facilities. Though services are available, most respondents cannot access them regularly because of the distance between their homes and the health facilities. Additionally, the array of services needed cannot be accessed at a single location. Different facilities provide different services. Different services are also provided on different days.

In India, services are scaled up at government and non-government health settings at district and sub-district levels. In the big cities like Mumbai, the volume of clients is high resulting in long queues and a lower quality of service. Migrants also face language barriers as the service providers often use their local language. Though there is a system in place, clients often wait an entire day to pick up their medication. Additionally, although no identity proof is required for HIV services, respondents reported that they were asked for identity proof to access services.

The study shows that even when services are available, clients face many challenges to access them, especially at destination sites⁶³.

Access to TB care and support at Vietnam-Cambodia border provinces

In 2020, Vietnam was one of the 30 highest-burden countries globally with TB and MDR-TB, whereas Cambodia was one of the 30 highest-burden countries with TB. While both nations have made significant progress in reducing TB rates in recent years, they lack the financial resources to end TB as a public health problem. Within this context of strained health resources, migrant populations – internal migrants within each of the two countries and cross-border migrants on the Vietnam– Cambodia border – can easily be missed or overlooked in national efforts to detect TB.

Although cross-border migrants are at high risk of contracting TB, there remains a scarcity of data to support the development of national guidelines and policies for TB control among migrants in Vietnam and Cambodia. A qualitative study done in 2020-2021 focused on two southern provinces in Vietnam (An Giang and Tay Ninh) with high notification rates of TB and two Cambodian provinces (Svay Rieng and Takeo), which together witness cross-border movement.

The study revealed a lack of systematic data on migration statuses, such as nationality and migration history, in both countries. User-friendly and quality healthcare services in Vietnam have encouraged Cambodian respondents to access healthcare. At the same time, some Vietnamese stakeholders were not cognizant of the language barriers faced by Cambodian patients. The study also showed that a sizeable number of participants in both countries rarely paid attention to public posters, leaflets or health sessions about TB or other health issues in their communities as information, education and communication (IEC) materials were not well-designed to capture patients' attention and sporadically placed in communities.

Although the National TB Control Programme (NTP) Vietnam is committed to treating TB patients regardless of nationality, a degree of misunderstanding was evident among some stakeholders in Vietnam. Fragmented policy implementation at the local level might cause delays in early diagnosis and treatment for cross-border migrants with TB. Cambodian stakeholders and cross-border migrants with TB reported repetitive diagnosis procedures in Cambodia, despite patients already being diagnosed with TB in Vietnam. Similarly, healthcare providers faced challenges in the provision of continuous treatment to cross-border TB patients due to a lack of synchronisation of country protocols on TB treatment - highlighting limited trans-border collaboration and partnerships between health authorities on either side of the border.

Cross-border migrants were also found to encounter non-health-related challenges, such as a lack of ID cards and complex administrative procedures pertaining to the residential registration book system in Vietnam that prevented migrants from purchasing health insurance^{64 65}.

Access to TB care and support at Myanmar-Thailand border provinces

Myanmar and Thailand belong to the top 22 high burden countries for tuberculosis (TB). Health care organisations play an essential role in addressing TB control in the two bridging border jurisdictions, Tak province, Thailand, Myawaddy district, Kayin state, and Myanmar. However, health professionals face difficulties in TB control efforts due to fluid population movements, resource constraints and ambiguous mechanisms to implement collaboration along the border. The purpose of this study is to identify the challenges to TB control among Myanmar migrants faced by stakeholders, focusing on the area of collaboration and interaction along the border.

A study conducted in-depth interviews with health policymakers and providers responsible for developing and implementing policies and TB programs in Tak province, Thailand and Myawaddy district, Kayin state, Myanmar. The main theme reported by participants was challenging in limited corroboration and coordination among stakeholders. Unstructured information sharing and lack of communication hindered the stakeholders from engaging in TB control. The respondents stressed that referral mechanisms across the border need to be strengthened. Other challenges were associated with increasing loss to follow up and subsequent MDR cases, service delivery constraints, shortage of human resources, limited staff capacities within organisations and poor socioeconomic status of pa⁶⁶.

Sri Lanka

Sri Lanka's National Migration Health Policy, 2013 recommends a comprehensive series of strategies to promote the health of outbound and inbound migrants and internal migrants and the families left behind. The programme on National Migration Health Policy has enabled Sri Lankan refugees who return from India access to the primary healthcare system upon their arrival. Health screening facilities are provided, and early treatment, including those for malaria, HIV and TB, are available. Sri Lanka has implemented specialist health and welfare services for those returning migrant workers who have been subjected to abuse⁶⁷.

Sri Lanka has also entered into agreements with specific countries, for example, Qatar, and the Republic of Korea, to ensure that Sri Lankan workers have access to health care and social security benefits. The Sri Lanka Bureau of Foreign Employment has also established an Overseas Workers Welfare Fund to provide a comprehensive system for migrants' welfare⁶⁸.

Thailand's migrant insurance scheme

Thailand has established a universal healthcare scheme. The scheme was introduced in 2002 after the promulgation of the National Health Security Act 39 that sets the legal basis for the country's Universal Coverage Scheme. Data from 2008 estimated that the scheme covers 75% of Thai citizens. The remaining Thai population is covered by the Social Security Scheme, covering private-sector workers (7%), or by the Civil Servant Medical Benefit Scheme, covering civil servants (16%). In 2001, to provide health coverage to documented migrant workers, Thailand established a Migrant Health Insurance Scheme that includes prevention, diagnosis, and treatment services.

Payment of fees for annual membership for a compulsory annual medical examination is required to benefit from the scheme (1600 baht and 500 baht, respectively, in 2018). This scheme allows undocumented migrants to purchase health insurance membership. With this system, Thailand provides access to health services for migrants; however, the access is restricted to the health facility where migrants were first registered. Regular migrant workers employed in the formal sector can join the Social Security Scheme with the same entitlements as Thai citizens, where employers and workers each contribute 5% of the worker's salary, and the government contributes an amount equivalent to 2.75%. As of November 2018, it was reported that approximately 64% of documented migrant workers from GMS countries who were eligible for health insurance coverage were enrolled in Thailand. This proportion falls to 51% of all eligible migrants (documented and undocumented) are considered⁶⁹.

Beyond the Region

Cross border prevention and care of Tuberculosis in Europe

As tuberculosis (TB) spreads beyond borders with people movements, several interventions ensuring the continuity of care are essential, although difficult to put in place in the absence of well-defined agreements allowing data sharing and easy referral of patients to appropriate health facilities.

The establishment of transnational services for TB care and control in Europe is essential, as it allows not only for more effective and cost-effective patient pathways, avoiding repetition of diagnostic procedures for patients who cross borders, but also for better cross-border management for those already on TB treatment, so that interruption of treatment is avoided. Improved cross-border collaboration is especially important in managing multidrug-resistant (MDR) TB, ensuring prompt diagnosis, adequate uninterrupted MDR treatment and prevention of MDR-TB in migrants through the early outbreak and contact investigations.

In 2012, the World Health Organization (WHO) Regional Office for Europe, with input from national TB programme managers and country representatives, finalised a consensus document on a minimum TB control and care package. According to this, all TB care services must be free of charge irrespective of the person's legal status and nationality. The recommended minimum package aims to break down key barriers to diagnosis and treatment and data exchange for migrants and other cross-border travellers with TB. Despite this consensus document, cross-border TB control remains a major challenge, and implementing a minimum package for cross-border TB control and care remains highly heterogeneous. Recording and reporting of TB among undocumented migrants are largely lacking, preventing sharing of information.

The WHO Regional Office for Europe and the ERS has established an electronic platform (the WHO-ERS TB Consilium. First launched in September 2012, this web-based, the open-access multilingual system provides free clinical support. In addition, the TB Consilium also addresses the problem of trans-border follow-up of patients moving from one European country to another, representing the main mechanism for promoting interaction between TB care providers at a supranational level. This electronic tool remains underexploited. The WHO-ERS platform will ensure continuity of care when people move across different countries. It needs to be scaled up further.

Data sharing between the sending and receiving countries is of utmost importance. Harmonisation of policies, diagnosis, treatment and other control measures between neighbouring countries is critical. Successful implementation of effective cross border collaboration and coordination of efforts is key to being on track with the WHO's targets for 2030.

United States

The 2007 Pew Hispanic Centre/Robert Wood Johnson Foundation Hispanic Healthcare Survey highlighted that immigrants who are not citizens or legal permanent residents are more likely to be excluded from care in the United States and across borders. Exclusion due to legal status differences on either side of the border reduces the chances of receiving timely preventive services. Civic stratification and political determinants, broadly speaking, should be considered alongside social determinants of population health and health care⁷⁰.

Japan: universal access to TB care for migrant populations

Recognising the importance of ensuring that all individuals with active TB are diagnosed and treated, Japan has provided publicly funded TB services under a TB control law since the 1950s – later superseded by a more comprehensive infectious disease law. The law stipulates that the prefectural government shall bear the expenses of the following medical care to be provided to the patient:

1. Medical examination
2. Provision of drugs and medical equipment
3. Medical treatment, surgery and other kinds of medical care
4. Hospitalisation, nursing during medical treatment and other care.

Under the current era of an increasing migrant population in Japan, this historical principle of free TB care supported by law works positively for TB control among migrants because all individuals can access standardised quality TB care regardless of nationality or health insurance status.

To achieve the same objective, some countries have extended health insurance coverage more broadly to all migrant populations regardless of immigration status, which has resulted in significant public health successes, most notably with respect to the control of communicable diseases.

In addition to providing migrant populations with free universal access to TB care, Japan has also undertaken various initiatives to further ensure migrants' access to needed TB care. In Tokyo, for instance, a translator telephone dispatch service has been established to assist public health nurses in explaining the treatment and administrative processes to foreign patients, with a wide variety of languages spoken, for example, Burmese, English, French, Indonesian, Korean, Mandarin Chinese, Nepali, Portuguese, Spanish, Tagalog, Thai and Vietnamese. Meanwhile, in Shiga prefecture, posters and educational materials have been developed, as well as protocols to manage TB in the workplace.

Vietnam: removal of institutional barriers to care

In some countries, residency registration policies limit people's access to health services at their official place of residency, which cannot be easily transferred. Initially designed to discourage rural-to-urban migration, these registration policies have now effectively become a barrier for internal migrants in accessing necessary health services as migrants have remained largely undeterred from moving to urban centres. In the 2004 Vietnam Migration Survey, for instance, 42% of those surveyed reported experiencing difficulties because of their non-permanent residential status, and of those who did not register, 48% believed re-registration was not possible, while 22% did not think it was necessary and 9% did not know-how.

However, recognising the importance of removing these institutional barriers, Vietnam's 2007 Law on Residence has lessened requirements for permanent registration in centrally-administered cities and removed geographical restrictions for registrations of birth. Where possible, countries might also consider informing migrants in departure and destination areas, of registration rules and procedures and of the availability of health and other social services.

Papua New Guinea and Australia: cross-border coordination and referral in the Torres Strait

Papua New Guinea's Western Province, with a total population of 219 103 as of 2011, is a coastal, south-western province that shares an international sea border with Australia's Torres Strait Islands. Given the historical sea and land use of the Torres Strait area by its indigenous residents, a treaty between Australia and Papua New Guinea was signed in 1978 that, to date, allows for residents from both countries to freely cross the border.

While there is no provision for medical care in the agreement, casual cross-border migrants from Papua New Guinea have been seeking health services in Australia's Torres Strait Islands for many years.

In 2011 it was decided that all TB patients from Papua New Guinea receiving treatment in the Torres Strait clinics, as well as those with other medical conditions, were to be transferred back home and that major efforts would be undertaken to build the capacity of the Western Province's healthcare system and its TB services.

Importantly, to facilitate proper cross-border referral of patients, a Clinical Collaboration Group was established between Australian and Papua New Guinean doctors, which held its first official meeting in Daru, Western Province, in February 2013. All Papua New Guinean patients who seek care in the Torres Strait clinics are now referred back home through email and mobile communication between designated cross-border communications officers, with positive programme results thus far⁷¹.

Several countries have introduced micro-insurance in the form of community-based health insurance schemes to promote access to healthcare and ensure financial protection for the target population like migrants within a given country-specific context. For example, the Government of Mexico introduced a cross-border health insurance system to protect the health of uninsured Mexican migrants living and working in the USA, their families who remain in Mexico, and migrants who later return to Mexico⁷²
⁷³.

In certain EU countries, such as Germany and Italy, undocumented/illegal migrants can enjoy health care services with a varying range of benefit packages. Some countries, such as France and Italy, allow certain vulnerable migrant groups of children and pregnant women to enjoy health benefits to the same extent as nationals. In contrast, some countries, like the UK and the Netherlands, do not permit this. In Hong Kong, undocumented/illegal migrants can access health care services only in emergencies.

Access to healthcare: Experiences from across the world

Spain

The 1986 General Health Law and the 2011 Public Health Law granted all Spanish residents an explicit right to free healthcare. However, in 2012, in the wake of the financial crisis, the government sharply curtailed this right, using a Royal Decree. This allowed it to bypass the Cortes (parliament) and restrict access by migrants. This change limited access by undocumented migrants to emergency services only, unless they were children or pregnant women. In practice, introducing bureaucratic barriers and the fear of deportation made even emergency care difficult to obtain.

However, barriers to successful implementation still need to be overcome⁷⁴. , the government signed a new Royal Decree granting undocumented migrants the right to health protection and healthcare under the same conditions as people with Spanish nationality.

South Africa

The Southern African Development Community (SADC) model ensures migrants access to care. Implementation remains challenging, but the SADC's "Harmonised Minimum Standards for the Prevention, Treatment and Management of Tuberculosis" aim to improve referral systems and continuity of care for individuals who cross borders.

Tuberculosis control: Global Scenario

Many countries simply ban entry or residence as an attempt to keep TB out.

A review of key literature and legal statutes shows that many countries ban entry or residence of persons with TB:

- i. In the United States, active TB remains one of the seven listed diseases that trigger inadmissibility under the Immigration and Nationality Act,
- ii. Canada identifies active TB as a condition “dangerous to public health,” rendering foreign nationals inadmissible on the grounds of being a “danger to public safety.”
- iii. Australian, New Zealand, and United Kingdom laws all permit entry for migrants on a negative TB diagnosis.
- iv. China precludes visas for foreigners with TB as well as for “other infectious diseases that may severely jeopardise the public health.”
- v. In Liberia, the list of those who are “ineligible to receive visas and shall be excluded from admission. . . [include those] who are afflicted with tuberculosis in any form.”

Some countries withhold essential medical services for migrants; others require people with TB to undergo treatment as a condition of legal status, and many detain and deport migrants, often withholding or withdrawing TB treatment. Such migration laws drive the most vulnerable away from TB diagnosis and treatment, thus violating fundamental human rights relating to discrimination and healthcare access. For example, China’s hukou registration system makes many migrants, both international migrants and internal migrants, ineligible for subsidised healthcare, resulting in lower access to TB care, poor treatment outcomes, and drug resistance⁷⁵.

HIV control: Global Scenario

During the height of the AIDS pandemic, many countries restricted the travel or immigration of persons living with HIV, which was widely condemned as ineffective and rights-violating. Mandatory HIV testing and bans on entry, stay, and residence based on HIV status not only do not protect public health but undermine HIV prevention and treatment efforts. For millions of people living with HIV worldwide, these are repeated violations of their right to privacy, equality and non-discrimination and a constant reminder of HIV-related stigma. In 2016, United Nations Member States agreed to eliminate HIV-related travel restrictions. In 2019, around 48 countries and territories still maintained some form of HIV-related travel restriction.

The kind of restrictions include:

1. HIV testing is required for work permits.
2. HIV testing is required for study permits.
3. HIV testing or disclosure required for certain permits or entry less than 90 days.
4. HIV testing is required for residency permits (for stays longer than 90 days).
5. Prohibit entry and stay less than 90 days based on HIV status.
6. Residency permits denied (for stays longer than 90 days) based on HIV status.
7. Non-nationals living with HIV are deported based on their HIV status⁷⁶.

Access to healthcare by migrants: Barriers and obligations

Countries can only achieve universal health coverage when including migrants (both documents and irregular). As seen above, there are examples of countries where migrants’ access to healthcare is restricted and at times denied.

The main barriers for accessing healthcare by migrants based on the World Health Organization’s health system building blocks are:

1. Leadership/governance

- i. Conflicting policy goals between ministries responsible for health, immigration, and human resources
- ii. Legislation is not migrant inclusive

2. Healthcare financing

- i. Migrants' ability to when not enrolled in health insurance Schemes
- ii. Cross border health and social insurance schemes
- iii. Eligibility and enrolment in health insurance schemes

3. Information and research

- i. Data collection systems disaggregated by migrant status
- ii. Availability of databases on migrant health

4. Medical products and technologies

- i. Availability of essential medicines and technologies for migrant patients

5. Service delivery

- i. Language skills or interpreter availability
- ii. Essential health packages for migrants regardless of documentation status
- iii. Proximity and accessibility of services (e.g., mobile units)

Health workforce

Professional norms

- i. Discriminatory treatment and perceived “deservingness.”
- ii. Cultural competence of staff treating migrant patients (training)

The majority of barriers faced relating to money matters. With the exception of Thailand in the Region, undocumented migrants are not included. Only a few can afford to pay for healthcare in the private sector. Some countries of origin (Bangladesh, for example) of the migrants have provided health insurance coverage for the documented migrants to other countries and Sri Lanka, which provides care to returning migrants who need it. It turns out that political commitment is key to extending the coverage.

The key messages are that the right to health, which underpins the commitment to universal health coverage in the sustainable development goals, includes migrant populations; some countries are designing inclusive policies to ensure that undocumented migrants have access to health services, while other countries are becoming more restrictive and eroding the principle of universality; and Governments should expand and enhance health systems, where necessary, to incorporate the needs of undocumented migrants in national and local healthcare policies and plans and health professionals should do everything necessary to make this a reality.

Legal obligation towards cross border health in different jurisdictions

In Europe, Article 35 of the European Union Charter of Fundamental Rights espouses that “Everyone has the right to access preventive healthcare and the right to benefit from medical treatment under the conditions established by national laws and practices.”

Moreover, Article 13 of the Council of Europe Resolution 1509 (2006) on the Human Rights of Irregular Migrants confirms “minimum rights”, and more over states that emergency health care should be available to irregular migrants and that states should seek to provide more holistic health care catering to vulnerable groups.

The United Kingdom provides antiretrovirals to all people in the UK regardless of immigration status. However, in the UK, undocumented migrant children are not provided with any protection. Hong Kong grants undocumented migrants the right to access emergency care, but health authorities are legally obliged to report them to the authorities. Among the ASEAN community, healthcare access for undocumented migrants is non-existent.

The ILO Recommendation concerning HIV and AIDS and the World of Work, 2010 stresses occupational safety and health issues. It states that “*workers should benefit from programmes to prevent specific risks of occupational transmission of HIV and related transmissible diseases*” and that workers in occupations with increased susceptibility to the risk of HIV transmission need to be accorded priority⁷⁷.

Article 12 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) states that

“1) Everyone lawfully within the territory of a State, within that territory, has the right to liberty of movement and freedom to choose his residence; 2) Everyone shall be free to leave any country, including his own; 3) The above-mentioned rights shall not be subject to any restrictions except those which are provided by law, are necessary to protect national security, public order (order public), public health or morals or the rights and freedoms of others, and are consistent with the other rights recognized in the present Covenant; 4) No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of the right to enter his own country”⁷⁸.

While the Covenant allows States to limit entry on their territory on public health grounds, according to the International Health Regulations, the only disease for which an international travel vaccination certificate is required is yellow fever.

In the Case of *N. v. The United Kingdom*, a Ugandan asylum seeker appealed to the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR), claiming that upon deportation from the UK, she would not be able to access sufficient antiretroviral therapy in her country of origin. According to the aggrieved, the deportation would amount to torture and disrespect private and family life as per the European Convention on Human Rights. The Court ruled that ill-treatment falls within the scope of torture only in cases of “minimum level of severity that is relative and dependent on all the circumstances of the case, including the duration of treatment, its physical and mental effects and, in some cases, the sex, age and state of health of the victim.” The Court held that states might apply Art 3 on torture, “where harm derives from a naturally occurring illness and the lack of sufficient resources to deal with it in the receiving country”. The ECHR concluded that the UK might deport non-nationals who receive treatment in the UK, even if no sufficient treatment in the country of destination is guaranteed⁷⁹.

However, in *D. v. the United Kingdom*, the ECHR ruled against the deportation of an HIV-positive person. The Court ruled that eviction of the HIV positive foreigner was against Article 3 of the European Convention on Human Rights.

International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of their Families (ICRMW) (1990).

The ICRMW is the most comprehensive international treaty dealing particularly with migrant workers. It guarantees equality of treatment with nationals of the State of employment in relation to certain aspects, including equality of treatment to the families of migrant workers in access to social and health services. The Convention states that the rights migrant workers enjoy to be treated “no less favourably” than nationals with respect to compensation, and other conditions of work, including safety and health, may not be taken away based on “any irregularity” in the migrant’s “stay or employment.” The ICRMW also provides emergency medical care to all migrants, irrespective of their status. Article 28 states: “Migrant workers and members of their families shall have the right to receive any medical care that is urgently required for the preservation of their life or the avoidance of irreparable harm to their health on the basis of equality of treatment with nationals of the State concerned.

The Committee on Migrant Workers (CMW), the treaty body for the ICRMW, states that access to urgent medical care must be ensured to all migrant workers with parity in treatment with nationals in a non-discriminatory manner. States parties should prohibit the charging of excessive fees from migrant workers in irregular situations. States parties should ensure that migrant workers and members of their families are provided with information on the medical care provided and information about their health rights.

The CMW General Comment No. 1 on migrant domestic workers issued by the CMW urges States to repeal discriminatory laws, regulations and practices related to HIV, including those resulting in the loss of work visa based on the HIV status, and to ensure that medical testing of migrant domestic workers, including for pregnancy or HIV is conducted only on a voluntary basis, with the informed consent of the individual.

The Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) General Recommendation No. 26 emphasizes countries of origin to provide information and awareness on general and reproductive health, including HIV prevention, and requires that “all required pre-departure HIV/AIDS testing or pre-departure health examinations must be respectful of the human rights of women migrants.

UN Commission on Human Rights has interpreted the term “other status” in non-discrimination provisions in international human rights texts as “encompassing health status, including HIV/AIDS”. This prompts national courts to address HIV-related discrimination even when HIV and AIDS are not explicitly covered under national legislation⁸⁰.

ILO Discrimination (Employment and Occupation) Convention, 1958 (No. 111) warrants ratifying States to declare and pursue a national policy designed to promote equality of opportunity and treatment in respect of employment and occupation, with a view to eliminating any discrimination in respect thereof. This policy should cover all workers, including migrant workers. The ILO Committee of Experts on the Application of Convention and Recommendation (Committee of Experts) has commented positively on the adoption of national laws and policies providing for HIV status as a prohibited ground of discrimination, as well as on the creation of national AIDS authorities or the adoption of national policies or strategies on HIV and AIDS. In the specific context of labour migration, the Committee of Experts has also examined the issue of HIV-related discrimination under the Migration for Employment Convention, 1949 (No.49), concluding that the refusal of entry or repatriation of a migrant worker on the ground that the worker was HIV-positive would “constitute an unacceptable form of discrimination and is contrary to the Convention⁸¹.”

ILO HIV and AIDS Recommendation, 2010 (No. 200)

The Recommendation provides that: “there should be no discrimination against or stigmatisation of workers, in particular job seekers and job applicants, on the grounds of real or perceived HIV status or the fact that they belong to regions of the world or segments of the population perceived to be at greater risk of or more vulnerable to HIV infection⁸².”

Recommendation No. 200 applies to all workers and workplaces. Its provisions also apply to migrant workers. It provides that migrant worker should not be subjected to compulsory HIV testing, nor should they be required to disclose HIV-related information or be excluded from migrating based on their real or perceived HIV status at any stage of the migration process. It also advocates that training, safety instructions and HIV and AIDS guidance in the workplace should be provided in clear and accessible forms for all migrant workers as well.

Furthermore, the recommendation calls for international cooperation among countries of origin, of transit, and of destination to ensure migrants’ access to HIV prevention, treatment, care and support.

The Equality of Treatment (Social Security) Convention, 1962 (No. 118) calls for mutual multilateral or bilateral agreements to give effect to the inclusion of migrants in social protection systems in countries of employment and for portability of migrant contributions and earned benefits to their home countries.

According to the ILO Social Security (Minimum Standards) Convention, 1952 (No. 102), 200 the ILO Equality of Treatment (Social Security) Convention, 1962 (No. 118), 201 and the ILO Recommendation concerning National Floors of Social Protection, (No. 202).²⁰², migrants and their families should have access to these basic social security guarantees in the State where they reside, as well as in their home country⁸³.

Political Declaration on HIV and AIDS: Ending Inequalities and Getting on Track to End AIDS by 2030

The Heads of State and Government and representatives of States and Governments assembled at the United Nations from 8 to 10 June 2021:

1. Regretted that over 75 million people have become infected with HIV and over 32 million people have died from AIDS-related illnesses since the start of the global AIDS epidemic;
2. Expressed deep concern and regret that the international community did not meet the 2020 targets set out in the 2016 political declaration on HIV and AIDS, despite the fact that we have the knowledge and tools to prevent every new HIV infection and each AIDS-related death;
3. Committed urgent and transformative action to end the social, economic, racial and gender inequalities, restrictive and discriminatory laws, policies and practices, stigma and multiple and intersecting forms of discrimination, including based on HIV status, and human rights violations that perpetuate the global AIDS epidemic;
4. Strongly committed to provide greater leadership and to work together through international cooperation, reinvigorated multilateralism and meaningful community engagement to urgently accelerate our national, regional and global collective actions towards comprehensive prevention, treatment, care and support, increase investments in research, development, science and innovations to build a healthier world for all, and leverage the decade of action and delivery for sustainable development and ensure that no one is left behind, with an endeavour to reach the furthest behind first;
5. Committed to build back better in a more equitable and inclusive manner from the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic and its impact on the global AIDS epidemic and build resilience against future pandemics and other global health and development challenges, and continue to leverage the investments and experience of the HIV response to further enhance public health and strengthen health systems;
6. Committed to urgent action over the next five years through a coordinated global HIV response based on global solidarity and shared responsibility to fully implement the commitments contained in the present declaration, and urgently work towards an HIV vaccine and a cure, recognizing that achieving the commitments will reduce annual new HIV infections to under 370,000 and annual AIDS-related deaths to under 250,000 by 2025 and generate progress towards the elimination of all forms of HIV-related stigma and discrimination.

The Association of Southeast Asian Nations Declaration on the Protection and Promotion of Migrant Workers (2007) commits the Member States to “Intensify efforts to protect the fundamental human rights, promote the welfare and uphold the human dignity of migrant worker” and “facilitate access to resources and remedies through information, training and education, access to justice, and social welfare as appropriate and in accordance with the legislation of the receiving state, provided that they fulfil the requirements under applicable laws, regulations and policies of the said state, bilateral agreements and multilateral treaties”⁸⁴. In this respect, APEC developed the HIV/AIDS Workplace Guidelines: Guidance on Migrant and Mobile Workers to create an enabling environment for employers to implement effective workplace practices for PLHIV⁸⁵.

Barriers in cross border control of diseases

- **Political:** The challenge of integrating national and local political agendas to develop a diverse cross-border health policy that is effective and sustainable.
- **Legal:** The limited efforts to implement bilateral, regional and multilateral agreements by states and regional organisations on cross-border health.
- **Administrative:** Bureaucratic hurdles in implementation of agreements signed by the parties. Multiple interpretations of agreements by the state and regional authorities coupled with lack of coordination from the other side of the border.
- **Governance:** The absence of structures at the local and regional level to ensure the implementation and follow-up of agreements and cross-border patient flows.
- **Availability and accessibility of updated data:** The non-availability and difficulty in accessing updated demographic-health data, patient mobility, and general cross-border health status data.
- **Physical accessibility:** The difficult terrain makes it challenging to build connections by land or river due to a lack of infrastructure or public transport services.
- **Sanitary supplies:** The lack of equipment and specialised health care professionals in certain regions.
- **Communication, information, and digitalisation:** Information asymmetry and lack of know-how about the health system of the neighbouring country and of the cross-border agreements in force. This situation also impedes the exchange of data and the creation of automated systems for service delivery.
- **Cooperation:** The lack of specialised and established programs to promote cross-border health cooperation on an ongoing basis.
- The loss of social support assistance from the country of origin if residing on the other side of the border leads to disruption in access to treatment. The paperwork involved in reimbursement of healthcare expenses prevents mobile populations from availing of treatment. Patient transfer is mired in excessive bureaucracy, and transfers are only considered in case of emergency. The prescription written and medications prescribed do not have validity on the other side of the border⁸⁶.
- Mobile populations also have different perceptions and knowledge of illness, disease and treatments. As a result, some migrants prefer to go to informal health care providers as the first line of treatment.
- The differences in cultural practices across the border, such as those involving women or those involving contraceptives, also deter mobile populations from accessing healthcare services in another country.
- In Switzerland and Italy, it has been found that the migrants' lack of awareness of health care and preventive services has been the main reason for the underutilisation of health services.
- The internationally agreed obligations mandate universal access to drugs and care for infectious diseases such as TB. TB and drug-resistant TB care must include quality drugs free of cost in a gender-sensitive and culturally mindful manner. In some countries, there is sometimes denial of entry of TB suspects, and asylum seekers or undocumented migrants diagnosed with TB are extradited without continuity of TB treatment is ensured. For TB patients crossing national borders, there exists a lack of patient-centred approaches and/or availability of sound transfer mechanisms.
- In Zimbabwe, the most significant barriers to health care for cross-border migrants were cost, negative attitudes of medical staff, fear of police or immigration, language and wanting a different doctor⁸⁷.
- The lack of uninterrupted health insurance coverage, quality health care, and low levels of English proficiency causes US Hispanic adults to seek healthcare in Mexico and other Latin American countries⁸⁸.

Political action

World Trade Organization (WTO) agreements on the Application of Sanitary and Phytosanitary Measures (SPS) and Technical Barriers to Trade (TBT) state health as a legitimate objective for WTO members to take into consideration when necessary to protect the health of humans, animals, and plants. Given that technological developments in recent years have created sensitive early warning disease surveillance systems, rapid and reliable verification procedures, preparedness plans including medication stockpiles, and international response networks, WTO suggests that restrictions should be time-limited and minimally disruptive to international trade and travel⁸⁹.

Under the International Health Regulation (2005), governments are accountable to their citizens and the global community in managing outbreaks. They are required to develop a set of core public health capacities to be able to detect, assess and respond to infectious disease emergence⁹⁰.

The dynamics in South Asia are a product of complex domestic, bilateral, intra-regional and international geopolitical factors. The conflicts and tension in South Asia are shaped by troubled histories, thereby challenging cooperation in the region. Cross-border cooperation will allow migrants and mobile populations from poorer regions such as Nepal to seek a higher quality of health care in India and Bangladesh. Moreover, the development of solid border healthcare systems will generate employment and livelihood opportunities.

About 33.71 thousand people came into Bhutan between 2005-10, out of which 99% come from Nepal. A small number comes from Bangladesh and Myanmar. In Bangladesh, about 37% of the total migrants come from the neighbouring region of Myanmar. Likewise, Myanmar saw about 21.73 thousand migrants from Bangladesh between 2005-10. Nepal received 8.09 thousand migrants from Bhutan and 2.9 thousand from Bangladesh. Given the interconnectedness of countries, increased cooperation in cross-border health will allow the benefits to flow into other areas which remain tense and divisive.

The unabated spread of the coronavirus across the world highlights the close relationship between countries. The South Asian region owing to poor health systems, has borne high economic and social costs. India is a key player in South Asia, can proactively engage within WHO as well in organisations at the regional and international levels.

Cross-border health is an effective soft power tool for states to pursue their economic interests and advance international relations. Transborder spread of infection in the region can cause socio-political crises as well as strain diplomatic relations. Building a robust cross-border response is essential to security and peace in the region.

Moreover, the South Asian region is disproportionately affected by pandemics, natural disasters and humanitarian crises. Hence, leadership must step up to collaboration across borders. Experience dictates that aid is dependent on partnerships and trust across the border, as shown by the success of the polio programme.

Cross-border cooperation has a net benefit for countries, sometimes in economic terms. Cuba's health diplomacy programs have been materially beneficial, as reflected by Cuba's "oil for doctors" agreement with Venezuela. In another example, Brazil has used its successful HIV/AIDS programs to garner support from its southern allies, allowing it to push for bigger agendas such as a UNSC seat. In exchange for developing strong cross-border health intervention, access to natural resources in the neighbouring region is increasingly being practised in several parts of the world. The health interventions draw goodwill and are associated with increased FDI. For instance, China's need for natural resources in Africa is increasingly linked with Chinese health of diplomacy⁹¹.

India's engagement in the South Asian region is driven by historical contexts and political underpinning; however, it must change its narrative according to the image it seeks to project regionally and internationally.

By and large, countries must engage in cross-border integration of health systems because of the economic benefits, including access to raw materials and trade relations. Moreover, such cross-border involvements help in building alliances which prove helpful in critical moments. Given the geographical proximity of Bangladesh, Bhutan, Nepal and Myanmar, India stands to benefit from a cohesive system. Lastly, efforts to strengthen disease surveillance in parts of the countries where health systems are ineffectual shall prevent infectious diseases from spreading and threatening the entire region.

LOOKING BACK: EXPERIENCE OF CROSS-BORDER CONTROL OF COMMUNICABLE DISEASES

The successful management of cross-border issues is probably one of the most complex programmatic areas to achieve. It requires policymakers and decision-makers at the central ministry level to be in agreement and support these activities in synergism; secondly, it requires the technical staff to agree on the best approach for the work, and finally, it needs local government authorities, and perhaps non-governmental organizations, from both sides of the border to work together.

There are several examples of successful cross border collaborations, especially for disease surveillance, that could be used as best practices in terms of implementation of the devised action plans.

BETWEEN BBIN COUNTRIES

SEARO/WHO has taken lead to encourage cross-border control of priority communicable diseases. Initially it was an integrated approach involving Malaria, Kala-azar, HIV and Tuberculosis, later the focus shifted to specific diseases like malaria and kala-azar. No references are available for cross-border control of HIV and Tuberculosis.

1. Adopting integrated approach

1995-1998: Between these years the World Health Organisation (WHO) had organized several border meetings for SEAR countries (specifically Bangladesh, Bhutan, India and Nepal) to address the border Kala-azar and Malaria more effectively.

2001: An Inter-country meeting involving these countries on cross-border problems held in Kathmandu, Nepal, 6-9 March 2001 emphasized the need for development and implementation of Joint Plans of Action (JPA) to control four priority communicable diseases, namely: Malaria, Kala-azar, Tuberculosis and HIV/AIDS⁹²

This activity was further emphasized and endorsed during an inter-country meeting, New Delhi, India (July 2001)⁹³, and at the 54th session of SEA regional committee in Myanmar (September 2001)⁹⁴.

Recognizing that the intercountry cooperation for cross-border control of priority communicable diseases requires sensitivity and understanding as it inherently encompasses politics. It also requires special approaches because of the peculiar set of problems faced by border areas including inadequate health facilities, language barriers, remote areas that are poorly accessible, dichotomy between national and local policies, and lack of authority at the district level, the SEARO/WHO adopted the following principles for cross-border control of priority communicable diseases⁹⁵:

- Use of integrated and coordinated approaches with bottom-up planning and implementation in collaboration with the community;
- Recognize health problems and vulnerabilities of people living away from the mainstream in an environment prone to drug use and being free from “social control”
- Map health services on both sides of the border areas, both private and public;
- Formulate coherent policies for disease control for use on both sides of the border;
- Affirm the right of patients to receive services and medicines regardless of citizenship, place of residence and legal status;

- Build effective systems for exchange of information and expertise for joint planning and implementation;

Based on these principles, WHO planned pilot projects in 11 districts in adjoining border areas of Bangladesh, Bhutan, India and Nepal. Districts selected and identified for implementation of cross-border diseases control activities:

- Bangladesh (Sylhet) and India (Jaintia hill)
- Bhutan (Chukha, Samste) and India (Jalpaiguri, Darjeeling)
- India (Lakhimpur Kheri, East Champaran) and Nepal (Kailali, Bara, Rauthat).

The projects aimed at institutionalizing cross-border collaboration and information exchange among these countries for controlling HIV, TB, malaria, and kala-azar. The activities included situational analysis, advocacy, coordination, information exchange and capacity building⁹⁶.

As a part of this initiative, technical policies were agreed among programme managers and operational guidelines developed. Joint Plans of Action (JPOA) were finalized for selected districts along the border between Bangladesh and India, Bhutan and India, India and Nepal, and between Myanmar and Thailand. The Joint Plan of Action was finalized and signed by all sides except India^{97 98}.

2004: An assessment of the progress made in the pilot districts was presented at a Regional Consultation at Bangkok in 2004. Even though these projects did not fully achieve their objectives, they nevertheless achieved useful results, valuable lessons were learnt, and there were also some miscalculations.

Miscalculations:

- The magnitude and the scope of the project were far too ambitious and expectations were too high. Commitment on all sides needs to be increased.
- In addition, there was difficulty in the passing of information between different levels within each country. Likewise, the district levels are in need of capacity-building in order to acquire the ability to implement policies fully.
- The high level and frequency of health worker turnover severely impedes the continuity of the project.
- It was felt that the government policies were difficult to influence, expectations were often too high on some countries' ability to embrace changes in policy because of the sheer size of the administration and its limiting bureaucracy.

Recommendations⁹⁹:

The Regional Consultation provided some important recommendations for cross-border control of priority communicable diseases in selected border areas, like situation analyses to be done to assess their current situation, national resources should be allocated and, if needed, external resources should be mobilized for cross-border control of priority CDs through other agencies such as GFATM, and development partners; Border populations and migrants should be included in the existing surveillance as well as in planning, management, monitoring and evaluation systems; an information exchange mechanism should be established through periodic meetings at national and local levels, and through exchange of regular, standardized reports.

Lessons^{100 101}:

- i. Collaboration across border areas requires full cooperation and active participation from Governments on both sides of the border – not only at policy level but also at programme as well as operational levels.
- ii. Control of communicable diseases across borders has to do, not only with health sector but a multisectoral involvement at the country level including immigration, customs as well as NGOs active at border areas, and coordination between the countries based on Memoranda of Understanding, especially for establishing information exchange mechanisms across borders.
- iii. Cross-border control of priority communicable diseases is a difficult and complicated issue, needing bi- or multi-country collaboration. Moreover, border areas being remote and away from mainstream, lack the capacity for effective programme implementation and service delivery for existing and newly-emerging diseases. Thus cross-border projects must start modestly and build on the initial results.
- iv. Cross-border control of priority communicable diseases requires high level of commitment from participating countries and WHO in terms of human and financial resources. Even though commitment is often expressed at policy-level meetings, this does not get translated into action in the border areas.
- v. WHO, particularly at country level could play a facilitating and catalytic role among the countries in order to institutionalize intercountry cooperation. Similarly, there is a need to fully utilize the existing intercountry and interregional mechanisms such as ASEAN and SAARC.

The report of the in-depth evaluation was also discussed at the 57th Regional Committee meeting in 2004¹⁰². The salient observations were that:

- i. Despite many cross-border meetings organized by WHO, the follow-up actions appeared to be inadequate.
- ii. Though joint strategies, action plans, and pilot projects were developed but the success achieved was short-lived.
- iii. Collaboration with regional associations such as Association of South-East Asian Nations (ASEAN) and South-Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) is crucial to ensure the sustainability of cross-border activities.
- iv. All relevant resources, including local nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) and the community, need to be fully mobilized and involved. NGOs have an important role to play in the border areas, particularly in conflict zones.

These developments were a set-back for the integrated approach to address priority communicable diseases.

2005: An Asia Pacific Strategy for Emerging Diseases was developed in 2005 as a road map to strengthen core capacities in Member States for effective preparedness planning, prevention, prompt detection, characterisation, containment and control of emerging infectious diseases threatening national, regional and global health security. Recognizing that infectious diseases do not respect borders, the strategy underscored global partnerships, rapid sharing of data and other information, enhanced preparedness and evidence based control strategies towards fulfilling the broader requirements of IHR 2005 and covering public health events of potential international concern, irrespective of origin or source¹⁰³.

2007: IHR 2005 is an internationally agreed instrument for global public health security. It represents the joint commitment to shared responsibilities and collective defence against disease spread and has been legally binding for WHO Member States since June 2007. Its purpose is to prevent, protect against, control and provide a public health response to the international spread of disease. The control of diseases at border crossings remains an essential element of the regulations. The key elements of IHR highlight the need for local collaboration and actions on local issues that should not be restricted to a checkpoint approach only¹⁰⁴.

A bi-regional cross-border meeting on Emerging Infectious Diseases was organized by the World Health Organization ((WHO) **February 20 28-in Bangkok from 26 07** to review the status of cross-border disease control activities and develop a strategic framework for cross-border collaboration¹⁰⁵. The meeting provided a platform to discuss the development of core capacities for the implementation of International Health Regulations ((**2005-IHR** **border issues being sensitive, greater -Cross . political commitment is necessary to move forward. The need to involve regional political and phasized to ensure political economic institutions such as SAARC and ASEAN was em commitment, regional cooperation and sustainable development of cross-border activities.**

It advised to ensure political will and commitment at the highest levels to implement coordinated border health measures at jointly designated border crossings. It suggested the use of Asia-Pacific Strategy for Emerging Diseases (APSED) as a strategic framework to build and strengthen local core capacities for emerging infectious diseases and IHR implementation, including inter-sectoral collaboration in cross-border areas. It recommended development of coordinated/integrated surveillance for priority communicable diseases at cross-border areas, establishment of mechanisms for multi-sectoral intervention and referral arrangements and development of preparedness and contingency plans for border health management. It highlighted the importance of regular contact/meetings between neighbouring countries for information sharing and monitoring implementation of activities, and to increase access of migrant/displaced populations to health services and strengthen surveillance system in this population. The recommendations stressed the need to strengthen coordination and cooperation among stakeholders for cross-border collaboration at the local, national and international levels.

2012: A WHO inter-country consultation on networking for malaria control/elimination in the South-East Asia Region emphasized a revival with the inclusion of Myanmar and Sri Lanka for web-based information sharing, etc. Deliberations focused on consolidation of efforts through multi-pronged strategies by each Member State.

2. Disease Specific approach

2a. Malaria

2016: An inter country meeting on cross-border collaboration was held in New Delhi, India in 2016. This meeting underscored the urgent need to develop a framework for cross-border collaboration and undertake implementation in alignment with the GTS 2016–2030 and the Regional Framework for Action. The general objective was to strengthen collaboration for elimination of malaria in South Asia, contributing to a malaria-free South-East Asia Region by 2030. The specific objectives were to: (i) review the present malaria situation (including drug and insecticide resistance) and malaria programme activities and their quality/coverage in South Asian countries along the borders, including related challenges and existing cross border collaboration mechanisms; (ii) identify areas of practical and effective mechanisms of collaboration across borders to accelerate malaria elimination and prevent re-establishment of local transmission in malaria-free areas; and (iii) outline a framework for cross-border collaboration in malaria elimination in South Asia. The recommendations were to: develop a protocol

for assessment of malaria in cross-border settings; establish networks by designating/nominating focal persons (national, state and district levels), bilateral working groups and bilateral district-level coordination committees; set up a core group (WHO and national programme focal points) for immediate coordination action as well as a regional coordination mechanism (since it was noted that several Member States have set aside funds for this purpose but were not able to utilize them due to the lack of a functional mechanism); initiate high-level action, including but not restricted to MoUs, with the aim of creating an enabling environment for local action, starting with policy agreement by different ministries; collaborate with existing cross border mechanisms; review operational case definitions of malaria cases (indigenous/ imported) by WHO that are to be stringently followed by Member States; and provide an overall framework and platform for dialogue and for identifying priority interventions to be implemented at the local level, drawing on the lessons from other regions. Later, a protocol and a template were developed and some Member States undertook related situational analyses¹⁰⁶.

2017: A follow-up international consultation on cross-border collaboration for malaria elimination in South Asia was held in New Delhi in November 2017, initiated by the Government of India, with a focus on developing a draft strategic framework for a South Asia subregional cross-border collaboration network for malaria elimination. Along with establishing a broad consensus around working together, meeting participants also took important steps to define how cross-border collaboration to eliminate malaria should be translated into action. Subsequent to this meeting, an important document – Addressing the challenge of malaria across international border lines: Framework for South Asia Subregional Cross Border Collaboration Network – was developed.

sharing lessons learned from partners and country programmes. The 2017 Forum was convened in Thailand with the objective of strengthening partnership coordination toward malaria elimination in the GMS through the following measures: exchanging information (including activities and results) as well as best practices across partners; discussing the major challenges and gaps toward malaria elimination¹⁰⁷.

Recognizing the need for high-level political commitment, the Region’s Ministers of Health made a commitment towards a malaria-free South-East Asia Region by 2030 in November 2017 in New Delhi through signing the Ministerial Declaration on Accelerating and Sustaining Malaria Elimination¹⁰⁸.

2017: The Regional Action Plan 2017–2030 Towards 0. Malaria-Free South-East Asia Region was launched along with a framework for a South Asia subregional cross-border collaboration network to eliminate malaria.

2018: The WHO released *An operational framework for cross-border collaboration for a malaria-free South-East Asia Region* during the 71st Session of the WHO Regional Committee for South-East Asia drawing from a framework for a South-Asia subregional cross-border collaboration to eliminate malaria released in 2017.

Guided by the overarching vision of achieving a “Malaria-free South-East Asia Region by 2030” and achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals, an operational framework has been developed which focuses on helping Member States to:

- i. prevent and/or reduce transmission and disease burden with special emphasis on minimizing risk of importation of malaria cases;
- ii. prevent, and/or rapidly respond to, and control malaria epidemics; and
- iii. prevent re-establishment of malaria transmission..

This operational framework provides guidance on almost all issues important for addressing malaria through cross-border collaboration, including sharing of surveillance data, prioritization of responses and interventions according to epidemiological scenarios, key fronts for leadership and governance and monitoring and evaluation. It delineates next steps and identifies milestones and targets for the next 3 years¹⁰⁹.

2019: A two-day meeting on cross-border collaboration on malaria elimination along the India-Bhutan border was organized in Guwahati, Assam, India, on 4–5 November 2019 in collaboration with the WHO Country Office for India. The meeting was to translate various recommendations from previous meetings/consultations and to operationalize a mutually agreeable strategic “roadmap” with special emphasis on a border-relevant package of interventions at the subnational (district) level.

Bhutan aims to achieve elimination by 2023 and faces a distinct threat of missing the set elimination target and reintroduction of malaria in hitherto malaria-free areas due to cross-border issues.

Recommendations made at the meeting included district-to-district actions like sharing of malaria data through identified focal points; holding coordination meetings (quarterly) for joint review and planning; and synchronized implementation of interventions like LLIN distribution, IRS by districts. Facilities for diagnosis, treatment and follow up of treatment compliance to be made available irrespective of nationality. Surveillance needs to be strengthened and M&E be adjusted to burden reduction & elimination settings. Periodic epidemiologic analysis of each border district must be undertaken. It also emphasized on optimal cooperation and coordination between Bodoland Territorial Council (BTC)/BTAD and state NVBDCP in Assam¹¹⁰.

2020: A meeting of the National Malaria Programme Managers in the WHO South-East Asia (SEA) Region was held virtually in December 2020. The objective was to update on new global and regional guidance, review of progress in countries and coordination of malaria control and elimination-related activities in the Region, including cross-border collaboration. It urged member countries to develop cross-border roadmap with tangible actions, including surveillance and response within country and between countries sharing international border. It urged the WHO to provide technical support to countries on various aspects of malaria elimination including effective cross-border collaboration, and regional-level initiatives¹¹¹.

2021: To review current situation in cross-border collaboration for kala-azar and malaria elimination along the India international border with Bangladesh, Bhutan and Nepal and plan the way forward, a virtual meeting was held in September 2021. Amongst the common challenges identified were lack of priority towards commitment for cross-border collaboration, an sufficient and sustained resources for cross border component of the elimination strategy. It was suggested that first priority should be given to improve access to health care and to strengthen surveillance in border districts. Situational analysis and epidemiological assessment of each border district should be carried out and respective countries should upgrade their NSPs to strengthen the prevention, control, surveillance and monitoring and evaluation activities in border districts. The importance of multisectoral coordination and cross-border collaboration was reiterated¹¹².

2b. Kala-azar

Like HIV, malaria, and tuberculosis, kala azar was also a priority communicable disease identified for cross border control in Bangladesh, India and Nepal. But due to its epidemiologic characteristics of the disease the goal changed from control to elimination as a public health problem around the year 2000.

All of kala-azar endemic countries share a similar disease epidemiology. Among others elements, they share the same sand fly vector, the disease is concentrated in neighbouring areas, and people move across borders for trading, job opportunities, family reasons, etc. Therefore, the whole region is very vulnerable and the risk of reintroduction of the disease is huge where it has been eliminated. There are many examples of imported cases of kala azar and recent introductions in countries that were previously free of KA, like Bhutan where the first case was detected in 2009.

Cross-border issues form an integral part of the elimination strategy, the focus in the majority of the countries have been on in-country efforts.

The WHO's process of validation for kala-azar elimination identifies presence of a functional cross-border coordination mechanism, where relevant. And requires evidence of cross-border activities having been undertaken among implementation units, districts, States and countries. Now as countries near the elimination targets the importance of cross-border engagements has come out of the shadows.

For more than two decades, cross-border issue has been emphasized for kala-azar control and elimination, and has been recognized systematically in most meetings and documents ^{113 114 115 116 117 118 119 120 121 122 123 124 125 126 127 128}.

Cross-border issues have got overshadowed. Not much progress has been made on this front is borne out by the fact that in a meeting in September 2021, the programme managers of Kala-azar elimination programme have included lack of priority towards commitments for cross-border collaboration and insufficient and un-sustained resources for cross-border component as major challenges. Other operational obstacles include inadequate situation analysis to inform comprehensive planning and action as well as irregular follow-up and coordination support and absence of new and/or minimal use of existing platforms (web-based/electronic) for information sharing and harmonization of efforts. Multisectoral coordination was highlighted as an area needing immediate attention. This includes strengthening collaboration and coordination with other sectors such as finance, education, immigration, security, tourism, labour, private sectors and others in border districts within national borders, and to resolve the bottlenecks in improving access to health care in border districts along with improving the efficiency and impact of interventions to target population

Beyond BBIN Countries

Selected few are cited below, with four of them seen in greater detail.

Nigeria, Benin and Togo, 2017

During the multinational Lassa fever outbreak in 2017, Nigeria, Benin and Togo developed public health emergency response plans targeted at building border health. Analysis of population mobility and retrospective cholera surveillance data were important elements in their response plans. Nigeria recognized the importance of border communities and provided them with adequate training on detecting and reporting public health information. Border health systems can be made effective by including public health emergency response plans at the point of entry, prioritizing border areas and developing cross-border surveillance and coordination¹²⁹.

Nordic countries

Finland, Norway, and Sweden each have their own communicable policy to tackle communicable diseases with respect to cross-border movement and migration in the Baltic Sea area. Norway and Sweden have adopted a fortress-like approach by implementing border screening to prevent "importation" of certain communicable diseases¹³⁰. Norway has been conducting TB screening at its

borders and Sweden does it for SARS and smallpox. In Western Europe, there exists a division. On the one hand, countries are adopting an authoritative or interventionist approach, delegating considerable power to the state in the name of communicable disease control, as seen among Nordic countries. On the other hand, we have France and Spain, which make communicable disease control voluntary¹³¹.

Ecuador–Peru border region, 1990s

In recent years, malaria (*Plasmodium vivax* and *Plasmodium falciparum*) has been successfully controlled in the Ecuador–Peru coastal border region. From the mid-1980s until the early 2000s, the region experienced a surge in malaria transmission, which experts attributed to a combination of ineffective anti-malarial treatment, social-ecological factors (e.g., El Niño, increasing rice farming, construction of a reservoir), and political factors (e.g., reduction in resources and changes in management). In response to the malaria crisis, local leaders from El Oro and Tumbes joined together in the mid-1990s to forge an unofficial binational collaboration for malaria control. This natural partnership emerged to address the shared challenges of managing a malaria epidemic in a transient border population. Over the next 20 years, local public health leaders from both countries worked closely to strengthen surveillance and response strategies through sharing of resources, operational research to inform policy, and novel interventions to halt transmission. The close relationships and strong, stable leadership at the local operational level were keys to the success of the malaria control programmes.

The bi-national collaboration at the operational level was the fundamental component of the successful malaria elimination programme. This unique relationship created a trusting, open environment that allowed for flexibility, rapid response, innovation and resilience in times of crisis, and ultimately a sustainable control programme. Strong community involvement, and extensive microscopy network and ongoing epidemiologic investigations at the local level were also identified as crucial programmatic strategies.

The results illustrate that bi-national collaboration is key to a successful malaria elimination programme¹³².

Thailand and Cambodia, 2000-2010

The Promdan project was aimed to improve the health of Khmer migrant workers along the Thai-Cambodia border. The migrant population is at high risk for HIV. The project, while raising awareness about AIDS, also tried to address the socio-cultural needs of the community. Contraceptives to practice safe sex were made available on the boats and around brothels. A politically acceptable model was developed for intercountry immunization. Social interventions included encouraging family connections, saving, and fostering cultural understanding between Thai and Cambodian communities. The project was implemented through extensive support and collaboration between government agencies, civil society, non-profits, and private corporations. The project resulted in the increased knowledge of HIV/AIDS in the community, improved availability of contraceptives, higher level of health and enhanced community and familial interactions¹³³.

South-eastern European Health Network (SEEHN), 2001

The South-eastern European Health Network (SEEHN) was established in 2001 among the governments of Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Moldova, Montenegro, Romania, Serbia, and the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia. The group initiated a communicable diseases project aimed at strengthening both national and regional surveillance systems with a focus on cross-border collaboration. The group has been credited with preparing plans for influenza preparedness at national and regional levels and also the introduction of molecular techniques into influenza surveillance laboratories across the region.

The SEEHN communicable diseases project strategic plan comprised four stages. The first stage was directed towards strengthening national surveillance by building regional institutional and human capacity in public health surveillance. The next stage involved establishing national policy and guidelines for communicable disease surveillance. The state included harmonization of guidelines, case defining and procedures in tune with EU standards. The third stage was to increase integrated lab surveillance capacity and information exchange—the regional capacity to detect clusters of avian influenza. The final stage was laid emphasis on enhancing regional cooperation among the players. The SEEHN has created a platform where experts from the various domains are able to discuss emerging issues and challenges in communicable disease control without being tied down by social structure and administrative constraints¹³⁴.

East African Integrated Disease Surveillance Network,2002

The East African Integrated Disease Surveillance Network (EAIDSNet) was founded jointly by the ministries of health and academic institutions in Kenya, Tanzania and Uganda, later joined by Rwanda and Burundi. The network was formed in 2002 with the goal of integrating a disease surveillance system. The group directed efforts to strengthen district health management teams in border districts and to collaborate in the development of training programs for building credible surveillance and control efforts. The EAIDSNet has responded in the face of outbreaks of Rift Valley Fever, Marburg and wild poliovirus. The focus was on the animal-human health interface and the need to develop integrated surveillance strategies. The network undertook a simulation exercise on the Kenya-Uganda border to test national avian influenza preparedness and response plans; it also performed a review of information and communication technology competencies. Moreover, EAIDSNet developed and tested a web portal linking existing human and animal disease surveillance reporting systems across facilities in border districts¹³⁵.

Middle East Consortium on Infectious Disease Surveillance

The ministries of health of Israel, Jordan and the Palestinian Authority jointly established the Middle East Consortium on Infectious Disease Surveillance (MECIDS). The group streamlined their reporting methodologies, conducted joint training and data sharing, enhanced cross-border communication, and responded to cross-border outbreaks. MECIDS deployed preparedness planning exercises in response to the H5N1 outbreak in 2006; also conducted a series of national pandemic influenza table-top simulation exercises between 2007–2008, and a regional exercise in 2008¹³⁶

Vietnam and China, 2002

The border region of northern Vietnam and southern China is faced with increasing HIV infection the region. A peer-based HIV prevention intervention was carried out using social marketing of sterile needles and syringes for injection drug users (IDUs) in the border area. Peer educators collected and disposed of used needles and syringes, provided IDUs with a choice of new needles/syringes or coupons valid in pharmacies and clinics for new needles/syringes. Early in the project, multi-sectoral collaboration and acceptance of pharmacy vouchers and distribution of new needles/syringes by IDUs were met with great success. However, the fear of law enforcement authorities requires the separate collection of used needles/syringes and distribution of pharmacy vouchers and new needles by peer educators. In China, new needles/syringes and vouchers are largely being provided through the exchange.

Malakit, 2018

In French Guiana, gold miners enter the French Guianese forest from neighbouring countries, Suriname and Brazil. The mobile population working in these mines are vulnerable to malaria. The three countries combined efforts to reduce malaria proneness among the migrants. This cooperation led to the implementation of ‘Malakit’, a pilot aimed at evaluating a new strategy to control malaria among migrant gold miners working illegally in French Guiana. Health workers or “facilitators” provide the

participants with a self-diagnosis and self-treatment kit along with adequate training and material for the target group to be able to respond to malaria symptoms on their own in the absence of health care services¹³⁷.

Oyapock Cooperation Health, 2017-2020

Oyapock Cooperation Health (OCS) is an initiative by French Guiana and Brazil with a bid to stop the HIV epidemic along the border by developing a cross-border prevention and care network. OCS started with a screening campaign to uncover HIV infected population. Targeted screening is carried out on both sides of the border at sites frequented by particularly high-risk populations. The French Guianese NGO! Dsanté, the Brazilian NGO DPAC Fronteira, and the main French Guianese hospital, Centre Hospitalier Andrée Rosemon, are working together to implement the project. OCS provides the necessary infrastructure to screen, follow-up and treat HIV. On either side of the border, mediators facilitate communication between institutions of care and HIV-positive patients, as well as aid patients in accessing their rights. A 'housing first' initiative of around ten beds to individuals who need medical, therapeutic and social assistance at certain key instances in their lives. Postexposure prophylaxis (PEP) and pre-exposure prophylaxis (PrEP) are offered as a preventive treatment. PrEP promises to be particularly beneficial for at-risk populations such as sex workers and men who have sexual relations with men. Furthermore, OCS trains members of the community in sexual and reproductive health and education. OCS recruits individuals (ex. health professionals, teachers) already in place as verbal and visual educators¹³⁸.

Deep dives

Shared here are two examples highlighting the role of cross border collaboration in malaria control. One shows how the success achieved can be quickly undone by civil unrest; the second shows the importance of sustained funding to continue good work in cross border collaboration. Then there are two examples of how control of cross border transmission of poliomyelitis in the Horn of Africa was interrupted and finally, how cross border activities are playing a central role in the Onchocerciasis elimination programme in Africa. Finally, the Mekong Basin Disease Surveillance (MBDS) Network highlights the importance of trust in cross-border collaboration.

Each one of the examples has lessons for the South Asia cross border collaboration.

Cross border collaboration between Saudi Arabia and Yemen for malaria control, 1979

The promotion of cross-border collaboration for malaria control between Saudi Arabia and Yemen Arab Republic/ Yemen began in 1979. Actual coordinated control efforts began in 1980 and included co- planned malaria control activities, IRS using DDT and mass drug administration, and an integrated approach with schistosomiasis control. Meetings were held between Yemeni and Saudi ministries of health throughout the 1980s and 1990s and included the establishment of a permanent committee consisting of joint ministries of health, interior, foreign affairs, and finance. By April 2001, a Saudi–Yemeni inter-country committee was established at a meeting in Jizan, Saudi Arabia, which planned to coordinate information on malaria cases along the border, improve the mapping of focal risks, define priorities for coordinated control and increase malaria awareness among the border populations.

In July 2001, a meeting in Sana'a, Yemen, agreed to allow accessibility of malaria technical staff of both countries to cross the borders for the purposes of malaria activities, and special travel dispensation passes were provided to Yemeni and Saudi malaria program staff. This was important for joint activities that required tracing and following up of malaria cases and demonstrated an important political intergovernmental commitment to malaria. By 2002, the joint cross-border program of activities was established and remained operational through 2013. These activities were directly supported by the Saudi government and included border malaria units linked to mobile medical/surveillance teams to screen migrants with the provision of testing and treatment free of charge as well as vector control using

ultra- low volume fogging, IRS, and larviciding within a 10 km margin on each side of the border. Cross- border activities came to an abrupt end due to the escalating crisis in Yemen in March 2015.

Yemen has been a constant source of imported infections into Saudi Arabia given the high number of Yemeni's seeking employment or escaping decades of civil conflict. Between 2015 and 2017, 32% of all imported infections detected in all regions of the country were of Yemeni origin. Malaria remains entrenched on the Yemeni side, and conflict has led, since 2015, to a complete collapse of the health system and a humanitarian crisis that has resulted in large numbers of migrants fleeing the country or internally displaced

The impact of economic development in the face of continued threats of imported malaria, whilst hard to empirically quantify, cannot be ignored. The period of lowest malaria incidence (2008–2015) in Jazan and Aseer occurred during a time of rapid economic development (Fig. 2). It is hard to directly attribute the precise contributions of economic development versus aggressive local elimination strategies, cross- border collaboration protecting boundary areas, and drought, as these all occurred simultaneously throughout the surveillance period and must be viewed within a plausibility framework.

The case study provides a model to understand the complexity of elimination strategies across borders, building a historical narrative of malaria endemicity, changing receptivity through economic development and migration. This is a valuable exercise for all border areas where elimination is close on one side and intractable on the other¹³⁹.

Lubombo Spatial Development Initiative (LSDI),1999

This is acknowledged as the most successful demonstration of effective cross-border malaria control. Background: The Lubombo Spatial Development Initiative (LSDI) was a tri-country project between South Africa, Swaziland and Mozambique with the aim of accelerating socio-economic development in the region. The malaria component of the project was introduced to decrease the transmission of malaria in the region.

Beginning in 1999, this initiative contributed to sustained declines in malaria incidence, which unfortunately were rapidly undone when funding ended in 2011. To address this major gap, RIs should be explicitly funded for evaluations that measure their impact, ensuring cost-effective implementation. This collaboration was endorsed by the Heads of State of the three countries and committed the three national malaria control programmes to work together, sharing resources and technical expertise.

The area targeted for accelerated development was the northern KwaZulu-Natal Province of South Africa, eastern Swaziland and southern Mozambique; areas with high malaria transmission in the three countries. Although the LSDI was a highly successful initiative that succeeded in reducing the malaria burden in high transmission areas of the participating countries, the financial resources that had been committed to the programme by country partners did not materialize. As a result of the insufficient funds and problems with resource mobilization, the LSDI was terminated in 2011 after 12 years of remarkable success.

Swaziland's goal was to eliminate malaria by the end of 2015, but even this country with very low transmission of malaria experienced an upsurge of malaria. One of the major problems experienced by the malaria control programme in Swaziland is the importation of malaria from neighbouring countries, particularly Mozambique.

The largest proportion of imported malaria into Swaziland originates from southern Mozambique, most noticeably from the three southern-most provinces of Maputo, Gaza and Inhambane.

The implementation of cross border malaria control is highly achievable, as has been demonstrated by the LSDI. The implementation of cross border collaboration through the LSDI has been very successful and stands as an example of best practice on the African Continent. The LSDI very effectively demonstrated the impact of coordinated vector control and case management in a high transmission setting.

The 12-year period of the LSDI showed a substantial decrease in disease burden amongst the three countries involved when compared to the baseline year of 2000. The decrease in malaria cases was 99 % in South Africa and 98 % in Swaziland. Malaria prevalence in Mozambique decreased by 85 % over the same period.

However, after the LSDI ended, between 2012 and 2014, there was an upsurge of malaria cases in the sub-region, mainly as a result of migration from high transmission areas to low transmission ones. An upward trend in case data was counter to the goal of elimination.

Conclusion: South Africa and Swaziland benefitted from the LSDI and were able to sustain malaria control and progress to the stage of elimination. Mozambique could not sustain the gains made during the LSDI, and case numbers increased. Technical and financial resources are key challenges for malaria control and elimination interventions¹⁴⁰.

Lessons learnt

1. Border malaria is not only a public health issue but also a political, social and economic development issue. A border is a political boundary between countries, and political unrest, conflict or civil war, and social security issues are common in border areas. Such unstable political environments represent a hindrance to the health agenda, including malaria. Social and economic development in border areas is slower and often lags behind other areas.
2. Populations residing in border areas can be difficult to reach for a variety of reasons. Border areas can be remote with difficult terrain. Minorities, tribes or indigenous populations residing in border areas have their own cultures and languages, which create barriers for delivering interventions. Undocumented people engaged in illegal activities, such as mining, may have significant barriers to accessing malaria prevention or treatment.
3. In border areas, populations residing on two sides of the border often share the same community. Their movement is normally frequent, short-term and cyclical, and can be for business or personal purposes. Border malaria can occur due to different access to health care or unequal quality or cost for treatment.
4. Access to health services or coverage of interventions is sub-optimal in most border areas. Both border posts and community-based volunteer networks have been established to increase access to malaria services, but whether such measures are sufficient and effective should be assessed.
5. Health systems and surveillance in border areas are often suboptimal compared with other parts of the country. The quality performance of a surveillance system in border areas is the key to success. To achieve that, capacity building in local health facilities in border areas must be strengthened. Ensuring sufficient human resources and financial support, as well as technical support, monitoring and supervision, are important for maintaining a strong surveillance system in border areas.
6. Interventions:
 - a. Joint vector control, health education and response to outbreaks lower incidence rapidly and significantly, and such collaboration at the local level is most efficient.
 - b. Harmonised treatment policy on both sides of the border is likely to help reduce transmission.
 - c. Joint case investigation, foci investigation, response and follow-up help interrupt transmission in border areas.
7. Information-sharing and coordination:

- a. Difficulties in international coordination/border collaboration, as border areas, may not be a priority for the country with higher transmission.
- b. Information-sharing should happen at the local (district) level.
- c. When one country is more interested than the other, a joint project might aid cross-border collaboration.

Elimination of Onchocerciasis in Africa, 1992

Onchocerciasis is a parasitic infection caused by the filarial nematode *Onchocerca volvulus* and transmitted through the bites of black flies of the genus *Simulium* that breed in rivers and streams. The impact of mass treatment with ivermectin and supplemented by vector control in some countries has changed the global scene of onchocerciasis. Onchocerciasis is one of the 10 NTDs targeted for elimination through the WHO's Roadmap on NTDs. Achieving elimination requires sustained annual treatment coverage rates of >80 % at the community level for a period of 15–20 years.

There has been reported progress made in the elimination of onchocerciasis in Central and Southern American countries and in some localities in Africa. The target for elimination in the Americas has been set at 2022, while for 12 countries in Africa, this is expected in 2030.

The evolution of efforts to address onchocerciasis within the adjacent geography of three countries within the Mano River Union: Sierra Leone, Liberia and Guinea (Conakry), provides valuable lessons of how cross-border collaboration can evolve to ensure that health gains on one side of the border are secured through an appropriate cross-border integrated strategy.

An analysis of the practical steps taken in this example of cross-border collaboration yields a general set of lessons learned that can be applied to the range of political, administrative, operational, technical and financial elements of disease control programs. While each cross-border scenario is unique and each element may not be relevant in every situation, stakeholders engaged in confronting the need for cross-border collaboration for public health challenges should consider these options as levers that can be applied to strengthen their programs and lead to improved outcomes.

As long as diseases are not confined to national borders, the need will continue for effective cross-border collaboration to fight those diseases. The lessons learned from the onchocerciasis program in the contiguous areas of the countries of the Mano River Union provide a framework of principles that can be applied to other cross-border situations, not just for onchocerciasis but also for other PC NTDs. The principles cover a range of considerations: Political, administrative, operational, technical, and financial. All partners and stakeholders involved in these programs—WHO, national NTD programs, implementation NGOs—should actively consider how they can adapt and apply these principles in each unique geographic and political scenario.

Lessons learnt:

Political

- i. Achieve political commitment and authorization for collaboration at the highest level possible/necessary in each affected country
- ii. Link ongoing disease control efforts to higher-level political influence bodies to raise importance on the national agendas

Administrative

- i. Establish a guidance document that identifies the common objective of the collaboration and provides an objective reference of identified key issues for all parties to refer to in the course of the collaboration.

- ii. All written communications should be provided in the official languages of each participating country.

Operational

- i. Agree on a regular cycle of national disease task force strategy meetings, at a minimum annually.
- ii. Conduct more frequent cross-border committee meetings between district medical officers and associated partner organizations (e.g., NGDO) program teams to align on tactical implementation
- iii. Account for these statutory meetings in each country's budgeting process and work plans
- iv. Share existing training resources and co-develop new resources to ensure sufficient and similar health care worker training
 - i. Align each county's drug procurement requests to ensure adequate and non-duplicative coverage for border regions, also considering cross-border migration issues

Technical

- i. Create a mechanism to provide complementary technical/scientific support as necessary
- ii. Jointly institute strong monitoring and evaluation programs to ensure that all endemic villages are treated.
- iii. Develop joint data management and common reporting of treatment coverage and impact on disease.

Financial

- i. Advocate for and mobilise resources for the implementation of the common elements of the program¹⁴¹.

Interrupting wild poliovirus circulation in the Horn of Africa, 1999

In 2013, the outbreak of wild poliovirus (WPV) in the Horn of Africa (HOA) triggered an aggressive, coordinated national and regional response to interrupt continued transmission. Kenya, Somalia, Ethiopia, South Sudan, and other HOA countries share a range of issues like porous and sparsely populated borders, insecurity due to armed conflicts, and weak health systems with persistently under-resourced health facilities resulting in low-quality care and low levels of immunization coverage in mobile populations which enabled the outbreak. The continued risk of WPV importation demanded cross-border and intersectoral collaboration. The HOA CORE Group Polio Project (CGPP), with support from WHO, strategized to transform ad-hoc cross-border meetings and actions into a more sustainable, long-standing Cross-Border Health Initiative (CBHI). Its aim was to direct, develop and document cross-border activities. While the CBHI emphasizes the critical need for cross-border collaboration, it also recognizes the equal importance of each border health authority to pay special focus and attention to its border communities, facilities and high-risk mobile populations to mitigate the risk of cross-border importation of WPV.

The government-led high-level intercountry cross-border forums and CBHI has led to improved immunisation coverage and increased AFP detection among high-risk mobile populations, limiting the importation of WPV across borders.

The CBHI has demonstrated the value of an institutionalized approach that is collaborative and coordinated. This important strategy is adaptable to address other communicable diseases that transcend borders. The CGPP in the HOA has focused on improving access to vaccination services in high-risk mobile populations that straddle common borders.

As a testament to the power of collaboration, the CBHI's domain has expanded to integrate the control of other infectious diseases. In 2016, the health committees in Turkana and Garissa counties added a country coordinator for tuberculosis to promote discussions with Uganda and Somalia on tuberculosis management. The Kenyan counties that border Somalia has merged their county development integrated plans with cross-border county action plans and widened the role of their CBHI committees to address other diseases. The CBHI is now an integral part of the operational health plans of border health units and the annual work plans of the participating county departments of health, thus ensuring the sustainability of the CBHI after the end of the project. The CBHI has been critical in reaching underserved, high-risk mobile populations with oral polio immunisations and other health services. The CBHI model can be adapted for other health interventions that require strong partnerships to achieve similar goals¹⁴².

Lessons learnt

1. To achieve disease elimination or eradication, a well-structured and well-governed programme, a high-quality surveillance system, a clear strategy to efficiently reach high-risk and hard-to-reach populations, a timely response to detected cases/events, and high-quality coordination and synchronisation of activities – especially in border areas (international and national) – are essential.
2. The translation of technically sound strategies and policies into the lowest levels of implementation (at the lowest administrative division) is the key to success, but this is always challenging.
3. Health facilities at the community and district levels along borders are the primary stakeholders. They should be empowered to make decisions on the ground. Engagement with all stakeholders (such as immigration and customs officials from border districts) in the advocacy and implementation of strategies is beneficial to the interruption of transmission across borders. Timely communication between health workers and other stakeholders is needed.
4. Border areas should be considered a single epidemiological block, as such functional coordination is critical and joint implementation of programme activities is important. It should be recognized that success on one side is never a complete success and that in the end, coordination will benefit both countries that share a border. Periodic joint meetings should be organized to review progress and to plan for the future.
5. Some good practices suggest that in elimination settings, a buffer area of at least 20 km could be established to assure there is no reinfection.
6. A border issue is more of an operational issue, e.g., official communication from a high level to the border area can be time-consuming; no funding to support the work on the other side of the border.
7. Incorporating tools of modern biology (like genetics) can provide evidence of cross-border transmission.
8. The WHO plays a critical role in cross-border collaboration. In Africa, resolutions and protocols by the WHO are well-respected.
9. Anthropological studies about mobility patterns of specific groups can be useful in reaching mobile populations.
10. Sharing data and information can be challenging if it is politically sensitive. An agreement is needed on which variables are of the highest importance.

Mekong Basin Disease Surveillance (MBDS) Network, 1999

In February 1999, representatives of the six bordering countries - Cambodia, China (Yunnan and Guang-xi), Lao PDR, Myanmar, Thailand, and Vietnam convened in Bangkok, Thailand, and agreed to work closely to combat disease outbreaks in the Greater Mekong Sub-Region. At this meeting, facilitated by the Rockefeller Foundation, participating epidemiologists and policymakers proposed the creation of the Mekong Basin Disease Surveillance (MBDS) network and, upon returning to their respective countries, obtained approval from their ministers of health to establish MBDS. The development of MBDS was in direct response to the 1997 memorandum of understanding between the

World Health Organization (WHO) and the Association of South-East Asian Nations (ASEAN), which identified disease prevention and control as a priority for inter-country collaboration.

Objectives are to:

- i. Improve cross-border infectious disease outbreak investigation and response by sharing surveillance data and best practices in disease recognition and reporting, and by jointly responding to outbreaks;
- ii. Develop expertise in epidemiological surveillance across the countries; and
- iii. Enhance communication between the countries.

Governance: The health ministers of each MBDS member country signed two memoranda of understanding (the first in 2001 and the second in 2007) to provide an agreed framework for the governing structure and processes of the consortium:

- i. Each country would be represented by a country coordinator;
- ii. The country coordinator would work closely with cross-border coordinators responsible for designated sites where the extent of cross-border movement could lead to disease outbreaks;
- iii. A network secretariat would organize regular meetings of country and cross-border coordinators and support all members in the network's activities;
- iv. And an MBDS Executive Board, made up of one policymaker at the senior level from each member country, would set policy and link the network to higher levels of government.

Country coordinators are usually epidemiologists based in the health ministry departments responsible for disease surveillance; the MBDS Secretariat is hosted by the Thai Ministry of Public Health, which provides office space and other support. The leaders of MBDS realized the importance of institutionalization of the network and have been working towards this since 2008. In January 2012, MBDS formally registered in Thailand as a foundation (mainly to attract funding).

Trust-based relationship: While MBDS operates within an agreed governance structure and according to agreed processes, it is driven by informal trust-based relationships between MBDS member countries. Although mutual trust is the core value of the network, this trust did not appear overnight but grew steadily. In the first three years of MBDS existence, when the mutual trust was not strong, sharing outbreak information was difficult. However, as mutual trust improved, cross-border data sharing dramatically increased.

All founding MBDS leaders are still actively involved in network activities. This crucial continuity of leadership is also apparent at the border sites; for example, the Mukdahan and Savanhnaket health staff on the Thai-Lao borders regularly communicate with each other informally, as villagers and patients frequently cross the border. In a trip to the Bokeo and Chiang Rai site, a colleague working for one of MBDS's international partners observed the cordial relationship between the staff of the local health departments of Lao PDR and Thailand and the active exchange of information taking place between them using modern technologies. Language is often a barrier in communicating, but this was not the case as the two countries understood each other's languages.

International Organizations Partnering With MBDS

A number of partners contributed to the development of MBDS.

- i. The RF was the primary and first donor and provided core support from 1998 to 2012.
- ii. Agence Française de Développement (AFD);
- iii. Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation Emerging Infections Network (APEC EINet) maintained by the University of Washington;

- iv. ASEAN Plus Three Emerging Infectious Disease (EID) Programme under the auspices of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) Secretariat and funded by the Australian Agency for International Development (AusAID);
- v. Asian Development Bank Greater Mekong Sub-regional Communicable Diseases Control Project (ADB-GMS-CDC);
- vi. Innovative Support to Emergencies, Diseases and Disaster (InSTEDD);
- vii. Kenan Institute Asia; Nuclear Threat Initiative Global Health and Security Initiative (NTI GHSI); Program for Monitoring Emerging Diseases (ProMED), an activity of the International Society for Infectious Diseases (ISID);
- viii. RAND Corporation;
- ix. World Health Organization (WHO);
- x. World Organization for Animal Health (OIE);
- xi. United Nations System Influenza Coordination (UNSIC).

Other collaborations: MBDS has itself contributed to the development of other similar regional

Strategy	Country responsible	Partner support
Enhance cross border communication and information exchange	Lao PDR	ADB-GMB-CDC, ASEAN Plus Three EID Programme, K.L. Asia, RF
Improve the human-animal sector interface and strengthen community surveillance	Vietnam	ADB-GMB-CDC, ASEAN Plus Three EID Programme, KL. Asia, ProMed, RF, WHO
Develop human resources and strengthen epidemiological capacity	Thailand	ADB-GMB-CDC, APEC EINet, ASEAN Plus Three EID Programme, INSTEDD, K.L. Asia, NTI GHSI, ProMed, RAND, RF, University of Washington Center for Excellence in Public Health Informatics, WHO
Strengthen capacities for information and communications technologies	Cambodia	ADB-GMB-CDC, APEC EINet, InSTEDD, K.L. Asia, ProMed, RF, University of Washington Center for Excellence in Public Health Informatics
Strengthen laboratory capacity	China	ADB-GMB-CDC, AFD, ASEAN Plus Three EID Programme, InSTEDD, K.L. Asia, NTI GHSI, RF, WHO
Strengthen risk communications	Myanmar	ADB-GMB-CDC, ASEAN Plus Three EID Programme, ProMed, RF, WHO
Conduct and apply policy research	Collective	ADB-GMB-CDC, ASEAN Plus Three EID Programme InSTEDD, RAND, RF.

networks through the active involvement of its members.

Collaboration with Partners

During the third phase (2008 to 2011), network activities fell within seven core strategies, each strategy led by one country based on its capacity or its interest to develop the relevant capacity, and supported by partners:

The MBDS serves as a model for regional disease surveillance in other parts of the world.

Lessons Learnt

Trust-based collaboration: First, there is a big difference between running a project and running a longer-term trust-based collaboration. A project has an end date and responsible persons whose aim is to achieve the agreed results in due time no matter what will happen. A collaboration whose goal is to build trust requires more time and does not inherently have an end date. Trust cannot be established without the type of common understanding among member countries that can only be gained through continuous engagement. Only by working with each other over time, for example, by making decisions about difficult situations through “consensus” and by rotating leadership of the network on an annual basis, did MBDS establish trust and derive strength from it. The mutual trust established over these years is a strong platform for sustaining MBDS collaboration into the future.

Working with the Governments: Most disease surveillance systems in the region and elsewhere are mainly run by government systems. It was a prudent decision at the beginning to place MBDS within the official governance structures of each country. For example, the fact that country coordinators are government officials who already know each other and are friendly to each other facilitates MBDS operations and makes MBDS contributions integral to government operation¹⁴³.

Efforts towards cross-border disease control in other countries

Policy Frameworks in other countries

Australia

National Framework for Communicable Disease Control, 2014

The envisions bringing together government, agencies and committees for strengthening the countries response to communicable diseases. The framework has two key objectives

- Improved communicable disease prevention, detection, and response
- Improved organisation and delivery of communicable disease control

Moreover, the framework outlines the implementation of evidence-based national prevention policies—the improvement in the delivery of communicable disease prevention measures and improving the health of vulnerable populations. The framework accords priority to areas that include populations that suffer a disproportionately high burden of communicable diseases, typically refugees and immigrants¹⁴⁴.

France’s strategy for global health, 2017

The strategy envisages strengthening international health security and supporting the capacity building of states using a preventive approach to implement the IHR in conjunction with the WHO. Moreover, the strategy calls for developing exchanges and partnerships between health authorities for joint health programs and information immigrants¹⁴⁵.

European Action Plan for HIV/AIDS 2012–2015

The plan outlines optimization of HIV prevention, diagnosis, treatment and care outcomes. The plan acknowledges that certain key populations are at higher risk, and the response should focus on these key populations. The key population includes migrants.

Moreover, the plan directs HIV testing and counselling: to reduce the size of the undiagnosed population and the number of late HIV diagnoses by expanding access to and increasing early uptake of HIV testing and counselling services, especially in key populations at higher risk.

The plan calls for the prevention of sexual transmission of HIV by implementing behavioural change communication, increasing access to reliable, affordable and high-quality condoms and water-based lubricants and other specific priority actions among migrants.

Regional Action Plan for HIV in SEA Region

The Regional Action Plan for HIV in SEA Region envisions zero new infections, zero HIV-related deaths and zero discrimination and targets the ending of AIDS epidemic as a public threat by 2030. The strategy moves from control to elimination. The plan promotes outlines a people-centric approach and underlines the principles of human rights and health equity.

The Regional Action Plan for HIV prioritises the following

- (i) Combination prevention for key populations – sex workers and their clients, MSM, PWID and transgenders
- (ii) Diversifying testing, treating and viral load suppression for most-at-risk group
- (iii) Enabling environment by reforming HIV-related legal and human rights concerns
- (iv) Strategic information and data reporting system built using standardised indicators
- (v) Developing financial sustainability by utilising HIV investment cases to advocate for adequate allocation of domestic resources and mobilizing external funding support
- (vi) Involving community in the planning and delivery of services as well for gathering socio-behavioural inputs and identifying challenges.

The actions outlined in the Regional Action Plan serve to guide Member States to achieve the 2020 targets on HIV prevention¹⁴⁶

The target for the WHO European Region by 2015 is the reduction in the number of new HIV infections acquired through sexual transmission by 50%, including migrants

As per the plan leveraging broader health outcomes through HIV responses has the following priority areas of intervention:

Tuberculosis programme: to reduce the burden of tuberculosis among people living with HIV, and that of HIV in people with tuberculosis, by implementing collaborative activities and integrating tuberculosis and HIV programmes, especially recognizing the high proportions of multidrug-resistant and extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis in the region and among migrants who have both diseases.

Laws and regulations related to the HIV response

Objective: To address laws and regulations that present obstacles to effective HIV prevention, treatment, care and support, and to strengthen the enforcement of protective laws and regulations.

The target for the WHO European Region by 2015

- All Member States will have enabling laws and regulations for equal, non-restricted access to effective HIV and related health services and will enforce them
- Ensure that national laws recognize the right to health and do not create barriers to HIV and related health services for undocumented persons, including migrants and asylum seekers
- Remove mandatory or compulsory HIV testing and mandatory/compulsory disclosure of HIV status, including for prisoners and migrants¹⁴⁷.

EU Standards for public health and tuberculosis prevention Standard 18

All care providers for patients with tuberculosis should ensure that persons who have been in close contact with active and infectious tuberculosis patients are evaluated and managed in line with international recommendations.

Clinicians and national programme managers are to interact with the relevant health authorities of host and/or home countries of tuberculosis patients belonging to migrant groups or mobile populations to ensure a continuum of care and contact investigation as appropriate

Standard 21

All providers must report both new and re-treatment tuberculosis cases and their treatment outcomes to local public health authorities in conformance with applicable legal requirements and policies. This principle is also applicable to tuberculosis patients moving across EU borders.

Ministry of Labour and Employment of Ordinance No. 1,927, dated December 10th 2014, sets guidelines for combating discrimination against people with HIV and AIDS in the workplace. The Ordinance determines that it is a discriminatory practice to require that workers, including migrants, people looking for employment, and job applicants provide a recent HIV test result¹⁴⁸.

South Africa

Malaria Elimination Strategic Plan 2019-2023

- The goal of this Malaria Elimination Strategic Plan is to achieve zero malaria transmission in South Africa by 2023
- The constitution of South Africa grants everyone, including migrants and travellers' access to health services, enabling any individual to be appropriately tested and treated for malaria.
- Integration with other government stakeholders and partners for implementing key interventions and cross-border malaria initiatives
- National Malaria Programme is responsible for developing policy and guidelines, providing technical assistance to provincial malaria programmes, building the capacity of the programme at all levels, coordinating partners and cross-border collaboration, advocating for resource mobilisation, and political commitment.

One of the objectives of the plan includes providing effective management, leadership, and coordination for the optimal implementation of malaria elimination interventions at all levels by 2020.

Under this objective, the country will strengthen cross-border and inter-district collaboration for malaria elimination.

Regional initiatives such as Elimination 8 (E8), MOSASWA (Mozambique, South Africa and Swaziland (Eswatini)) and Trans-Limpopo Malaria Initiative (TLMI) need to be sustained and strengthened through the establishment of cross-border operational committees, synchronisation of cross-border operations, and harmonisation of cross-border policy.

The third objective is to ensure that 90% of the population affected by malaria receives information education communication messaging by 2023.

Behaviour change communication is envisaged under this objective. Messages should be disseminated throughout the year, with intensification leading up to malaria season and around the peak holiday seasons, when there is significant population movement within South Africa and across borders.

Partnerships with neighbouring governments must be strengthened to address regional case importation. Functional malaria elimination committees and advisory groups must also be in place to offer technical and management guidance to malaria programmes at all levels¹⁴⁹.

South Africa's National Strategic Plan for HIV, TB and STIs 2017-2022

Increase cross-border co-operation: To improve responses for migrant labourers, especially with respect to TB, South Africa will continue to strengthen cross-border co-operation with neighbouring governments and other stakeholders.

The plan makes a case for the following customized and targeted intervention to reach the mobile population, migrants' and other undocumented foreigners. Following interventions are included:

- Provision of health services along the transport corridors
- Flexible service delivery options including the provision of condoms, provision of ART refills and TB treatment
- Focused prevention messages addressing specific challenges
- Intensified psychosocial support
- Cross border collaboration on HIV, TB and STI policy and programming
- Utilise informal networks to raise awareness about services
- Accelerated access to official papers to access services
- Places of safety
- Implementation of social impact plans that mitigate the impact of HIV, TB and STIs, for organisations involved in big infrastructure and construction projects, e.g. building power stations, major roads^{cxiv}

CLMV countries

In line with UNAIDS strategy, countries adopted a comprehensive HIV/AIDS control program including public education, 100% condom distribution, voluntary counselling and testing, and continuum of care

China has had bilateral agreements in place with Myanmar, Laos and Vietnam for cross-border control activities of HIV/AIDS, TB, and malaria. Thailand also has sponsored cross border activities with Myanmar, Cambodia and Laos. These are examples of effective collaboration. Dengue is a priority for such support.

The International Office of Migration has been piloting TB screening programs for international and cross-border migrants. Only for international travel at the port of entry, a health form may be filled up, a contact number obtained, and a thermal scan is done, but this is usually not done at land or seaport of entries. Offering people with health problems voluntary screening facilities at the border may identify new cases of infectious diseases. They could be offered treatment and screening of family members.

Infection control progress has been made with informal information exchange among national CDC units and among cross-border provincial governments with the support of local governors. Following several meetings, governments have agreed on formulating guidelines and standard operating procedures (SOPs). The regional workshops and technical forums proved very useful. Regional and cross-border activities have helped to establish quite a good network among ministries, provinces and experts, but this would also benefit from making it more formal. GMS CDC projects were able to provide bridge funding through a regional pool mechanism managed by the regional coordination unit (RCU)¹⁵⁰.

ECONOMIC COST OF NOT CONTROLLING COMMUNICABLE DISEASES

Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) and cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) are used extensively for the purpose of program evaluation. While CEA establishes a relation between the costs of the intervention and the benefits or outcomes it generates. Cost-benefit analysis is useful in assessing whether the economic benefits outweigh the economic costs of a policy.

This chapter provides an overview of both types of analyses for communicable diseases vis-a-vis intervention. Given the inherent challenges in estimating and calculating program costs and benefits, these examples are taken from across the world and not limited to SEA¹⁵¹.

The obvious financial costs of communicable diseases such as AIDS and TB include medical care, drugs, and funeral expenses. Another significant cost is the loss of productivity, costs to firms in replacing, training and hiring new workers etc.

The two high economic costs are reduced labour supply and increased costs. The loss of young lives in their most productive years will affect overall economic output.

HIV/AIDS

Studies across the globe reflect the costs of inaction in controlling communicable diseases.

Africa

In Tanzania, an HIV caused death reduces per capita food consumption by 15 per cent in the poorest households. Children in HIV-afflicted houses are malnourished and suffer from high drop-out rates. A study in Tanzania revealed that 8 percent of total household expenditure went to medical care and funerals in households that had an adult death in the preceding 12 months. This value was 0.8% in houses with no deaths¹⁵².

In Kagabiro village, Tanzania, in households afflicted by AIDS - 29% of household labour was spent on AIDS-related treatment and funeral services. If two people were involved in looking after the affected family member, the total labour loss was 43%, on average¹⁵³. It was estimated by the Government of Tanzania, the World Bank and the World Health Organization in 1991 that the total GDP of the country will be 15 to 25 percent smaller in 2010 because of the impact of AIDS¹⁵⁴.

In Cote d'Ivoire, 80 percent of the expenditures were directed towards AIDS patient. With the death of the AIDS-affected member, the average consumption fell by as much as 44 percent during the following years¹⁵⁵.

In Uganda, household saving was directed mainly towards healthcare and funeral costs of HIV positive family members¹⁵⁶. In Ethiopia, a study found out that the average cost of treatment and funeral expenses in an HIV afflicted household was several times the average household income¹⁵⁷.

A study in Zimbabwe found that the cost of AIDS is even higher than for other companies that do not provide health benefits. The study found that a transport company had 3,400 workers infected with HIV, and 64 died from AIDS in 1996. The total costs of AIDS to the company in 1996 were estimated at Z\$39 million, equal to about 20 per cent of the company's profits¹⁵⁸.

Another study by the Zimbabwe Farmers Union (ZFU) found that the death of a breadwinner due to AIDS cuts reduces the marketed output for staple crops as a large sum of investment has to be redirected from agriculture to medical expenses¹⁵⁹.

Reduction in Marketed Output Due to AIDS Deaths in Zimbabwe	Reduction in Marketed Output
Maize	61%
Cotton	47%
Vegetables	49%
Groundnut	37%
Cattle Owned	29%

A World Bank study estimated the impact of AIDS in 30 sub-Saharan African countries and found a likely reduction of the annual growth rate of GDP of 0.8 to 1.4 percentage points per year and a 0.3 percentage point reduction in the annual growth rate of GDP per capita.

Countries that provide healthcare subsidies will face the brunt of increased government spending in the event of the disease spreading further. If the infections in India rose to about 5% of the adult population in the next ten years, the government's spending on health would increase by another one-third. If India were to subsidize at least half the cost of healthcare, the AIDS epidemic would have increased government spending by about 41 per cent¹⁶⁰.

Canada

In Canada, the estimated total cost of screening would have been \$3.3 to \$3.4 million. The in-hospital costs of treating HIV-infected immigrants in whom AIDS developed between 1989 and 1998 would have been \$5.0 to \$17.1 million. Accordingly, screening would have saved \$1.7 to \$13.7 million over the ten years after immigration. The economic cost of screening is much lower than the costs of treatment. Accounting for social costs and public good timely screening of cross-border traffic can thus prove very beneficial.

France

Early ATC strategy proved cost-saving or cost-effective in the worst-case scenario. In the most favourable scenario, early ATC generated an average net saving of €198,000 per patient and prevented 0.542 secondary infections. In the worst-case scenario, the early ATC strategy generated an average cost of €28,000, a cost-effectiveness ratio of €133,000 per averted infection and prevented 0.211 secondary infections. Interpretation In addition to individual health benefits, improving early ATC for migrant PLHIV proves an efficient strategy in terms of public health and economics.

Migrants accounted for 46% of newly diagnosed cases of HIV infection in France in 2013. Early and late access to care is defined by an entry into care with a CD4 cell count of 350 and 100/mm³, respectively. A study reveals that early ATC generates an average net saving of \$2,23,920 per patient and prevents 0.542 secondary infections. In the worst-case scenario, early ATC generates an average net saving of \$36,188 per patient and prevents 0.299 secondary infections. Early access to care can reduce burdens on public health along with individual health benefits.

TUBERCULOSIS

The economic burden of TB between 2006 and 2015 for the twenty-two high TB burden countries, including India, is estimated to be about \$3.4 trillion. China accounts for more than a third of the overall economic burden of the countries in consideration, and India and China together account for more than half. The implementation of sustained DOTS in the twenty-two high-burden countries would result in an estimated economic gain of around \$1.6 trillion¹⁶¹.

India

The average financial cost incurred by a TB patient is about USD 7500 (INR 525000) in India, which is 137% of the per capita income of the Indian economy. The cost does not include the social costs incurred by the disease.

USA

Expanding the Directly Observed Treatment Short-course by the USA to the neighbouring regions of Mexico at the cost of \$34.9 million would result in 2591 fewer cases of tuberculosis in the United States, with 349 fewer deaths from the disease and net discounted savings of \$108 million over a 20-year period.

The expansion of the DOTS program would still remain cost-effective if initial investment were doubled, if the United States paid for all antituberculosis drugs in Mexico, or if the decline in the incidence of tuberculosis in Mexico was less than projected.

Moreover, the addition of tuberculin skin testing to the radiographic screening of legal immigrants from Mexico would result in 401 fewer cases of tuberculosis in the United States but would cost an additional \$329 million. Similarly, a \$9.4 million investment to expand the DOTS program in Haiti and the Dominican Republic would result in net US savings of \$20 million over a 20-year period¹⁶².

Malaria

Ghana

The costs and benefits of three major malaria interventions in Ghana - continuous and sustained LLIN distribution, seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC) in Northern Ghana and increase in testing and treatment of suspected malaria cases have been evaluated in a study by Copenhagen Consensus.

The analysis describes that. Our analysis shows that a continuous bed net distribution that reaches and sustains at 90 per cent coverage of households (from 56% currently), has the potential to avoid 40,390 deaths between now and 2030, leading to benefits 44 times the cost. Moreover increasing access to rapid diagnostic testing of suspected malaria cases in health facilities has the potential can avoid 24,770 deaths by 2030¹⁶³.

Intervention	Total Net Present Cost (2018-30)	Health Benefits	Economic Benefits
Distribute and sustain 90 per cent coverage of LLIN	GH¢ 442 million	Avoid 12.9m cases of uncomplicated malaria, 696,000 cases of severe malaria and 40,390 deaths	Morbidity avoided benefits of GH¢ 9 million, mortality avoided benefits of GH¢ 139 million in 2018, with benefits expected to increase to GH¢ 230 million and GH¢ 4,803 million respectively in 2030

Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention to 90% of the children in the Guinea Savannah zone	GH¢ 167 million	avoid 964,000 uncomplicated cases, 72,400 severe cases and 3,265 deaths between 2018 and 2030	GH¢ 116 million initially rising to GH¢ 496 million by 2030
Universal testing and treatment of suspected cases presenting at health facilities	GH¢ 87 million	Avoid 434,780 severe cases, 24,700 deaths, reduction in uncomplicated malaria cases (17,330 in total to 2030) between 2018 and 2030	GH¢ 211 million in the first year, rising to GH¢ 2,689 million by 2030

Source: Cost-Benefit Analysis of Selected Malaria Interventions in Ghana, Ghana Priorities, Copenhagen Consensus Center, 2020.

Note: Ghanaian cedi, GH¢ is the unit of currency of Ghana

Another study on the potential impact of large reductions in malaria incidence on economic outcomes found that the relative contribution of reductions in malaria mortality to the size of the labour force would increase over the period 2016–2030 (from 1.2% to 4.7%)¹⁶⁴.

A study conducted by Jeffrey Sachs and John Gallup in 2001 compared the income of malaria-endemic countries with the payment of non-endemic countries at different points during the period 1965–1995. The study revealed that malaria-endemic countries had per capita income levels that were 70% lower than those of non-endemic countries. Moreover, a 10% reduction in malaria case incidence was associated with a nearly 0.3% increase in the level of per capita income over the period 2000–2017. A 100% reduction in malaria case incidence would result in an average per capita income increase of nearly 3%. Furthermore, malaria elimination in the lowest income countries would increase the national per capita income by nearly 16%.¹⁶⁵

In Zambia, an integrated environmental management practice coupled with rapid diagnostics, testing and the use of bed nets averted an estimated 14,122 deaths, 517,284 malaria attacks and 942,347 work shift losses. The cumulative costs of malaria control interventions were US\$ 11,169,472 (in 1995 US\$). The programmes averted an estimated US\$ 796,622 in direct treatment costs and US\$ 5,678,745 in indirect costs as a result of reduced work absenteeism. Integrated malaria control in copper mining communities increased copper production and revenue equivalent to US\$ 7.1 billion (in 1995 US\$)¹⁶⁶.

A study conducted in Nepal empirically analyses curative and preventive costs and benefits of its malaria elimination program from the perspectives of both service providers in the public sector and people who are at risk. The curative intervention of the malaria elimination program is economically viable in Nepal with a net present value (NPV) of USD 23 million, benefit-cost ratio (BCR) of 1.58 and internal rate of return of 63%. Malaria preventive intervention is highly beneficial, with an NPV of USD 435 million and a BCR of 2.13. An annual investment of USD 36.59 million can bring societal benefits of USD 92.81 million. The government can save USD 132 million by the end of 2025¹⁶⁷.

KALA-AZAR

A study in Bihar conducted the stratified multistage sampling of 15,178 households with 214 individuals infected in the previous 12 months found that eighty-five per cent of individuals with VL

were unable to perform normal daily activities for some period of time. Daily activities were restricted for an average of 30 days.

However, because a large proportion of the affected is children and women who are not engaged in work outside the home, only 36% report any loss of workdays and income. Those who did miss work because of VL lost a median of 120 days, with a median income loss of INR 6000 (\$146). The average daily income loss was approximately INR 50 (\$1.22), which is consistent with estimates of the daily wage in the district. The estimated total household VL treatment expenditure with the estimated household income loss yields an estimate of INR 8610 (\$210)¹⁶⁸.

Cross-sectional data were collected from different sources to estimate societal costs of and benefits from Kala Azar interventions with a 13-year project period in Nepal. Total costs are estimated based on the unit cost of inputs used for interventions. A total discounted net benefit of Kala Azar intervention is Nepalese Rupees (NRs) 65,287 million. The study suggests that every rupee invested in KA intervention at present will yield NRs 71 in future. Given the infectious nature of the disease, regional benefits from the interventions will be much higher¹⁶⁹.

Cross-border control and elimination of communicable diseases is a profitable investment due to the ability for it to pay itself with future reductions in spending and generate better economic returns. The elimination requires additional investments into robust surveillance systems to detect and respond to remaining cases. Financial investments in reduction need to be equated with benefits in maintaining the status quo. The elimination delivers additional indirect benefits outside of health- other countries benefit from the reduced spread, thereby granting positive externalities to neighbouring countries.

The start-up costs of disease elimination are not known with much clarity. Most of the studies in this domain use financial costs, and therefore, the true cost of the human resources and program management and health system strengthening is not known. The cost of non-health benefits can also not be known.

In the short term, the investment needed to achieve elimination is likely to initially be equal to or higher than that of a control programme. However, the total benefits of elimination, many unquantifiable, will greatly outweigh its cost. Estimating the health and economic costs thus becomes a vital factor in sustaining elimination and control programmes.

MAPPING OF PARTNERS AND STAKEHOLDERS

Partner mapping was undertaken by listing partners whose names were found in scientific publications, meeting reports, expert group / technical group consultations, publications and annual reports of UN agencies, and major global partnerships. Each of these lists were then examined to ensure consistent categorisation. The acronyms were converted into full forms names consistent across lists. The list was then grouped under four diseases viz. HIV, Kala-azar, malaria and tuberculosis.

The list is as complete as possible but does not represent the ever changing partners' numbers. Instead, it provides an impression of partner makeup across the diseases.

Categorization

For this review, the categorisation of partners adopted is as follows:

1. Research and Development: This includes partners that are involved in product discovery and development of new therapies (vaccines, treatments etc.);
2. Technical assistance/service support: This includes those that provide drug donations, support improved service access and give technical assistance;
3. Advocacy (national and international levels): includes partners who advocate for an increased international and national response to specific diseases, fundraise for specific control programmes etc.
4. Financing includes providing funds for specific programmes (not as donations).

The partners have also been categorised as having primary or secondary roles vis-à-vis the above areas. Partners could be individual entities (like research or academic institute), or a consortium (like KalaCORE) or a regional initiative or global partnerships or a UN agency.

Partnerships can be defined as collaborative working relationships where partners can achieve more by working together than they can independently. Effective partnerships produce synergy when the partners' complementary skills, resources, perspectives, and shared know-how lead to more effective solutions^{lxixiii}

A consortium is a group of two or more entities that come together under a banner to support a cause and choose to request financial support as a single application. The role and responsibility of each partner are cut out. The Consortium generally dissolves once the funding dries up.

Unlike a consortium, regional initiatives (RIs) are multi-country and multi-sector partnerships with governmental support that work towards a common aim, like malaria elimination. Examples of RI are the Asia Pacific Malaria Elimination Network (APMEN), Asia Pacific Leaders Malaria Alliance (APLMA), Regional Artemisinin-resistance Initiative (RAI).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for Partners

To decide which stakeholders to consider, a list of inclusion and exclusion criteria was defined: For global partners: active on more than one continent, especially South Asia. For regional partners: active in more than one country

Partners were included if their work was primarily related to cross-border involvement. Organizations working exclusively on issues of drug resistance or focusing exclusively on basic and clinical research on specific parasitic (malaria and Kala-azar) bacterial diseases (e.g. tuberculosis), and virus (HIV) were not considered. To be included, organizations must have demonstrated interest in the area of cross-border and must be actively involved in it. As a result, only partners, which were active at some point over the last three years were considered for inclusion.

National initiatives were excluded when their work focused entirely on interventions in one country. National and State /Provincial Governments are the most important partners, but not mentioned individually. NGOs were included if they were working in border districts tackling one or more of the identified communicable diseases.

A list of partners with input from experts was developed, mainly WHO SEARO staff dealing specifically with malaria, Kala-azar, tuberculosis and HIV, and have worked in various positions in the specific disease. Annexe 2 provides the list of experts contacted. The experts were also asked about the availability of written information, including specific partners' statements related to the cross-border issues.

It was possible to identify partners working in cross-border activities in malaria. As several have had the experience of being involved in sub-regional malaria elimination programmes, at least forty countries have been certified as malaria-free in the world, and two of them are in the neighbourhood Sri Lanka and Maldives. Further, two (Bhutan and Nepal) have the potential to achieve zero indigenous cases of malaria. Matrix for engaging with these partners has also been worked out.

But similar success could not be achieved for partners in Kala-azar. Though countries of the SEA region have overshot elimination targets and countries, especially Bangladesh, have made appreciable progress in achieving elimination targets, limited or no work has been done on cross-border issues. Therefore, it has not been possible to identify partners engaged in cross-border control activities. Instead, partners working on eliminations have been given. Therefore, it has not been possible to identify partners engaged in cross-border control activities. Instead, partners working on eliminations have been given.

The search for partners in HIV and Tuberculosis working on cross-border issues was not fruitful. The emerging issue is providing diagnosis, treatment and follow-up facilities to migrants -both internal and across the border; and the latter could be documented or undocumented. A list of organisations, agencies, and others is provided without going into details of their activities.

Importance/influence Matrix

Making an 'Importance' versus 'Influence' Matrix helps map out partners and their relation to the issue at stake in the multi-stakeholder partnerships. It generates insights into the importance and influence of each stakeholder. With this information, it becomes possible to develop a specific approach and strategy for the identified stakeholders.

Importance is the priority given to satisfying the needs and interests of each partner. Whereas influence is the power, a partner has to facilitate or impede the achievement of an activity's objective.

The stakeholder analysis (identifying influential and interested stakeholders and their respective level of motivation to participate) started in the preparation phase of the project when we contacted a selection of the immediately obvious partners. They gave hints at additional stakeholders to be included in a snowballing approach.

The only information available on websites was consulted for the desk research, which formed the basis for this report. In addition, this mapping only considers partners that specifically address cross-border issues. Finally, this mapping relies on the accuracy of publicly reported information. Facts and figures cited in this report are based on data reported by partners. The factual accuracy could not be validated. Ideally, we would have liked to share the information sheet with the partners and interview them. The response rate from partners was poor; they needed more time.

Engaging with Partners

High interest, low influence

Keep this group updated, informed, and supportive of cross border control of priority communicable diseases. Regularly share research, successes and challenges in policy development, ongoing salt reduction work, and other relevant updates via newsletters, phone calls, webinars, and informal networking events.

High interest, high influence

This is the key group and in the best place to offer advice on achieving impact. Consult the group for strategic advice, share draft proposals for comment and arrange formal meetings to keep them informed of progress with policy development.

High influence, low interest

To increase interest in cross border control of priority communicable diseases, and therefore their support, aim to form partnerships and relationships with this group. Write formal letters to key representatives, attempt to arrange introductory meetings and arrange interactive workshops to explain the need for cross border control of priority communicable diseases and work collaboratively.

Low influence, low interest

It is important to monitor this group but less necessary to engage with them.

Classification of stakeholders according to end note influence and interest, with resulting activation forms and strategies¹⁷⁰.

MALARIA

Among the partners who have a stake in malaria control and who have been working either singly or as part of various consortiums, there is a list of the important ones that will continue to play an important role in the region

1. Asian Development Bank
2. Asia Pacific Leaders Malaria Alliances
3. Asia Pacific Malaria Elimination Network
4. Association of South-East Asia Nations
5. Australian Agency for International Development
6. Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation
7. Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation
8. Bangladesh Rural Advancement Committee
9. Clinton Health Access Initiative
10. Global Fund
11. International Organization for Migration
12. Mekong Basin Disease Surveillance
13. Mekong Malaria Elimination Programme
14. Program for Appropriate Technology in Health
15. Population Services International
16. President's Malaria Initiative
17. Roll Back Malaria
18. South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation
19. Save the Children Federation
20. Southeast Asia Regional Coordination Mechanism Forum

21. United Nations Development Programme
22. United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
23. United Nations Children’s Fund
24. United Nations Office for Project Services
25. US Agency for International Development
26. World Bank

Details of Partners in Malaria

1. Asian Development Bank	
About	The Asian Development Bank is a regional development bank headquartered in Manila, Philippines. Maintains 31 field offices around the world to promote social and economic development in Asia
Focus	Assists its members, and partners, by providing loans, technical assistance, grants, and equity investments to promote social and economic development.
Geographic Regions active in	Malaria work in Greater Mekong Subregion (GMS)
Activities	Advocates for a collaborative approach to malaria elimination that goes beyond the health sector and national governments to draw in the private sector, non-government agencies, and the donor community across multiple domains, with a focus on health systems strengthening, rather than on a single disease.
Partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government of Australia (Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade) • Government of Canada (Department of Foreign Affairs, Trade and Development), and • Government of the United Kingdom (Foreign Commonwealth and Development Office).
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	<p>Yes</p> <p>It set up a Regional Malaria, and Other Communicable Disease Threats Trust Fund (RMTF) was set up in December 2013. Its remit was to support multi-country, cross-border and multisector responses to urgent malaria and other communicable disease issues, with a focus on the countries of the Greater Mekong Subregion (GMS). In 2015 the fund moved from supporting the control of malaria to eliminating the disease as a public health threat. This shift was in response to growing resistance to artemisinin-based combination therapy, which was emerging in four GMS countries: Cambodia, Myanmar, Thailand and Vietnam.</p>
Potential contribution	Yes
Web	https://www.adb.org/
Type	Bank
Primary role	Financing
Secondary role	Advocacy

2. Asia Pacific Leaders Malaria Alliance (APLMA)	
About	It is a high-level initiative for collective action to eliminate malaria across Asia and the Pacific by 2030. It is a network composed of leaders of countries that are pursuing malaria elimination, facilitating policy leadership and access to essential elimination resources and commodities.
Focus	It translates evidence to advocacy for policy change at the highest levels of government and supports leadership collaboration across the region. It also helps mobilize political, financial, and technical support tailored to the specific malaria conditions each country in the region faces.
Geographic Regions active in	Asia Pacific region (22 countries)
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empowers tangible elimination progress across the region with a heavy focus on high malaria burden countries. • Supports and provides governments and political leaders access to regional and national insights, as well as visibility on the game-changing approaches and tools they need to end malaria <p>APLMA helps mobilise political, financial, and technical support tailored to the specific malaria conditions each country in our region faces.</p>
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes Organises East Asia Summits. Convenes senior officials beyond health, monitoring and reporting on progress and bottlenecks and facilitating cross-border collaboration, to devise and execute strategic solutions for the region. Upholding political commitment is imperative across all sectors of society, from Heads of State, Government Ministries, international bodies and multilateral institutions to corporate leaders, academia, civil society, thought leaders and influencers.
Potential contribution	Yes
Web	https://www.aplma.org/
Type	a non-profit entity
Primary role	Advocacy
Secondary role	Convenor

3. Asia Pacific Malaria Elimination Network (APMEN)	
About	The network brings together around 20 Asia-Pacific national malaria programs and 50 partner institutions (academic, non-profit, and private sector organizations) committed to realising malaria elimination in the region and facilitates increased collaboration around advocacy, capacity building, information sharing and evidence generation. A platform to bring the network together and facilitate cooperation, collaboration and partnership to reach the regional malaria elimination goal.
Focus	Identifying and addressing programmatic needs and supporting national malaria programs, and facilitating technical exchange through its three Working Groups on Surveillance & Response, Vector Control and Vivax. Identifying and addressing programmatic needs and supporting national malaria programs and facilitating technical exchange through its three Working Groups on Surveillance & Response, Vector Control and Vivax.
Geographic Regions active in	21 Asia Pacific countries

Activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To coordinate and advocate for capacity strengthening at the national and regional levels 2. Identify knowledge gaps and 3. facilitate operational research on questions directly related to malaria control and elimination
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	<p>Yes</p> <p>The Asia Pacific Malaria Elimination Network (APMEN) and the Asia Pacific Leaders Malaria Alliance work in an integrated manner to further the elimination goal in the region, with APLMA facilitating policy leadership and access to essential elimination resources and commodities and APMEN identifying and addressing programmatic needs and supporting national malaria programs.</p>
Potential contribution	Yes
Partners	National Malaria Programmes from 21 countries and 50 Partner Institutions.
Web	https://apmen.org/
Type	Not-for-profit
Primary role	Convenor
Secondary role	Advocacy

4. Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN)	
About	Association of Southeast Asian Nations is an economic union comprising ten member states in South East Asia. .
Focus	ASEAN's primary objective was to accelerate economic growth and, through that, social progress and cultural development. A secondary objective was to promote regional peace and stability based on the rule of law and the principle of the United Nations charter.
Active in	Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Indonesia, Lao PDR, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand and Viet Nam.
Activities	Promote intergovernmental cooperation and facilitate economic, political, security, military, educational and socio-cultural integration between its members and other countries in Asia. India became a sectoral dialogue partner of ASEAN in 1992 and became its full dialogue partner during the fifth ASEAN Summit in Bangkok in 1995. India also became a member of the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF) in 1996. India and ASEAN have been holding summit-level meetings on an annual basis since 2002. ASEAN-India Flagship Programme on Science & Technology for Combating Malaria: A Public Health Challenge was also organized.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes ASEAN health ministers have identified malaria and resistance to the antimalarial drug artemisinin as priority issues. Organises Summit Meetings of the head of member States.
Potential contribution	Maybe
Web	https://asean.org/
Type	
Primary role	Economic Forum

5. Australian Agency for International Development (AUSAID)	
About	AUSAID (Australian Agency for International Development) is the Australian Government's overseas aid programme providing grant assistance to NGOs.
Focus	Reducing poverty and achieving sustainable development,
Active in	Including South and East Asia, the Pacific, Africa and the Middle East.
Activities	Australia's foreign policy recognizes the importance of malaria control and elimination to enhance human development and ensure regional stability and economic prosperity. Since 2013, Australia has supported the Asia Pacific Leaders Malaria Alliance (APLMA) to unite regional leaders and advocate for malaria elimination across the Asia-Pacific by 2030
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes
Potential contribution	Possibly yes
Web	https://www.dfat.gov.au/
Type	Government agency
Primary role	Donor

6. Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation (BIMSTEC)	
About	BIMSTEC is an inter-regional grouping that seeks to foster regional and economic cooperation among nations in the littoral and adjacent areas of the Bay of Bengal - India, Thailand, Myanmar, Nepal, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka and Bhutan. It has emerged as the ‘preferred platform’ for regional cooperation in South Asia.
Focus	It is an economic bloc and aims to accelerate economic growth and social progress among members across multiple sectors - trade, technology, energy, transport, tourism and fisheries, agriculture, public health, poverty alleviation, counter-terrorism, environment, culture, people to people contact and climate change.
Mechanism	<p>BIMSTEC is a four-tiered organisation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Summit comprising the Heads of State or Government of the Member States • The Ministerial Meeting comprising the Ministers dealing with foreign relations of the Member States • The Senior Officials’ Meeting consisting of the Foreign Secretaries/ Secretaries/ appropriate Senior officials nominated by the BIMSTEC Member States • The BIMSTEC Permanent Working Committee (BPCW) comprises senior officials of the respective National Focal Points. <p>BIMSTEC Summit Declarations have often cited the need to collaborate for control of HIV and AIDS, malaria, TB.</p>
Activities	Includes public health
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Not yet Possible. The Annual Summit can be used as an advocacy platform for cross-border malaria.
Potential contribution	Perhaps yes
Web	https://bimstec.org/
Type	Inter-regional

7. Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation	
About	Not for profit, American private philanthropy was founded in 2000. The Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (Gates) is a funding organisation based in Seattle, Washington, USA. Guided by the belief that every life has equal value, this innovative group works to help all people lead healthy, productive lives. In particular, this foundation focuses on improving people's health and on giving them the chance to lift themselves out of hunger and extreme poverty. The valuable resources shared help empower people for success. 2000.
Focus	By working and expanding access to existing tools, using data to better track and target the disease, advancing research on potentially transformative innovations, and advocating for others to join in the effort to end malaria.
Geographic Regions active in	Global reach
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce the burden of malaria by expanding the use of effective existing tools, including preventive medication and case management, and improving disease surveillance and data for decision-making high-burden settings • Accelerate progress toward eradication by investing in next-generation surveillance systems, elimination in regions where drug-resistant malaria has emerged, and research and development efforts • Get ahead of resistance by eliminating falciparum malaria-the type that causes the most severe cases and deaths-in the Greater Mekong Subregion, developing a robust pipeline of new treatments, and analyzing disease and mosquito genetic data to quickly respond to threats.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes It funds many organizations, including The Global Fund, which provide funds for cross-border malaria. Has an office in India and engages in malaria elimination.
Potential contribution	Yes
Contact person	Philip Welkhoff is the director of Malaria
Web	https://www.gatesfoundation.org/
Type	Philanthropy
Primary role	Funding agency
Secondary role	Advocacy

8. Bangladesh Rural Advancement Committee (BRAC)	
About	BRAC is an international development organisation based in Bangladesh.
Focus	Public health (TB and Malaria) in addition to economic development, education, disaster relief
Geographic Regions active in	Bangladesh, Myanmar, Nepal, Afghanistan, Philippines, Sierra Leon, South Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda. In Bangladesh, work is in the 13 high endemic districts.
Activities	Strengthen and expand national malaria control activities to all endemic districts working directly and through other NGOs. directly implementing malaria control activities in all sub-districts of Chittagong hill tracts (border area)
Partners	
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes Has collaborated with the Government of Bangladesh for cross-border malaria control in the Bangladesh-India border in Meghalaya, India, funded by the Global Fund.
Potential contribution	Yes
Web	http://www.brac.net/
Type	Non-profit
Primary role	Technical support (implementing agency)

9. Clinton Health Access Initiative (CHAI)	
About	is a global health organization
Focus	To save lives and reduce the burden of disease in low- and middle-income countries around the world. Strengthen the government and private sector to create and sustain high-quality health systems in countries
Active in	Also active in South Asia – India and Myanmar
Activities	Including expanding access to care and treatment for malaria, TB and HIV. Focus includes border malaria and TB treatment for migrants.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes
Potential contribution	May be
Web	https://www.clintonhealthaccess.org/about-us/
Type	NGO
Primary role	Implementation
Secondary role	Advocacy

10. The Global Fund (GFATM)	
About	The Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria is an international financing and partnership organisation
Focus	aims to attract, leverage and invest additional resources to end the epidemics of HIV/AIDS, TB and Malaria, and strengthen health systems
Geographic Regions active in	Global
Activities	Provides funds
Partners	Include multilateral organizations like WHO, UNAIDS, World Bank, UNICEF UNDP, bilateral partners like USAID, DFID and AUSAID, as well as many smaller NGOs.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes Supports projects on cross-border collaboration for malaria elimination. Its South East Asia Regional Coordination Mechanism Forum is the South East Asia (SEA) Constituency. Its focus is on cross-border areas of the member countries for supporting the elimination
Potential contribution	Yes
Web	https://www.theglobalfund.org/en/
Type	Funding agency
Primary role	Financing
Secondary role	Advocacy

11. International Organization for Migration (IOM)	
About	The IOM is an inter-governmental organization that provides services and advice concerning migration to governments and migrants, including internally displaced persons, refugees, and migrant workers.
Focus	<p>It is the leading intergovernmental organization in the field of migration and works closely with governments and other partners. It is the leading intergovernmental organization in the field of migration and works closely with governments and other partners.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to help ensure the orderly and humane management of migration, • to promote international cooperation on migration issues, to promote international cooperation on migration issues, • to assist in the search for practical solutions to migration problems • to provide humanitarian assistance to migrants in need, including refugees and internally displaced people. <p>Promote humane and orderly migration by providing services and advice to governments and migrants. Has a focus on malaria amongst migrants.</p>
Geographic areas active in	Globally, GMS (Cambodia, Lao Peoples Democratic Republic, Myanmar, Thailand and Viet Nam); Myanmar, and Thailand in the region.
Activities related to migrant populations	IOM activities include: migration & development, regulating migration, migration health, claims programs, facilitating migration, general programs; movement emergency and post-migration management; migration, climate change & environmental degradation.
Partners	IOM and WHO have collaborated to provide up-to-date recommendations on technical implementation and policy implications of addressing malaria for migrants and mobile populations.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes Supports cross-border malaria activities
Potential contribution	Yes
Web	https://www.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd1486/files/jahia/jsp/index.jsp
Type	UN Agency
Primary role	Guidance and support
Secondary role	Implementation support

12. Mekong Basin Disease Surveillance Foundation	
About	Self-organised and sub-regional cooperation spearheaded by health ministries from member countries to collaborate on infectious disease surveillance and control. Self-organised and sub-regional co-operation spearheaded by health ministries from member countries to collaborate on infectious disease surveillance and control.
Focus	Reduce morbidity and mortality caused by outbreak prone diseases in the sub-region through <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve cross-border infectious disease outbreak investigation and response by sharing surveillance data and best practices in disease recognition and reporting and by jointly responding to outbreaks; 2. Develop expertise in epidemiological surveillance across the countries; and 3. Enhance communication between the countries.
Geographic Regions active in	The Mekong Basin Disease Surveillance Foundation or MBDS comprises six countries: Cambodia, China (Yunnan and Guangxi Provinces), Laos, Myanmar, Thailand and Vietnam
Activities	Disease surveillance and information exchange, build local capacity, share information and cooperate in outbreak response. It piloted cross-border cooperation, with the exchange of regular disease information on a daily, weekly, monthly or quarterly basis, cross-border meetings, monitoring and evaluation, multisector engagement (especially immigration, local authorities), cross-border epidemiologic case history, cross-border medical care and clinical follow-up to nearby provincial areas. It has used 2-way ICT-based communications between local, provincial and central levels in routine surveillance reporting and outbreak investigation (examples include equipment and protocols for communications through the internet, cell phone SMS messaging, satellite telephones, telephone hotline, email).
Partners	Include: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. Rockefeller Foundation ii. Nuclear Threat Initiative iii. RAND iv. WHO v. USAID vi. ADB vii. ASEAN
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes South Asian countries could learn from their experience of setting up the system for data sharing for malaria in GMS.
Potential contribution	Yes
Web	https://mbdsnet.org/
Type	NGO
Primary role	Technical support
Secondary role	Advocacy

13. Mekong Malaria Elimination Programme	
About	It is a WHO initiative that supports malaria elimination across the six countries of the Greater Mekong subregion (GMS), Located in Phnom Penh, Cambodia
Focus	The key area of work includes partnership coordination, advocacy and communication, as well as leading technical support on cross-country projects, regional/country surveillance, national malaria elimination intensification plans, and aggressive approaches.
Geographic Regions active in	Cambodia, China (Yunnan Province), the Lao People’s Democratic Republic, Myanmar, Thailand and Vietnam.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provide technical support on malaria elimination; • support the development of national malaria elimination intensification plans and focalized aggressive approaches; • advocate on the prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of malaria; • implement cross-border initiatives to accelerate elimination; • monitor drug efficacy and strengthen malaria surveillance systems; and • coordinate and publish epidemiological data on malaria elimination across the six countries through the Malaria Elimination Database. <p>The Malaria Elimination Database, a cornerstone of the MME Programme, is a regional platform that collects monthly malaria data at district and lower levels. It allows GMS countries to strengthen surveillance, enhance monitoring and evaluation, perform analyses on malaria distribution and trends, and share data through quarterly epidemiological summaries and annual bulletins.</p>
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes Could be a partner for learning on cross-border issues.
Potential contribution	Yes
Primary role	Technical support
Secondary role	Advocacy

14. Programme for Appropriate Technology for Health (PATH)	
About	An international, non-profit global health organization
Focus	Across five platforms—vaccines, drugs, diagnostics, devices, and system and service innovations—to develop and deploy innovations, implement health solutions and strengthen health systems to save lives and improve health outcomes.
Active in	More than 70 + countries; PATH in South Asia works in India, Bangladesh, Myanmar, Nepal, Sri Lanka
Activities	PATH Center for Malaria Elimination and Control is accelerating progress against malaria through innovative tools, approaches, and partnerships. Its projects are currently supported by grants from numerous funders, including the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, The Global Fund to Fight AIDS, Tuberculosis and Malaria, United States Agency for International Development, Gavi, the Vaccine Alliance and Unitaaid, among others. PATH's capacities in malaria include operations research, health systems strengthening, Information system strengthening, Financing and resource mobilization, monitoring and evaluation, Applied behaviour change communication, Communications and marketingMonitoring and evaluation, Applied behavior change communication, Communications and marketing
Partners	BP Koirala Institute of Health Sciences, Dharan, Nepal ICDDR, B, Dhaka, Bangladesh
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Maybe. Project-based.
Potential contribution	Minimal at the moment
Contact person	Neeraj Jain
Email	india@path.org (India office) or njain@path.org
Web	https://www.path.org/india/
Type	International NGO
Primary role	Technical support, including program implementation
Secondary role	Research and Development

15. Population Services International (PSI) 15.Population Services International (PSI)	
About	PSI works to improve the availability, affordability and use of effective malaria prevention, diagnosis and treatment in addition to sexual and reproductive health, water and sanitation, malaria, HIV/TB, non-communicable diseases. Provides products, clinical services and behavioural change communications for the health of people in high-need populations. In malaria runs the Greater Mekong Subregion Elimination of Malaria through Surveillance (GEMS+). The Greater Mekong Subregion Elimination of Malaria through Surveillance (GEMS+).
Focus	The GEMS+ project supports national malaria programs in Cambodia, Lao PDR, Myanmar, and Vietnam to integrate the private sector into national malaria elimination strategies, surveillance systems, planning, and management structures.
Geographic Regions active in	Cambodia, Lao PDR, Myanmar, and Vietnam
Activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. training, supervising, monitoring, and motivating providers; 2. routine support to providers to test, treat, and report malaria cases; 3. ensuring availability of sub-national staff (both internally and in government) to support the collection of paper forms, supervise, and monitor quality; 4. provider assessment through regular data analysis.
Partners	
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	<p>Yes</p> <p>Helps in cross-border malaria activities on the Thailand-Myanmar border. PSI co-developed the Malaria Case Surveillance (MCS) app to allow providers to easily report cases as soon as they find them in an easy-to-use interface.</p> <p>Utilising this real-time data collection from providers in the field, PSI is able to make informed decisions. . PSI co-developed the Malaria Case Surveillance (MCS) app to allow providers to easily report cases as soon as they find them in an easy-to-use interface. Utilising this real-time data collection from providers in the field, PSI is able to make informed decisions.</p> <p>PSI uses the District Health Network Information System (DHIS2) to house its electronic surveillance system, which allows for widespread access to data and user-friendly tools to visualize data in ways that facilitates decision making.</p>
Potential contribution	Yes
Web	https://www.psi.org/about/
Type	Non-for-profit
Primary role	Technical support
Secondary role	Advocacy

16. US President's Malaria Initiative	
About	The US President's Malaria Initiative (PMI),
Focus	Implements malaria surveillance, research, commodity distribution and prevention activities. To prevent the spread of drug-resistant malaria, usually found in cross-border regions.
Geographic Regions active in	Sub-Saharan Africa and the Greater Mekong Subregion in Asia
Activities	<p>partners with countries</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. to provide people with mosquito nets, ensure homes are sprayed with insecticides and distribute preventive medicines for children and pregnant women. 2. Invests in research and new tools to combat malaria, and monitor and evaluate the progress of PMI-supported programs. 3. Trains the health workers that provide the service, which contributes to building resilient health systems. trains the health workers that provide the service which contributes to building resilient health systems.
Partners	<p>Include</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • USAID, • Centres for Disease Control and Prevention, Atlanta, • Global Fund ATM, • World Bank, • Roll Back Malaria, • UNICEF
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	<p>Yes</p> <p>Supported Cross border collaboration in the Greater Mekong Subregion (GMS) to combat Drug-Resistant Malaria and provided assistance for the development of coordinated work plans.</p> <p>PMI and Global Fund have supported Senegal-Gambia's cooperative effort to synchronize nationwide anti-malaria activities on both sides of the high transmission cross-border region.</p>
Potential contribution	Yes
Web	https://www.pmi.gov/
Type	Government agency
Primary role	Implementing agency
Secondary role	Technical support

17. Roll Back Malaria (RBM)	
About	The RBM Partnership is the global platform for coordinated action against malaria. It mobilises for action and resources and forges consensus among partners. WHO, the World Bank, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) created the Roll Back Malaria.
Focus	Provides high quality, practical, consistent and relevant technical advice is made available through networks of experts based in research, academic, and disease control institutions, particularly those in endemic countries. It also supports the research and development of new products and tools to control malaria.
Geographic Regions active in	Active in all malaria-endemic countries, through its sub-regional coordinators' networks and its partners, notably national malaria control and elimination programmes
Activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. convene partners focused on this common cause; 2. coordinate partners to maximize alignment, facilitate cooperation and ensure that common challenges are addressed cooperatively; 3. mobilise resources by identifying resource requirements and creating humanitarian and business cases to support the mobilization of resources; by identifying resource requirements and creating humanitarian and business cases to support the mobilisation of resources; 4. facilitate communication, identify and address opportunities and challenges by engaging partners, sharing experience and best practices; and 5. provide mission-critical support to malaria-affected countries and regions, supporting the critical enablers required to enhance political will and providing targeted support where it is needed most., supporting the critical enablers required to enhance political will and providing targeted support where it is needed most.
Partners	The World Health Organization, the World Bank, UNICEF and UNDP
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes Supports activities on border malaria RBM Partnership's strategy for 2018-2020 identifies regional collaboration as key to defeating malaria. Several sub-regions across the African continent have stepped up their cross-border efforts towards malaria elimination, a move mirrored by the six countries of the Greater Mekong Subregion and seven Central American countries.
Potential contribution	Yes
Web	https://endmalaria.org/
Type	
Primary role	Technical advice
Secondary role	Research and Development

18. South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC)	
About	The South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation is the regional intergovernmental organisation and geopolitical union of states in South Asia.
Focus	SAARC aims to promote economic growth, social progress and cultural development within the South Asia region.
Active in	Eight Member States: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan and Sri Lanka.
Activities	SAARC Tuberculosis and HIV/AIDS Centre (STAC) is one of the Regional Centres of SAARC working for the prevention and control of TB and HIV/AIDS. There is also a SAARC Centre for Malaria. Has organized meetings on cross-border issues in TB and HIV control Programmes. The SAARC Charter envisages acceleration of social progress through active and others) with particular attention to Malaria.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes The 18th SAARC Summit held in Kathmandu in 2014 concluded with the adoption of the SAARC Declaration. The Declaration recognises labour migration as an issue in need of collective action. Article 21 states that SAARC countries agree to collaborate to ensure the protection of migrant workers. The 18th SAARC Summit held in Kathmandu in 2014 concluded with the adoption of the SAARC Declaration. The Declaration recognizes labour migration as an issue in need of collective action. Article 21 states that SAARC countries agree to collaborate to ensure the protection of migrant workers.
Potential contribution	It may be from a political level.
Web	https://www.saarc-sec.org/
Type	Inter-governmental organization

19. Save the Children Federation, Inc	
About	Save the Children Federation, Inc., commonly known as Save the Children USA, is a non-profit organization working to improve the lives of children in the United States and around the world.
Focus	Health, education, protection, Policy and Advocacy and Emergency Relief
Active in	Has presence in South East Asia
Activities	Has been the principal recipient of Global Fund in malaria project in Nepal and Myanmar
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes Could be an implementing partner
Potential contribution	Perhaps yes
Web	https://www.savethechildren.org/
Type	NGO
Primary role	Implementation
Secondary role	Advocacy

20. South East Asia Regional Coordination Mechanism Forum (SRCMF)	
About	South-East Asia Regional Coordination Mechanism Forum is the South East Asia (SEA) Constituency of the Global Fund, one among the ten constituencies that form the Implementer Group of the Board of the Global Fund. SRCMF has been launched by the 11 member countries of the GF SEA Constituency.
Focus	SRCMF's focus is on Cross-border areas of the member countries for supporting the elimination of malaria, tuberculosis and HIV/AIDS in Cross-border areas by 2030.
Geographic Regions active in	SEA Region consists of 11 member states (Bangladesh, Bhutan, Democratic People's Republic of Korea, India, Indonesia, The Maldives, Myanmar, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Thailand, and Timor-Leste.)
Activities	Coordinating National Program implementation, especially in the subnational and local levels, supporting M&E, resource mobilization, advocacy, fostering partnership and sustainability of GF programs to accelerate and achieve the 2030 goals
Partners	WHO, RBM, UNOPS, GFATM, APLMA/APMEN CDC, Path, WHP, RTI
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes
Potential contribution	Yes
Contact person	Dr Jigmi Singay
Email	Jigmi2118@gmail.com
Web	https://www.theglobalfund.org/en/ https://www.theglobalfund.org/en/board/constituencies/
Type	NGO under Company Act 2013 Section 18 in India
Primary role	Coordination for Cross-border disease elimination Program activities
Secondary role	Besides Coordination and M&E, Resource mobilization, advocacy, fostering partnership and sustainability of GF programs

21. United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)	
About	The United Nations Development Programme is a United Nations organization tasked with helping countries eliminate poverty and achieve sustainable economic growth and human development. The United Nations Development Programme is a United Nations organization tasked with helping countries eliminate poverty and achieve sustainable economic growth and human development.
Focus	helping to eradicate poverty, reduce inequalities and exclusion, and build resilience so countries can sustain progress.
Active in	In a collaboration between the Roll Back Malaria Partnership, the UNDP has launched the Multisectoral Action Framework for Malaria. It makes a clear case for re-structuring the way countries address malaria. It presents a menu of concrete, implementable processes and actions to transform malaria responses—from being a concern of the health sector only towards a coordinated multi-pronged effort that harnesses expertise across a range of sectors and institutions
Activities related to migrant populations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing comprehensive national policy and institutional frameworks for migration. • Managing migration for long-term positive development impacts at the sub-national and local levels. • Resilience based development solutions for migration and displacement in times of crisis, conflict and disaster
Partners	UNDP is requested to serve as the Global Fund’s interim Principal Recipient (PR) in countries facing a wide variety of special challenges. UNDP is requested to serve as the Global Fund’s interim Principal Recipient (PR) in countries facing a wide variety of special challenges.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes. UNDP partners with the Global Fund to support and strengthen national responses to malaria, among others, in supporting countries to implement large-scale health programmes, including reaching some of the most hard-to-reach populations and strengthening institutions to deliver essential services in challenging and high-risk country contexts. .
Potential contribution	May be
Web	https://www.undp.org/
Type	UN Agency
Primary role	Procurement agency

22. United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR)	
About	Mandated to aid and protect refugees, forcibly displaced communities, and stateless people, and to assist in their voluntary repatriation, local integration or resettlement to a third country.
Focus	Engage with migration issues that affect refugees and other persons under its mandate, including asylum seekers, internally displaced people and stateless people .
Active in	The UNHCR Malaria prevention and control activities are directed by guiding principles of effective malaria control in complex emergency settings, which applies equally to refugee situations, as for other situations of displacement.
Activities related to migrant populations	UNHCR's public health programming supports refugees so that they can be healthy and works with governments to provide emergency health services, improve local health services and include refugees in national health systems and plans. UNHCR has also been a sub-recipient of GFATM grants for malaria.
Partners	World Food Programme (WFP), the UN Children's Fund (UNICEF), the World Health Organization (WHO), the UN Development Programme (UNDP), the Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) and the Joint UN Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS).World Food Programme (WFP), the UN Children's Fund (UNICEF), the World Health Organization (WHO), the UN Development Programme (UNDP), the Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) and the Joint UN Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS).
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Perhaps yes, in border areas where refugees are an issue, like India-Bangladesh and India-Myanmar. UNHCR advocates for the inclusion of refugees in National Malaria Control Plans, Global Fund and other donor proposals.
Potential contribution	Maybe.
Web	https://www.unhcr.org/
Type	UN Agency
Primary role	Provide emergency
Secondary role	

23. United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF)	
About	United Nations Children’s Fund is a United Nations agency responsible for providing humanitarian and developmental aid to children worldwide.
Focus	to save children’s lives, defend their rights, and help them fulfil their potential from early childhood through adolescence.
Active in	The primary focus of UNICEF’s malaria efforts is to reduce the number of children’s lives lost to the disease to zero. UNICEF partners closely with WHO and others to achieve a world free of malaria, as set out in the Global Technical Strategy for Malaria 2016-2030.
Activities related to migrant populations	To provide children of migrants with access to health services, education, shelter, nutrition, water and sanitation. To help protect the rights of migrants and displaced children.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Potential partner for malaria control in children in border districts. It partners WHO in seasonal malaria chemoprevention, which has been used effectively in recent years to prevent mortality among children under the age of five years. UNICEF is a key partner in the” High burden to high impact”, a country-led response – catalysed by WHO and the RBM Partnership – to reignite the pace of progress in the global fight malaria against malaria.
Potential contribution	Maybe.
Web	https://www.unicef.org/
Type	UN agency

24. United Nations Office for Project Services (UNOPS)	
About	The United Nations Office for Project Services is an operational arm of the United Nations, dedicated to implementing projects for the United Nations System, international financial institutions, governments and other partners around the world.
Focus	UNOPS provides infrastructure, procurement and project management services for a sustainable world
Active in	Has presence in South East Asia
Activities	UNOPS is the principal recipient of a \$ 100 million grant from the Global Fund to manage the Regional Artemisinin- Resistance Initiative in five countries in GMS. UNOPS is the legal and administrative host for RBM Partnership to End.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	<p>Yes</p> <p>The Regional Artemisinin-resistance Initiative 2 Elimination (RAI2E) programme is a \$243 million regional grant to accelerate the elimination of Plasmodium falciparum malaria in the Greater Mekong Subregion between 2018 and 2020. RAI2E supports increased malaria service coverage for remote populations in border areas and other at-risk populations, as well as case management through health volunteers and strengthening of national surveillance systems.</p> <p>UNOPS is responsible for managing the funds of the project and providing quality assurance as well as monitoring and evaluation. The programme is being implemented by 34 partners across the region and is funded by the Global Fund to Fight AIDS, tuberculosis and malaria.</p>
Potential contribution	Yes
Web	https://www.unops.org/about
Type	UN Agency
Primary role	Procurement
Secondary role	Project Management, Financial Management

25. US Agency for International Development (USAID) (USAID)	
About	USAID leads international development and humanitarian efforts to save lives, reduce poverty, strengthen democratic governance and help people progress beyond assistance. It is an independent agency of the United States federal government that is primarily responsible for administering civilian foreign aid and development assistance.
Focus	USAID carries out US foreign policy by promoting broad-scale human progress at the same time it expands stable, free societies, create markets and trade partners for the United States and fosters goodwill abroad.
Active in	Has presence in Bangladesh, India, Myanmar and Nepal
Activities	USAID works closely with the governments of endemic malaria countries to strengthen their capacity to prevent and treat the disease. USAID leads the US President's Malaria Initiative (PMI) (PMI)
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes USAID focuses on the border areas where drug-resistant malaria has been detected, with support for activities like surveillance for drug resistance, case detection and reporting, drug quality monitoring, and commodity supply for malaria prevention services to remote and hard-to-reach communities.
Potential contribution	Yes, they could be a potential donor.
Web	https://www.usaid.gov/
Type	Government agency
Primary role	Funding
Secondary role	Technical advice

26. World Bank	
About	The World Bank is an international financial institution that provides loans and grants to the governments of low- and middle-income countries for the purpose of pursuing capital projects
Focus	Includes investing in countries in malaria control.
Active in	Malaria control is an important part of the World Bank's health portfolio.
Activities	The World Bank treats financing for malaria control as an integral part of the financing for essential health services in the context of universal health coverage. The Bank works with countries to ensure that essential health interventions (including malaria) are adequately planned, cost and budgeted for in national health sector plans in a sustainable manner. The World Bank is a founding member of the Roll Back Malaria Partnership, which serves as a global framework for implementing a coordinated response against malaria. Finances the procurement of personal protection measures.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes Supports Roll Back Malaria and funds cross border control of malaria
Potential contribution	Yes
Web	https://www.worldbank.org/en/home
Type	Financial institution
Primary role	Funding
Secondary role	Technical assistance

Malaria Partners Engagement

Note:

1. The circle marked 'Government' includes both Central and State/Provincial Governments as well as health and non-health.
2. Red circles also includes organizations where Head of Governments participate
3. The quadrant titled 'Collaborate' has circles in different sizes. The size indicates the importance; the larger the circle, the greater the importance.

KALA-AZAR

It has not been possible to determine which of the partners is engaged in cross-border control of Kala-Azar. A list of the partners working for Kala-azar elimination is provided, which is followed by some information about each one of them.

List of partners in Kala-azar

1. Accelerating the Sustainable Control and Elimination of Neglected Tropical Diseases (ASCEND)
2. Association of Southeast Asian Nations, (ASEAN)
3. B.P. Koirala Institute of Health Sciences (BPKIHS)
4. Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation (BIMSTEC)
5. Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF)
6. Cooperative for American Remittances to Europe (CARE, India)
7. Drugs for Neglected Diseases initiative (DNDi)
8. Foreign, Commonwealth Development Office, UK (FCDO formerly DfID)
9. Global Health Strategies (GHS)
10. Institute of Medical Sciences, (IMS)
11. Institute of Tropical Medicine (ITM)
12. International Centre for Diarrhoeal Disease Research, Bangladesh (ICDDRDB)
13. Japan International Co-operation Agency (JICA)
14. Kala-azar Medical Research Centre (KMRC),
15. KalaCore
16. Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine (LSTM)
17. London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (LSHTM)
18. Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF)
19. National Institute of Preventive and Social Medicine (NIPSM)
20. PATH ((formerly known as the Program for Appropriate Technology in Health)
21. Public health Foundation of India (PHFI)
22. Rajendra Memorial Research Institute (RMRI)
23. Setting the Post Elimination Agenda for Kala-azar in India (SPEAK-India)
24. South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC)
25. South East Asia Regional Coordination Mechanism Forum (SRCMF)
26. Wellcome Trust (WT)

1. Accelerating the Sustainable Control and Elimination of Neglected Tropical Diseases (Ascend)	
About	This is a consortium. The three-year programme aims to support national governments in sustainably tackling NTDs, with a focus on the control and elimination of five preventable NTDs
Focus	includes visceral leishmaniasis,
Active in	24 countries including Bangladesh and Nepal. Working with Governments for early diagnosis and treatment
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Elimination
Partners	The NTD Modelling consortium <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The London Centre for NTD Research • Imperial College London • The Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine • The KIT Royal Tropical Institute • The SCI Foundation
Period	Ends in June 2022
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Unlikely
Potential contribution	Unlikely

2. Association of Southeast Asian Nations, (ASEAN)	
About	Association of Southeast Asian Nations, is an economic union comprising 10 member states in South East Asia.
Focus	ASEAN's primary objective was to accelerate economic growth and through that social progress and cultural development. A secondary objective was to promote regional peace and stability based on the rule of law and the principle of United Nations charter.
Active in	Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Indonesia, Lao PDR, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand and Viet Nam.
Activities	promote intergovernmental cooperation and facilitates economic, political, security, military, educational and socio-cultural integration between its members and other countries in Asia. India became a sectoral dialogue partner of ASEAN in 1992. And became its full dialogue partner during the fifth ASEAN Summit in Bangkok in 1995. India also became a member of the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF) in 1996. India and ASEAN have been holding summit-level meetings on an annual basis since 2002. ASEAN-India Flagship Programme on Science & Technology for Combating Malaria: A Public Health Challenge was also organized.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes ASEAN health ministers have identified malaria and resistance to the antimalarial drug artemisinin as priority issues. Organizes Summit Meetings of head of member States.
Potential contribution	May be
Web	https://asean.org/
Type	
Primary role	Economic Forum

3. B.P. Koirala Institute of Health Sciences (BPKIHS)	
About	B.P. Koirala Institute of Health Sciences (BPKIHS), an autonomous Health Sciences University on Oct 28, 1998., Dhran, Nepal
Focus	work towards developing socially responsible and competent health workforce, providing health care and involving in innovative health research
Active in	Nepal
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Elimination
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Can provide technical support
Potential contribution	Perhaps yes
Email	bpkihs@bpkihs.edu
Web	http://www.bpkihs.edu/
Primary role	Academic
Secondary role	Research & Development

4. Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation (BIMSTEC)	
About	Headquartered in Dhaka, BIMSTEC came into being on 6 June 1997. It is an inter-regional grouping that seeks to foster regional and economic cooperation among nations in the littoral and adjacent areas of the Bay of Bengal.
Focus	It aims to accelerate economic growth and social progress among members across multiple sectors — trade, technology, energy, transport, tourism and fisheries, agriculture, public health, poverty alleviation, counter-terrorism, environment, culture, people to people contact and climate change.
Regions active in	nations in the littoral and adjacent areas of the Bay of Bengal
Activities / Whether active in cross-border Kala-azar control?	No, not yet.
Members / Partners	India, Thailand, Myanmar, Nepal, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka and Bhutan.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	All countries (except Sri Lanka and Thailand) of the South Asia region which share land borders with India are members.
Potential contribution	Could be a platform for enhancing political commitment for cross-border control of diseases.
Contact person	Tenzin Lekphell , Secretary General
Email	spa_osg@bimstec.org .
Web	www.bimstec.org
Type	Economic and political platform
Primary role	Advocacy
Secondary role	

5. Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation	
About	Not for profit, American private philanthropy founded 2000. The Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (Gates) is a funding organization based in Seattle, Washington USA. Guided by the belief that every life has equal value, this innovative group works to help all people lead healthy, productive lives. In particular, this foundation focuses on improving people's health and on giving them the chance to lift themselves out of hunger and extreme poverty. The valuable resources shared help empower people for success.
Focus	The three priority areas are to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discover new insights to fight serious diseases and other health problems affecting developing countries. • Develop effective and affordable vaccines, medicines, and other health tools. • Deliver proven health solutions to those who need them most. Spurring innovations, strengthening global cooperation, creating market incentives, generating high quality data and evidence
Active in	in India, Bangladesh and Nepal
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Kala azar elimination works with organizations around the world that are using innovative methods to improve healthcare. The main mission is to help ensure that advances in health are created and shared with those who need them most.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Perhaps yes
Potential contribution	Possible
Contact person	Katey Einterz Owen, Director NTDs, Seattle
Web	https://www.gatesfoundation.org/
Type	Philanthropy
Primary role	Funding agency
Secondary role	Advocacy

6. Cooperative for American Remittances to Europe (CARE)	
About	CARE (Cooperative for American Remittances to Europe): not-for-profit organisation. Founded in 1940s; CARE India in 2013. Member of the CARE International Confederation.
Focus	improve the access to quality healthcare services for the poor and marginalised communities.
Active in	Bihar, Jharkhand and West Bengal, India
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Elimination. Health systems strengthening, reproductive maternal new born, child and adolescent Health in Bihar, nutrition, and early identification and treatment of communicable diseases including Kala-azar. Has provided support in planning and implementation of the IRIS, KA MIS, case/ epidemiological surveillance and entomological surveillance.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Implementing agency
Potential contribution	Perhaps yes
Contact person	Dr Sridhar Srikantiah, Technical Director
Email	ssridhar@careindia.org
Web	https://www.careindia.org/
Type	National NGO
Primary role	Technical support
Secondary role	Advocacy

7. Drugs for Neglected Diseases initiative	
About	A not-for-profit, registered office in Geneva, Switzerland.
Focus	discover, develop, and deliver new treatments for neglected patients around the world that are affordable and patient-friendly
Regions active in	Has offices in Congo, Kenya, Japan, Brazil, USA, India, Malaysia, South Africa. Active in South Asia
Activities / Whether active in cross-border Kala-azar control?	Work on development of drugs for neglected tropical diseases including Kala-azar and other diseases affecting poor people where affordable drugs are not available
Partners	More than 200 partners in 40 countries: Academia, Industry, NGOs, Healthcare providers, Ministries of Health of countries. MSF an important partner
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Probably yes. Can help to improve access of drugs in border districts
Potential contribution	Advocacy
Contact person	Dr Kavita Singh, Director South Asia Office, New Delhi
Email	Ksingh@dndi.org
Web	https://dndi.org/about/who-we-are/
Type	International NGO
Primary role	R&D,
Secondary role	Advocacy for improving access

8. Foreign, Commonwealth Development Office, UK (formerly Department of International Development- DfID)	
About	UK's official department responsible for administering foreign aid
Focus	to meet the many challenges of tackling world poverty. Health is amongst the many areas it supports especially improving health systems and services
Active in	SEA region
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Elimination efforts. Provided funds to Consortia like KalaCORE, ASCEND, SPEAK, India
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	May fund
Potential contribution	Perhaps yes
Web	https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/foreign-commonwealth-development-office
Type	Funding agency
Primary role	Financing
Secondary role	Advocacy

9. Global Health Strategies	
About	<p>GHS is an international organization that works with donors and clients to ensure the development and delivery of health products, services, technologies and information.</p> <p>GHS' India office specializes in strategic communications, policy research and analysis and implementation projects on compelling public health issues in India and other countries.</p>
Focus	Wide range of issues including infectious diseases like Tuberculosis, Lymphatic Filariasis and Visceral Leishmaniasis; immunization, reproductive health and health innovation among others
Regions active in	US, Brazil, India, China, Europe, Africa
Activities / Whether active in cross-border Kala-azar control?	<p>GHS has worked for several years in close collaboration with the Government of India and other important stakeholders on critical neglected health issues. For example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Works to build a conducive environment for the elimination of Lymphatic Filariasis (LF) and Visceral Leishmaniasis (VL or Kala-azar) in India • Leverages communications and stakeholder engagement as mutually reinforcing tools to ensure appropriate attention at all levels by decision-makers and program managers towards elimination of LF & VL in India • Engages stakeholders (such as government leadership, technical and public health experts, popular figures, media and policymakers at the national level and across 14 states - including all 4 Kala-azar endemic states i.e. Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Jharkhand and West Bengal) on multiple platforms to strengthen the narrative on accelerating progress towards elimination of LF & VL in India.
Partners	Philanthropies, multinational organizations, NGOs, and governments
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes
Potential contribution	Advocacy and Communications
Contact person	Ms Anjali Nayyar, Executive Vice President
Email	anayyar@globalhealthstrategies.com
Web	https://globalhealthstrategies.com/
Type	For profit company
Primary role	Advocacy
Secondary role	Communications

10. Institute of Medical Sciences, BHU, Varanasi	
About	The Institute Of Medical Sciences is one of the six institutes of Banaras Hindu University in Varanasi, India
Focus	It is the medical school of the university.
Active in	Uttar Pradesh and Bihar
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Elimination Has conducted clinical trials on kala azar drugs.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Can provide technical support
Potential contribution	Minimal
Contact person	Dr Shyam Sundar
Email	drshyamsundar@hotmail.com
Web	https://new.bhu.ac.in/Site/UnitHomeTemplate/1_68_1134_Institute-of-Medical-Sciences-Faculty-of-Medicine
Type	Teaching and Research
Primary role	Research & Development
Secondary role	Technical support

11. Institute for Tropical Medicine	
About	Academic institute for training and research in tropical medicine and health policy, systems and service delivery in developing countries.
Focus	Fundamental, translational and applied scientific research; delivers advanced education and training; and provides medical, scientific and societal expert services. run major research programmes on the organisation, financing, management and integration of health care systems and disease control programmes, and carry out fundamental, applied and operational research on global (AIDS, malaria, TB) as well as “neglected” tropical diseases
Active in	Bangladesh, India, Nepal
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Elimination <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • evaluation of diagnostics (DAT, rK39, rK28) for visceral disease and markers for asymptomatic infections; • effectiveness of chemotherapy: resistance vs treatment failure; • effectiveness, cost and acceptability of new vector control methods; • elimination: strengthen surveillance systems
Partners	Work with B.P. Koirala Institute of Health Sciences and WHO,
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Can provide technical support
Potential contribution	Minimal
Contact person	Dr Epco Hasker
Email	ehasker@itg.be
Web	https://www.itg.be/E/about-us
Type	Education, training and research
Primary role	Research and Development
Secondary role	Technical support

12. International Centre for Diarrhoeal Disease Research, Bangladesh	
About	An international health research organisation located in Dhaka, Bangladesh. supported by about 55 donor countries and organisations,
Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dedicated to saving lives through research and treatment, • Addresses some of the most critical health concerns facing the world today, ranging from improving neonatal survival to HIV/AIDS. • Helps solve significant public health challenges facing the people of Bangladesh and beyond, especially the most vulnerable, through the generation of knowledge and its translation into policy and practice. • Health systems strengthening • Maternal/reproductive health • Newborn health • Child health
Active in	Bangladesh
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Elimination. The Centre contributes to the Programme mainly through research and capacity building. Areas of research encompass epidemiology, diagnostics, clinical trials, vector studies and nutrition. The extensive network of partners works in close collaboration with the national programme. Has been a principle recipient of Global Fund grant.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Can provide technical support
Potential contribution	Minimal
Contact person	Dr Dinesh Mondal.
Email	din63d@icddr.org
Web	http://www.icddr.org/
Type	Academic, research and training institute
Primary role	Research and Development
Secondary role	Technical support

13. Japan International Co-operation Agency (JICA)	
About	A governmental agency that delivers the bulk of Official Development Assistance for the government of Japan.
Focus	Assisting economic and social growth in developing countries, and the promotion of international cooperation.
Active in	Several countries including Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Nepal and Myanmar
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Elimination. Co-funded development of Kala-azar Research Centre at the SK Hospital in Mymensingh in collaboration with ICDDR,B
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Potential donor
Potential contribution	May be
Web	https://www.jica.go.jp/english/index.html
Type	Development partner
Primary role	Funding agency
Secondary role	Technical support

14. Kala Azar Medical Research Centre	
About	a unit of SITARAM MEMORIAL TRUST, founded in 1997
Focus	Works with National and State level initiatives towards Kala Azar prevention and elimination
Active in	State of Bihar
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Elimination. Clinical and public health aspects of kala azar
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Can provide technical support
Potential contribution	Minimal
Contact person	Dr Shyam Sundar
Email	drshyamsundar@hotmail.com
Web	http://www.kamrc.org/webpage.php?id=105%20&pid=164
Type	Indian NGO
Primary role	Research and Development
Secondary role	Technical support

15. KalaCORE Consortium	
About	The KalaCORE Consortium is a UK DfID funded initiative of UK£ 27 million
Focus	reducing the health and economic impact of VL, by supporting progress towards elimination in South Asia and by building stronger capacity for an effective VL response in East Africa.
Regions active in	1. South Asia: Bangladesh, India, Nepal 2. Africa: Ethiopia, South Sudan, Sudan
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Elimination 1. Support the programme in scaling up of Liposomal Amphotericin B 2. Strengthen cold chain and logistics 3. Capacity building at State and district level on strengthening surveillance 4. Epidemiological surveillance 5. Support development and dissemination of IEC/BCC material
Partners of Consortium	1. Drugs for Neglected Diseases <i>initiative</i> 2. London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine 3. Médecins Sans Frontières 4. Mott McDonald.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	No. Funding has ended.
Potential contribution	No
Contact person	Regional Coordinator for Asia: Dr Sakib Burza
Email	enquiries@kalacore.org ; sakibburza@gmail.com
Web	http://www.kalacore.org/
Type	Consortium /Partnership
Primary role	Technical support
Secondary role	Advocacy

16. Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine	
About	Research and teaching in tropical medicine
Focus	Leishmaniasis elimination
Active in	Border state of Bihar
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Elimination Kala azar elimination programme vector control in India,
Partners	RMRI, ICMR Institute, Bihar and CARE India.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Minimal. Strengths in vector biology and control
Potential contribution	Minimal
Contact person	Professor Janet Hemingway.
Email	Janet.Hemingway@LSTMed.ac.uk
Web	info@lstmed.ac.uk
Type	Educational institution
Primary role	Research and Development
Secondary role	Technical support

17. London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (LSHTM)	
About	Research-led postgraduate medical school with a mission to contribute to the improvement of global health through the pursuit of excellence in research, postgraduate teaching and advanced training in national and international public health and tropical medicine, and to undertake activities which influence policy and practice in these areas.
Focus	Research programmes are multidisciplinary and range from basic laboratory studies to applied public health research and from disease specific to those that deal with environmental or behavioural risk factors and health systems. Specialises in public health and tropical medicine.
Active in	Indian sub-Continent
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Elimination Support national eradication efforts and coordinate with control programmes.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Perhaps yes, would need to seek funding
Potential contribution	Perhaps yes, if funding is available
Contact person	Prof Mary Cameron
Email	mary.cameron@lshtm.ac.uk
Web	https://www.lshtm.ac.uk/
Type	Academic Institute
Primary role	Technical support
Secondary Role	Research and Development

18. Médecins Sans Frontières	
About	An international, independent, medical, humanitarian, non-governmental organisation that delivers emergency aid to people affected by armed conflict, epidemics, natural disasters, excluded from healthcare, and in countries affected by endemic diseases.
Focus	MSF's engagement with VL elimination in India (since 2007) and in Bangladesh (since 2010) as well as its core membership of KalaCORE (since September 2014). In India, MSF works in collaboration with the Rajendra Memorial Research Institute and the National Vector Borne Disease Control Programme.
Regions active in	MSF is active several countries including India, Bangladesh and Nepal
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	<p>Elimination</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. HIV-KA co-infection: identification, training and improving management of co-infected patients ii. Capacity building iii. Operational research <p>Due to the current low numbers of cases, MSF has closed its visceral leishmaniasis programmes in Bangladesh and India, but still plays a role in a technical advice and advocacy for the mobilisation of sufficient funds for the post-elimination phase.</p>
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Can help in clinical care of patients in border areas
Potential contribution	Perhaps Yes
Contact person	Dr Koert Ritmeijer coordinator of Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs) in MSF Operational Centre Amsterdam (MSF-OCA)
Email	info@amsterdam.msf.org , koert.ritmeijer@amsterdam.msf.org
Web	https://www.msf.org/
Type	International non-profit organization
Primary role	Technical support (treatment, clinical trials)
Secondary role	Advocacy

19. National Institute of Preventive and Social Medicine, Bangladesh	
About	Public health Institute, Dhaka,
Focus	Teaching and evaluation of programmes
Active in	Bangladesh
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	<p>Elimination</p> <p>Currently engaged in evaluation of visceral leishmaniasis elimination strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current research areas of focus include cost-effectiveness analysis of vector management strategies and monitoring and evaluation tools in Bangladesh • Training of health staff
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Can provide technical support
Potential contribution	Minimal
Email	
Web	https://www.nipsom.gov.bd/
Type	Governmental public health teaching and research institution
Primary role	Teaching and research
Secondary role	Technical support

20. PATH	
About	(formerly known as the Program for Appropriate Technology in Health) An international, non-profit global health organization
Focus	Across five platforms—vaccines, drugs, diagnostics, devices, and system and service innovations—to develop and deploy innovations, implement health solutions and strengthen health systems to save lives and improve health outcomes.
Active in	More than 70 + countries; PATH in South Asia works in India, Bangladesh, Myanmar, Nepal, Sri Lanka
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	<p>Kala-azar: Providing technical assistance for National and State vector born disease control program on Kala-azar elimination, supporting the Government of UP with Kala-azar elimination activities like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Surveillance through active cases detection • Ensuring early diagnosis and complete treatment of Kala-azar cases • Follow up of Visceral Leishmaniasis and Post-Kala-azar dermal leishmaniasis(PKDL) cases in the community through field level functionaries • Training and capacity building of health care providers in the state-district and block level for Kala-azar and LF • Supporting /Monitoring IRS (Indoor Residual Spray) for sandfly vector management • Conducting cross-border meeting between all four endemic states in India <p>PATH has an agreement with Gland pharma (manufacturer of Paromomycin (PMIM) Inj for Kala-azar treatment) for uninterrupted supply of PMIM to the country and development partners till July 2022.</p> <p>In past, PATH has also worked on activities like:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field testing of new innovative diagnostics like suitcase lab in four countries as a point of care diagnostic tool • Successful convening of international PKDL consortium meetings • Participation in studies and research activities supported by COR-NTD, TFGH, LSTMH, Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation • Safety- efficacy study of PMIM • Pharmacovigilance of Kala-azar drugs in Nepal and Bangladesh.
Partners	B P Koirala Institute of Health Sciences, Dharan, Nepal ICDDR,B , Dhaka , Bangladesh RMRI (Rajendra Memorial Research Institute , Patna , Bihar BHU (Banaras Hindu University) Medical University
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Can be useful as implementing partner. Would need funding.
Potential contribution	Perhaps yes
Contact person	Neeraj Jain
Email	india@path.org (India office) or njain@path.org
Web	https://www.path.org/india/
Type	International NGO
Primary role	Technical support including program implementation
Secondary role	Research and Development

21. Public Health Foundation of India	
About	An independent foundation, PHFI adopts a broad, integrative approach to public health, tailoring its endeavours to Indian conditions and bearing relevance to countries facing similar challenges and concerns.
Focus	Focuses on broad dimensions of public health that encompass promotive, preventive and therapeutic services
Regions active in	India
Activities / Whether active in cross-border Kala-azar control?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building a trained public health workforce through world-class, India relevant educational courses and training programmes • Supporting improvement of core public health programmes • Allied health workforce capacity building through technical assistance to state governments Yes
Partners	Government of India, State Governments, Civil Society Organisations/Members, Domestic and International Academic and Research Organisations, Multilateral and Bilateral Institutions and International Foundations
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes. Training of health workforce
Potential contribution	strengthening institutional and systems capacity in border districts in India
Contact person	Prof K Srinath Reddy, President
Email	Ksrinath.reddy@phfi.org
Web	https://phfi.org/
Type	not-for-profit, public private initiative
Primary role	Technical support
Secondary role	Advocacy

22. Rajendra Memorial Research Institute of Medical Sciences (RMRIMS), Patna	
About	Institute of the Indian Council of Medical Research, for Kala-azar research
Focus	research on clinical, basic and applied aspects of Kala-azar.
Active in	Bihar, India
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Elimination. operational research related to Kala-azar
Partners	World Health Organization (WHO/TDR), Institute for OneWorld Health, GlaxoSmithKline, DNDi, MSF,
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Can provide technical support. Would need funding
Potential contribution	Minimal
Web	https://www.rmrim.org.in/Introduction.html
Type	Research Institute
Primary role	Research & Development
Secondary role	Technical support

23. Setting the Post Elimination Agenda for Kala-azar in India (SPEAK-India)	
About	A VL Consortium
Focus	The aim was to identify and define the key questions, knowledge gaps and data needs that should be addressed for the VL elimination goal to be achieved and sustained, in the future.
Active in	India
Activities	operational research projects, surveillance, transmission, health systems and mathematical modelling
Whether related to elimination /cross border control	Elimination. Launched by the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) in partnership with the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MOHFW), Directorate of National Vector Borne Disease Control Programme (NVBDCP), London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (LSHTM) and the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF) 2016 in New Delhi.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	The funding is over. Can be useful if funding is made available
Potential contribution	Minimal
Web	https://speakindia.org.in/

24. South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC)	
About	The South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation is the regional intergovernmental organization and geopolitical union of states in South Asia.
Focus	SAARC aims to promote economic growth, social progress and cultural development within the South Asia region.
Active in	Eight Member States: Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan and Sri Lanka.
Activities	SAARC Tuberculosis and HIV/AIDS Centre (STAC) is one of the Regional Centres of SAARC working for prevention and control of TB and HIV/AIDS. There is also a SAARC Centre for Malaria Has organized meetings on cross-border issues in TB and HIV control Programmes. The SAARC Charter envisages acceleration of social progress through active ... and others) with particular attention to <i>Malaria</i> .
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes The 18th SAARC Summit held in Kathmandu in 2014 concluded with the adoption of the SAARC Declaration. The Declaration recognizes labour migration as an issue in need of collective action. Article 21 states that SAARC countries agree to collaborate to ensure the protection of migrant workers.
Potential contribution	May be from political level.
Web	https://www.saarc-sec.org/
Type	Inter-governmental organization

25. South East Asia Regional Coordination Mechanism Forum (SRCMF)	
About	South East Asia Regional Coordination Mechanism Forum is the South East Asia (SEA) Constituency of the Global Fund, one among the ten constituencies that form the Implementer Group of the Board of the Global Fund. SRCMF has been launched by the 11 member countries of GF SEA Constituency.
Focus	SRCMF's focus is on Cross-border areas of the member countries for supporting elimination of Malaria, Tuberculosis and HIV/AIDS in Cross-border areas by 2030.
Geographic Regions active in	SEA Region consisting of 11 member states (Bangladesh, Bhutan, Democratic People's Republic of Korea, India, Indonesia, Maldives, Myanmar, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Thailand, and Timor-Leste.)
Activities	Coordinating National Program implementation especially in the subnational and local levels , supporting M&E, resource mobilisation, advocacy, fostering partnership and sustainability of GF programs to accelerate and achieve the 2030 goals
Partners	WHO, RBM, UNOPS, GFATM, APLMA/APMEN CDC, Path, WHP, RTI ,
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Yes
Potential contribution	Yes
Contact person	Dr Jigmi Singay
Email	Jigmi2118@gmail.com
Web	https://www.theglobalfund.org/en/ https://www.theglobalfund.org/en/board/constituencies/
Type	NGO under Company Act 2013 Section 18 in India
Primary role	Coordination for Cross-border disease elimination Program activities
Secondary role	Besides Coordination and M&E, Resource mobilisation, advocacy, fostering partnership and sustainability of GF programs

26. Wellcome Trust	
About	a charitable foundation focused on health research based in London, United Kingdom.
Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support discovery research into life, health and wellbeing, and taking on three worldwide health challenges: mental health, infectious disease and climate. • Work with communities affected by escalating infectious diseases to bring those diseases under control and stop epidemics. • Funds discovery research into a broad range of disciplines, including infectious diseases. Insights and tools from this research will contribute to solving this health challenge, as well as increasing broader understanding of life, health and wellbeing. • Focus on the most affected communities, recognising that the overall burden of infectious diseases does not pose an equal threat to everyone's health.
Regions active in	Global
Activities / Whether active in cross-border Kala-azar control?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No
Partners	philanthropies, industry, multinational organizations, NGOs and governments.
Relevance to effective cross-border collaboration	Possible funding
Potential contribution	Funding
Contact person	Gordon Dougan, Director, Infectious Disease (Interim)
Email	
Web	https://wellcome.org/grant-funding
Type	International NGO
Primary role	Funding
Secondary role	Advocacy campaigns

Kala-azar partners engagement

Note:

1. The circle marked 'Government' includes both Central and State/Provincial Governments as well as health and non-health.
2. Yellow circles also include organizations where Head of Governments participate
3. The quadrant titled 'Collaborate' has circles in different sizes. The size indicates the importance, larger the circle, greater the importance
4. This does not include consortia, as they dissolve once the funding is over. However, the members of different consortia have been included as partners.

HIV

Countries in the region are characterized as having epidemics that are concentrated amongst specific most-at-risk-groups (MARPS) including sex workers, injecting drug users, men who have sex with men and, increasingly, migrants. Many migrate to other countries in search of work. Some migrants are HIV+ or become infected while working there. The issue therefore is proving access to diagnosis, treatment and follow-up. This is provided by the public healthcare system. It could not be ascertained as to which of these organizations are working in border districts.

Provided below is a list of partners in HIV.

1. AIDS Healthcare Foundation
2. Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN)
3. Australian Aid (AusAid)
4. B P Koirala Institute of Health Sciences, Nepal
5. Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF)
6. Clinton Foundation (CF)
7. FHI 360 (formerly Family Health International)
8. Foreign, Commonwealth & Development Office (formerly DfID)
9. German Aid (GTZ)
10. Global Alliance Vaccine Initiative
11. Global Fund
12. India HIV/AIDS Alliance
13. Institute of Epidemiology, Dhaka

14. International AIDS Society
15. International AIDS Vaccine Initiative (IAVI)
16. International centre for Diarrhoeal Disease Research, Bangladesh (ICDDR,B)
17. International HIV/AIDS Alliance
18. International Labour Organization (ILO)
19. National AIDS Research Institute
20. Population Services International
21. President's Emergency Plan for AIDS Relief (PEPFAR)
22. South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC)
23. Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (SIDA)
24. UNAIDS
25. United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)
26. United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF)
27. United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC)
28. United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA)
29. United States Agency for International Development (USAID)
30. World Bank

The collaboration and synergy between provincial and local governments in each of these countries is a crucial factor in ensuring that cross-border control of diseases is streamlined. The development of contact protocols as well maintenance of a contact database is an exercise that can be conducted with the help of local and provincial governments. Moreover, the establishment of clear isolation and quarantine protocol for multi-state responses along with an information-sharing network allows provincial and local governance to be in sync with each other's responses. In order to strengthen public health systems, governance needs to deliberate and develop protocols for sharing personnel across borders, including emergency credentials for physicians and health care workers and to systematize strategic national stockpile mechanisms across border communities.

Building clinical care capacity, coordinating epidemiologic investigations, legal implications, deployment of resources, human rights and civil liberties, and strengthening legal framework and laboratory capacity and capability are all domains that have to be managed by the local government while integrating with state, national and even international response plans.

In the eventuality of an outbreak, the initial response is local, but for the threat that is beyond local capacity, there has to be a framework that allows provincial and national agencies to integrate their response to assist local governments. The framework plan will allow each player to respond to the emergency within a predefined role.

Integration of these systems poses both jurisdictional challenges and geopolitical risks. The economy and polity, along with the physical features of neighbouring communities, states, and nations, must also be taken into consideration. The geographical topography like rivers, roads and mountains that separate one population or community from direct contact with the other is considered part of the geopolitical challenges, along with such activities as movement and communication from one national boundary to another.

The creation of a regulatory framework for testing, monitoring and tracking must follow a structured approach through prioritization of diseases for surveillance, also monitor and evaluate existing systems, and develop action plans to strengthen the systems. Surveillance of communicable diseases requires joint efforts between various stakeholders and governments in and between countries. At the country level, effective surveillance requires collaboration and coordination between the government in and between countries. Early warning systems can only function with coordinated efforts between and within countries.

The regional creation database and an insurance authority that addresses cross border deficits are of prime importance. The database must clearly define the jurisdiction over data while also facilitating cooperation among governments.

Tuberculosis

As tuberculosis spreads beyond borders with people movements, several interventions ensuring the continuity of care are essential, although difficult to put in place in the absence of well-defined agreements allowing data sharing and easy referral of patients to appropriate health facilities. It could not be ascertained who are working in border districts. Preventive, diagnostic, treatment and follow-up services are provided by public health programmes.

List of partners engaged in Tuberculosis.

1. Abt Assoc Inc
2. ALERT India
3. (Bagmati Welfare Society Network, Nepal (BWSN)
4. Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF)
5. Bangladesh Rehabilitation Assistance Committee (BRAC)
6. Catholic Health Association of India
7. Catholic Bishops' Conference of India-Coalition for AIDS and Related Diseases (CBCI-CARD)
8. Centre for Health Research and Innovation
9. Clinton Health Access Initiative
10. Foundation for Innovative New Diagnostics FIND
11. Foundation for Neglected Diseases Research
12. German TB and Leprosy Relief
13. Global Health Strategies
14. International Centre for Diarrhoeal Diseases Research, Bangladesh (ICDDRDB)
15. International TB Research Centre
16. International Union against TB & Lung Diseases (The UNION)
17. KNCV Tuberculosis Foundation
18. Kapilvastu Integrate Development Society , Nepal (KIDS)
19. Lepra India
20. Manipal Centre for Infectious Diseases
21. McGill International TB Centre
22. Médecins Sans Frontières, (MSF)
23. PATH
24. Population Services International (PSI) (SHOPS Plus project)
25. Resource Group for Education and Advocacy for Community Health (REACH)
26. Sustainable Development Goals Fund (SDG Fund)
27. South East Asia Regional Coordination Mechanism Forum (SRCMF)
28. STOP TB Partnership
29. TATA Institute of Social Sciences
30. TB Alert India
31. TB Alliance
32. TB Reach
33. The Global Fund
34. Tibetan Voluntary Health Association (TVHA)
35. United States Agency for International Development (USAID)
36. Vital Strategies
37. Voluntary Health Association of India
38. W. J. Clinton Foundation
39. World bank
40. World Health Partners
41. World Vision India
42. Zero TB Initiative

Conclusion

The collaboration and synergy between provincial and local governments in each of these countries is a crucial factor in ensuring that cross-border control of diseases is streamlined. The development of contact protocols as well maintenance of a contact database is an exercise that can be conducted with the help of local and provincial governments. Moreover, the establishment of clear isolation and quarantine protocol for multi-state responses along with an information-sharing network allows provincial and local governance to be in sync with each other's responses. In order to strengthen public health systems, governance needs to deliberate and develop protocols for sharing personnel across borders, including emergency credentials for physicians and health care workers and to systematize strategic national stockpile mechanisms across border communities.

Building clinical care capacity, coordinating epidemiologic investigations, legal implications, deployment of resources, human rights and civil liberties, and strengthening legal framework and laboratory capacity and capability are all domains that have to be managed by the local government while integrating with state, national and even international response plans.

In the eventuality of an outbreak, the initial response is local, but for the threat that is beyond local capacity, there has to be a framework that allows provincial and national agencies to integrate their response to assist local governments. The framework plan will allow each player to respond to the emergency within a predefined role.

Integration of these systems poses both jurisdictional challenges and geopolitical risks. The economy and polity, along with the physical features of neighbouring communities, states, and nations, must also be taken into consideration. The geographical topography like rivers, roads and mountains that separate one population or community from direct contact with the other is considered part of the geopolitical challenges, along with such activities as movement and communication from one national boundary to another.

The creation of a regulatory framework for testing, monitoring and tracking must adhere to principles of bioethics, address human rights and follow a structured approach through prioritization of diseases for surveillance, also monitor and evaluate existing systems, and develop action plans to strengthen the systems. Surveillance of communicable diseases requires joint efforts between various stakeholders and governments in and between countries. At the country level, effective surveillance requires collaboration and coordination between the government in and between countries. Early warning systems can only function with coordinated efforts between and within countries.

The regional creation database and an insurance authority that addresses cross border deficits are of prime importance. The database must clearly define the jurisdiction over data while also facilitating cooperation among governments.

IMPROVING COORDINATION AND COLLABORATION BETWEEN STAKEHOLDERS

There has been a bilateral cross border meeting between Bhutan and India, the previous being at Guwahati in November 2019 on cross border collaboration for malaria elimination. The meeting was attended by Ministry officials, Program Managers, state and district teams from all districts bordering India and Bhutan, and WHO officials. The report of the meeting indicates that in addition to updating on the situation of malaria at the country, state and district level, most of the time was spent on improving collaboration and coordination between the two countries and districts. Participants on both sides enumerated challenges and opportunities for collaboration. Several recommendations were made, mostly relating to sharing information, district-to-district coordination, joint review and joint planning. There should be optimal cooperation and coordination between Bodoland Territorial Council (BTC)/BTAD and state NVBDCP in Assam¹⁷¹.

In a recent virtual meeting on cross-border collaboration to eliminate Kala-azar and malaria along the India international border with Bangladesh, Bhutan and Nepal September 2021, besides sharing epidemiological updates, the participants called out the need to improve collaboration and coordination between countries. There is a need to strengthen information and data sharing through a formal or informal mechanism for joint and timely intervention. Though District level joint cross border action plans have been developed between India and Bhutan, they could not be implemented due to the COVID- 19 pandemic.

Bangladesh: Malaria transmission in Bangladesh has become highly focal; cases are confined mainly in areas near international borders with India. There is a substantial number of border crossing points in India-Bangladesh borders, some manned and others not. While suggesting next steps improve cross-border the need for high-level advocacy and cross-border Government meetings was stressed, among other issues. Improved cross border collaboration was suggested to develop a roadmap for cross-border collaboration and the need for a regional data sharing platform was also called out.

Nepal's presentation also stressed the need for effective and coordinated cross-border surveillance and response. It suggested strengthening the intra-country and bilateral agreements for collaborative interventions (joint planning and implementation at the border areas). Development of a cross-border collaboration mechanism that provides the enabling environment for malaria and Kala-azar elimination (including synchronized implementation) was identified as a priority area¹⁷².

Recommendations to synergize the work of various partners

The South-East Asia Region of the WHO has developed regional strategies for the elimination of malaria and Kala-azar, and so have all countries of the region, including Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar, and Nepal. The WHO has been providing technical assistance and has provided a platform for bringing together partners, experts, programme managers not only from the region but also across the regions for the exchange of ideas, experience, progress, problems, and suggesting possible solutions. At these convenings, countries are nudged to move ahead rapidly.

There are success stories in the region of eliminating, remaining malaria-free, and being certified as malaria-free – The Maldives and Sri Lanka. Remember that both of these countries are islands and do not have to struggle with problems associated with porous land borders and, in many instances, free movement across them.

Amongst the BBIMN countries, each country has been taking actions on its own, under the overall technical guidance from the WHO. As seen in the review, In Bhutan, from example, the number of indigenous and introduced cases were 12 in 2019; these increased to 43 in 2020. Bangladesh achieved Kala-azar elimination as a public health problem in 2016 and is presently preparing for the WHO validation process, but cross-border collaboration, one of the pre-conditions for WHO validation, is very weak. There is cross border movement of people, which is a significant risk factor in endemic border upazilas. Presently there are no health posts or screening services for Kala-azar. Neither are there any operational plans and activities implemented to address cross border risks for Kala-azar. No diagnosis and treatment services are provided to cross border migrants. In Nepal, indigenous cases have been comparatively less than imported cases since 2017. In 2019 Nepal reported 131 indigenous cases and 340 as imported cases.

These examples highlight the problems plaguing its cross-border control. Briefly, these are the absence of:

- i. Coordination between countries and between partners
- ii. Systems of communication and collaboration
- iii. Integrated and synchronized approach for implementation of interventions for case management, entomological surveillance, vector control, monitoring and evaluation
- iv. Cross border notification of diagnosed cases and their follow-up
- v. Joint framework for elimination across countries
- vi. Involvement of civil societies and local leadership across borders
- vii. Outbreaks reporting with effective surveillance and warning systems

It appears that not enough is being done to make an impact. The border districts need to increase coverage of the interventions, have tighter coordination and management of field operations, have better surveillance. The oversight of the activities needs to be strengthened at the district and at the state and national levels. There is a need to infuse urgency, intensity and quality in cross border commitment and actions.

Partners landscaping exercise has shown that in Kala-azar, none of them works specifically on cross border issues. However, there are some which are active in border districts. By virtue of being active in while in malaria, border malaria is recognized as a critical factor to eliminate malaria, hence there are partners with interest and expertise in tackling cross border malaria. There are also funding agencies assisting in controlling both these diseases in the region.

To address the deficiencies, it is important to improve coordination. For practical purposes, it is the act of bringing organisations and partners under an umbrella of a common goal to work together.

Recommendations to synergize partners' activities

The South-East Asia Region of the WHO has developed regional strategies for eliminating malaria and Kala-azar, and so have all countries of the region, including Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar, and Nepal. The WHO has been providing technical assistance and has provided a platform for bringing together partners, experts, and programme managers from the region and across the Regions for the exchange of ideas, experience, progress, problems, and suggesting possible solutions. At these convenings, countries are nudged to move ahead rapidly.

Inefficient coordination of activities has been recognised as a hurdle to success.

This study highlights various aspects of the need for cross border collaborations in the area of infectious disease control and containment. There are a number of solutions that have been presented, to be implemented in the short run, the medium term and the long run.

Disease control especially in border areas is not just about health care and access to medical care. It is also obvious that a large part of this study subliminally acknowledged the overlap in incidence of disease prevalence and poverty in the border districts studied. It can't merely be coincidental that most of the broader area along Nepal, Bhutan and Bangladesh is also miserably poor. This poverty is often neglected under the deluge of security concerns that must necessarily bother those looking at border areas. However what is loud and clear is that these are areas that lack in infrastructure, markets, access to education and inadequate consumption. The reason policy makers and strategic area experts should look into cross border disease control is that this would allow make way for prosperity in the otherwise sparse and inhospitable region.

Also of importance to the Insurance Regulator and the insurance sector is how important a segment is the population that lives in border areas. It is vulnerable to disease and to the vagaries of the political ups and downs in bordering nations. Here is an underserved segment that must now be given products that it would willingly pay for, given the uncertainties that it already faces. A flourishing insurance market and not just one that addresses healthcare, is what can be brought about very quickly in these risk prone areas. Especially if the coverage is broadened to make it applicable across borders. It is a necessary condition for growth in these areas and will result in economic development almost immediately if implemented well.

Short term plan:

To address the deficiencies, it is proposed to establish a sub-regional coordination unit to address coordination issues on cross-border malaria and Kala-azar. Coordination, for practical purposes, is the act of bringing organisations and partners under an umbrella of a common goal to work together.

Why is coordination with partners necessary?

The coordination helps partners in:

1. Knowing and understanding the work other partners perform
2. Ensuring effective use of resources
3. Forging common strategies
4. Adopting targeted approaches
5. Harmonising programmes and policies
6. Mobilising resources
7. Avoiding fragmentation of assistance
8. Reducing transition costs
9. Lessening the administrative burden on the countries
10. Minimising duplication

Given the urgency of cross border issues in malaria and the fact some countries have reached elimination targets in Kala-azar, in the immediate short-term, the following approach actions may be considered:

Bilateral engagements with countries

1. Engage with the central government and the through the country office the state and district level administration
2. Through the Ministry of Health keep Ministries of External Affairs, and Home / Internal security in the loop

3. Develop MoUs between countries, if not already available
4. Develop a one-year plan of action at the sub-national level in each country to address the immediate issues.
5. Have designated point persons in each district who should have the authority to coordinate on both sides of the border
6. Reach an agreement with the respective States/ districts on their roles and responsibilities, care to be taken to avoid overlaps.
7. Concentrate on local action, like active foci of transmission in the districts
8. Identify partners working in the states, especially the UN agencies, and their work and responsibilities.
9. In each border district, ascertain their needs and requirements, which are creating an obstacle in their functioning, and address them. These may be technical, managerial, or operational
10. Identify a point person in SEARO and country office for coordination
11. There should be an escalation plan or workflow that moves a pain-point issue up to a higher level. It minimises the time it takes to escalate decisions beyond their scope of authority. It improves coordination
12. Provisions should be made for coordination meetings at frequent and regular intervals.
13. One of the requirements for efficient coordination is to have a standardised solution for case surveillance, data sharing and data interpretation.

Medium Term (1-3 years)

Create a sub-regional coordinating unit at the SEA Regional Office for malaria and Kala-azar.

The hub will aim to improve coordination with partners and activities across five countries essential for cross border control of Kala-azar and malaria.

Objectives of the sub-regional unit would be to coordinate with partners and countries for smooth. The activities would be to ensure/facilitate:

1. Cross-border collaboration
2. Advocacy for prioritising cross border activities
3. Baseline situational analysis for the development of joint action plans
4. Development of joint action plans, in which each partner's role and responsibilities are defined and agreed upon.
5. Implementation of action plans
6. Standardisation and harmonisation of policies and practices
7. Sharing lessons learnt
8. Regular cross border meetings of district-level coordination committees
9. Organise an annual stakeholder forum involving ministries of health, WHO, other international organisations, nongovernmental organisations, development partners and researchers.
10. Release annual regional reports and newsletters.

For details, please see the Chapter on Framework for Sustainable Action Plan.

The activities of the unit would be guided by the operational framework developed by the SEA regional office.

It is expected that this sub-regional coordinating unit would facilitate coordination and dialogue among partners, communicating with stakeholders and coordinating cross border activities.

Long term plan: (more than three years)

Cross border coordination and collaboration is a politically sensitive, delicate and complex issue. It is also a cross-cutting topic that spans communicable diseases (including malaria, Kala-azar, other vector-borne diseases like Japanese encephalitis), health systems strengthening, especially in the border districts, and dealing with migrants (related to both documented and irregular) related issues, which are dealt in parts by different sections. In the absence of a point person or a unit dealing with cross-border as a subject, it falls between the cracks and fails to generate coordinated action. Success depends upon creating synergies and strengthening coordination / collaborating efforts between different partners, avoiding an overlap of activities.

Expand the scope of the sub-regional coordinating unit to cater to the needs of all cross-border issues of other diseases as well.

Role of the WHO

Since cross border issues involve sovereign states in the region, the regional office is in the best position to interact with the different countries. SEA Regional office has a presence in each country through its country offices, which work very closely with the national programmes. This facilitates dealing with the Governments of the countries: the WHO should provide space and staff, and other infrastructural facilities for running this coordinating unit.

The SEARO would continue to guide and assist, especially in:

1. Facilitate MOUs with countries to a coordinated regional action
2. Providing technical assistance
3. Catalysing resource generation
4. Encourage cost-benefit analysis of elimination programmes

LOOKING AHEAD: FRAMEWORK OF SUSTAINABLE ACTION PLAN

International borders that intersect endemic zones present the biggest challenge, to the success of elimination of diseases. Such cross-border endemic foci require special attention to ensure that programme activities are unified. It is vital that national programmes and the committees responsible for the oversight of progress towards elimination are aware and address such issues in their current planning and programmatic activities¹⁷³.

The border areas are usually some of the most remote areas and because of challenging terrain are difficult to reach, and more so if there is an ongoing civil unrest. This issue of access to healthcare system has been identified as one of the emerging challenges that needs to be addressed. Civil unrest or conflict prevents access to populations through disruption of health services and migration, access to remote populations in challenging geographic settings and vulnerable groups in elimination programmes¹⁷⁴. Health services in the border districts are poor and inadequate especially in peripheral areas. Communicable diseases pose major challenges in border areas as they require synchronization of intervention measures, a sensitive surveillance system, and sharing information across the border.

The migrant populations are another major factor in cross-border situations and always need to be accounted for in cross-border disease elimination programmes. The respective Governments and their national disease programmes have recognized these issues and have included them in their strategy documents and plans. The health of migrants, their access to preventive, diagnostic, curative, and follow-up services irrespective of their nationality, and that the treatment is continued when they go back to their country, is a major issue that needs to be addressed.

For more than two decades, efforts have been made in the SEA Region to tackle malaria, Kala-azar, tuberculosis and HIV along international borders and through cross-border collaboration. Though Member countries have committed to address malaria and Kala-azar along international border by signing/endorsing ministerial declarations, several bilateral and international meetings have been conducted. But success has been limited.

Some of the challenges identified have been known and stressed since the late 1990s. These include lack of priority towards commitments for cross-border collaboration and sufficient and sustained resources for cross-border component, inadequate situation analysis to inform comprehensive planning and action as well as irregular follow-up and coordination support and absence of new and/or minimal use of existing platforms for information sharing and harmonization of efforts¹⁷⁵. The level of commitments on all sides, and the follow-up actions have been inadequate. Multi-sectoral and multi-partner involvement is insufficient. Utilization of existing inter-country mechanisms is weak. There has been a mismatch between the expectations and the capacity of the health systems.

Lessons from other countries in controlling / eliminating other diseases through successful cross border collaborations indicate that for successful cross-border collaboration. Briefly, the five essential ingredients are:

1. Link the cross-border programme to higher political level. Achieve political commitment and oversight at the highest possible/ necessary level in each affected country.
2. Involve appropriate government departments. An international border is a political boundary between countries and a sensitive area.

3. Coordinate activities between multiple partners. As several partners are involved in the programme, coordination among them becomes critical. This includes timely data sharing, referral linkages, and reporting between countries. Coordination is best done by a neutral party to foster successful cross-border collaboration. A neutral party is one that does not take sides at any time in the controversies of a political, racial, religious or ideological nature. Being neutral is a means to an end, it is not an end by itself. A neutral party is often independent and enjoys the confidence and trust of all.
4. Involve WHO. It has a critical role in cross-border collaboration, because of its convening power and IHR mandate.
5. Ensure supplies (manpower, money and material) for management of diseases and access (physical and to health services) to all - irrespective of nationality.

A notable example of successful cross border collaboration between Bangladesh, Bhutan, India Myanmar and Nepal has been for polio elimination, when cross-border vaccination posts were established on international border between India and these countries. Now when the countries have inched closer to elimination targets for malaria and Kala-azar, and momentum is gaining to eliminate Tuberculosis and HIV as public health problems, this collaboration is more important than ever before.

Keeping in mind the lessons learnt from the region and experience from some successful cross-border disease control programme, an action plan is proposed. Presently there is no cross-border initiative which brings all the five countries i.e. Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar and Nepal on a common platform. A new sub-regional initiative is proposed.

Why a sub-Regional approach is better than a Regional one

Sub-regional networking has emerged as an important trend in global public health because such cooperation is transnational but organized and governed by member countries and directly addresses their shared priorities. Sub-regional networks are manifestations of the need to develop networks capable of spanning borders while maintaining relative managerial simplicity. This type of transnational cooperation can help to ensure a coordinated and expedited response to emerging public health threats. The unique structure of sub-regional networks gives them autonomy to more nimbly establish a bottom-up agenda to address shared priorities. They provide representatives from member countries with more opportunities to closely interact with their peers from other member countries. This includes interactions of local counterparts at cross-border sties. These interactions build trust, mutual respect and transparency among country members. (Table 1).

The sub-regional networks provide important strategic advantages. One, is the mutual respect and trust among members that develops over the years. Such relationships can mean the difference between success and failure. Second is to sustaining cooperation even if external support declines. Third is the predominantly horizontal orientation of the sub-regional cooperation and the “owner-driven” nature of its technical agenda. Moreover, International donors are more likely to fund approaches that involve a group of countries rather than a single country for disease elimination¹⁷⁶.

Sustainability framework encompasses a number of “sustainability-enabling factors” strategic attributes (governance, relationships, orientation, alignments, and priorities) and tactical achievements (related to infrastructure, activities, and visibility), and to orient their planning for future sustainability.

Table 1: Comparison of Characteristics of Regional and Sub-Regional Networks

Characteristics	Regional Networks	Sub-regional Networks
Organization	Large, multilateral, long-standing	Small, self-organized, recent
Agenda	Top-down: driven by the full set of Member States	Bottom-up: driven by a small number of member countries
Governance	Broadly self-governed: decisions made by consensus of all Member States at regional and global levels (World Health Assembly)	Narrowly self-governed: decisions made by consensus of a small number of member countries
	Partially representative executive board: includes representation from a small rotating subset of Member States	Fully representative executive board: includes representation from every member country
Legal basis	Constitution agreed upon by Member States IHR is a legally-binding treaty	Typically, “soft,” non-binding legal tools -- Memorandum of Understanding or other network-designed agreement
Affiliation	Large number of members: based on geography	Small number of members: based on natural affiliations, usually sharing borders

Efforts for prevention and control of cross-border diseases can be better coordinated and managed if border areas are considered as single epidemiologic block. Solutions have to be tailored according to the local problems. No one size fits all. This region will need to design and implement a strategy tailored for high level of human mobility between neighbouring countries. Global experience has shown that a regional/sub-regional approaches yield better results than country-specific focus.

International donors are more likely to fund approaches that involve a group of countries rather than a single country for disease elimination.

Action Plan

Aim: The aim of the action plan is to re-energize the activities for control of priority communicable diseases and put them on fast track

Objectives:

1. To move up on the political agenda cross border control of priority communicable diseases, which is key to success
2. To improve coordination between partners
3. To provide technical assistance to the countries to help them address specific problems

Phased approach:

1. In the first phase the focus will be on malaria and Kala-azar, as countries of the sub-region have already made significant progress in achieving the elimination targets and a push to cover the last mile is required. Both the diseases have figured in multiple agreements on cross-border elimination
2. In phase II Tuberculosis and HIV will be addressed. This would build upon the foundations already laid during the first phase.

This document addresses Phase I.

Action Plan as sub-regional initiative

A four-arm sub-regional initiative is suggested. It would consist of a:

1. Political arm
2. Coordination arm
3. Technical arm
4. Implementation arm

Political Arm

The need for political arm?

1. Adds gravitas to the issue
2. Provide urgency, energy, thrust, momentum to the cross border collaboration
3. Decisions taken at the highest political level carry more weight and more likely to be implemented
4. The support from other Ministries and Departments would be a given
5. Each country can derive political mileage on reaching elimination targets

Why should PMs lead this initiative?

Achieving political commitment is more than generating attention to the diseases or getting it onto a government agenda.

1. The highest level of political oversight ensures three types of commitments:
2. institutional commitment (the conversion of rhetorical commitment into substantive policy infrastructure including institutions responsible for coordinating actions, the adoption of enabling legislation, policies and policy instruments commensurate with the severity of the problem, and the commitment of mid-level bureaucrats responsible for coordinating action),
3. operational commitment (on-the-ground actions including the sustained allocation of human, technical and financial resources, the effective coordination of all actors involved along national to subnational implementation pathways and the commitment of street-level managers and implementation teams), and
4. system-wide commitment (involving all actors operating within health system including communities, families and individual citizens. When achieved, system-wide commitment can create a powerful reinforcing feedback-loop that institutionalises and sustains long-term policy and programme responses).
5. A high level oversight can be a powerful stimulus to action and sets the scene for improved sectoral collaboration., and is critical for ensuring that collaboration efforts are adequately resourced and are designed to be inclusive and responsive.
6. By involving the PMs it is expected that the government will consider cross border collaboration a priority for the disease programmes
7. The level of political commitment also affects the staffing of elimination programmes programs. If high-ranking officials truly understand the critical role for cross-border collaboration they will make certain that the best people in the country are assigned to direct major programs. Also when it is known that the PM would review the programme, every one puts in their best. This also helps to attract the best people because unless they are confident that they have strong political support, the best program managers tend to move toward other assignments.
8. The level of political commitment also influences the amount of financial resources available to address the issue. If cross-border collaboration is recognized as a crisis, then the response will be different than if it is considered to be just one more aspect of a health problem.

Terms of Reference to PM level body:

1. To review progress towards elimination in each country

2. Assess progress, barriers and constraints in cross-border collaboration, and suggest course correction, if needed
3. Ensure translation of political decisions into policy, and policy into action
4. Remove impediments to access to healthcare by migrants
5. Ensure availability of resources (manpower, money, and material – drugs, diagnostics, insecticides, and personal protectives)

Why should this initiative be led by India?

1. India is the only country which shares border with the other four countries.
2. India can assume leadership role in elimination efforts and improving access to health care services to migrants in India.
3. India has the largest burden of the four diseases amongst the five countries. Leadership of India ensure its participation. There is a disease burden gradient between India and its neighbours. There is large movement of people across borders,
4. India has substantial scientific skills, expertise, and infrastructure to provide technical leadership.
5. Success in India is critical for success of South East Asia region.

Why would India be interested to lead this initiative?

1. India's vision for the Region is SAGAR – Security to All and Growth for All – a reflection of its policy of inclusiveness.
2. It also has a Neighbourhood First' Policy which has sought to develop better relations with country's neighbours.
3. It provides India leadership role in the region.
4. India's Act East Policy, launched in 2014, is based on 4Cs – Culture. Commerce. Connectivity and Capacity building. It begins with Myanmar as it is India's link to South East Asia.
5. India has taking steps to improve ties and cooperation with Myanmar. This will be another opportunity. It has been helping Myanmar build institutional capacity and develop areas such as information technology, A number of projects have been launched, the most important being the Kaladam Multi-Modal transport project which will connect Kolkata with Sittwe port and the India-Myanmar-Thailand trilateral highway.

Some of the MoUs signed in Healthcare Sector between India and Myanmar include:

- i. MoU for cooperation in Medical Products Regulation between the Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO), Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, of India and Food and Drugs Administration (FDA), Ministry of Health and Sports of Myanmar, and
 - ii. MoU for cooperation in the field of Health and Medicine between the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare of the Government of the Republic of India and the Ministry of Health and Sports of Myanmar.
 - iii. MoU for cooperation in the field of Health Research between Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR), India and Department of Medical Research (DMR), Myanmar
6. India has launched an ambitious Border Area Development Programme. The Department of Border Management, Ministry of Home Affairs is implementing it. The programme covers all the villages which are located within 0-10 km distance of the International Border. BADP is to meet special developmental needs and well being of people living in the remote and inaccessible areas situated near the international borders, and to provide essential infrastructure through convergence of the Central/State /UT/BADP/Local schemes and participatory approach. The projects undertaken under the BADP relate to the construction of roads, bridges, drinking water supply, health, agriculture and allied activities, social sector activities such as creation of social infrastructure, capacity building and skill development, and construction of toilets particularly for women, education, sports activities, promotion of rural tourism/border tourism, etc. In Health sector the funds would be utilized for construction of Primary Health Centre buildings, medical equipment, mobile dispensaries / ambulances, houses for doctors and para-medics.

What does this platform offer to other countries?

All the countries stand to gain through this collaboration in putting together infrastructure needed to meet the pre-conditions of WHO to certify countries free of specific diseases. Examples have shown that it cross-border control and elimination of communicable diseases is a profitable investment due to the ability for it to pay itself with future reductions in spending and generate better economic returns. Given the inter-connectedness of countries, increased cooperation in cross-border health will allow the benefits to flow into other areas which remain tense and divisive. Cross-border health is an effective soft power tool for states to pursue their economic interests and advance international relations. Transborder spread of infection in the region can cause socio-political crises as well as strain diplomatic relations. Building a robust cross-border response is essential to security and peace in the region. Moreover, the South Asian region is disproportionately affected by pandemics, natural disasters and humanitarian crises. Hence, leadership must step up to collaboration across borders. Experience dictates that aid is dependent on partnerships and trust across the border, as shown by the success of the polio programme. Cross-border cooperation has a net benefit for countries.

Structure of Political arm

1. It will be a high level political body headed by the Indian Prime Minister and Prime Ministers of other countries as members, may be called Board
2. Since cross-border is a sensitive issue participation of Ministry of External Affairs, Home Affairs/Internal Security, Finance, and Health is essential. Others can be added as and when required.
3. The invitees to the summit meetings would also include experts, members for the Technical and the coordinating arms, UN agencies involved in cross-border activities related to health and migrants, and others as required.

SUMMIT

Possible name for the Political arm

This may be called 'SEEMANT'. This is a Sanskrit word meaning end of the boundary. This acronym stands for

Summit to

Expedite

Elimination of

Malaria and

Kala-azar within

National and across

Trans-national borders

Can any of the functions of the Political arm be performed by the Regional Committee of SEARO/WHO?

SEARO's Regional Committee: It is the WHO's governing body in the Region. It is comprised of representatives from the Region's all the 11 Member States. The Regional Committee formulates policies, provides oversight for regional programmes, hears progress reports, and considers, revises and endorses new initiatives. It adopts resolutions and makes decisions that guide the work of the Regional Office and country offices. Its jurisdiction is limited to health, while the cross border control of diseases involves other non-health sectors as well, on which the Regional Committee would have very little or no influence.

Can any of the existing initiatives facilitate the functioning of the political arm?

It would be ideal to house the political arm in one of the existing structures which has all the five countries (BBIMN). Examples of some existing platforms include:

ASEAN: Association of Southeast Asian Nations, is a political and economic union of 10 member countries in South East Asia, it promotes inter-governmental cooperation and facilitates and facilitates economic, political, security, military, educational and socio-cultural integration between its members and other countries in Asia. ASEAN's primary objective is to accelerate economic growth and through that social progress and cultural development. The 10 members include Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam. India became a sectoral dialogue partner of ASEAN in 1992, and full dialogue partner in 1995. India also became a member of the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF) in 1996. Amongst the five countries only Myanmar is a member

SAARC: South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC) was established in 1985 Among others, includes Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Nepal, but not Myanmar and the South Asian Free Trade Area (SAFTA) agreement came into force in 2006. Despite these mechanisms, regional cooperation has remained relatively low. Both economic and non-economic factors are responsible for this situation. Factors that range from tariff and non-tariff barriers to physical connectivity to asymmetric power relations and security concerns have served as obstacles to achieve regional cooperation in South Asia. Economic decisions rest on state actors who lack the momentum in stimulating regional economic activity. In addition, South Asian states tend to look inwards vis-à-vis each other due to the asymmetric nature of interstate relations. This has led South Asian states to prioritize issues of high politics rather than collective socio-economic development.

BBINS: The Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Nepal (BBIN) sub-regional initiative is envisioned to improve economic cooperation and connectivity among the four South Asian countries. It meets through official representation of member states to formulate, implement and review quadrilateral agreements across areas such as water resources management, connectivity of power, transport, and infrastructure. It emphasizes the importance of trade, economic cooperation and people-to-people contact, through enhanced regional connectivity, including through facilitation of regional cross-border road transport. The group has not been very active.

East Asia Summit: The East Asia Summit (EAS) is the Indo-Pacific's premier forum for strategic dialogue. It is the only leader-led forum at which all key partners meet to discuss political, security and economic challenges facing the Indo-Pacific, and has an important role to play in advancing closer regional cooperation. The EAS has 18 members - the ten ASEAN countries (Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, Vietnam) along with Australia, China, India, Japan, New Zealand, the Republic of Korea, Russia and the United States.

Of the five target countries only India and Myanmar are members.

South Asia sub-Regional Economic Cooperation (SASEC): brings together Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Maldives, Myanmar, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. The member countries share common aspirations of economic growth, economic diversification, inclusive growth and sustainability, and energy access and security. Health is not a part of its mandate.

BIMSTEC: The Bay of Bengal Initiative for Multi-Sectoral Technical and Economic Cooperation (BIMSTEC) is an international organisation of seven members: Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Myanmar and Thailand. This sub-regional organization came into being on 6 June 1997. Unlike many other regional groupings, BIMSTEC is a sector-driven cooperative organization. Among its sectors is public health. Its Permanent Secretariat is in Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Some of the existing initiatives

Why BIMSTEC?

Cross border collaboration is not only important between countries who share land border with India, but is also important between Thailand and Myanmar; Bangladesh and Myanmar, and Sri Lanka and India need to work together to maintain Sri Lanka's Malaria free status. BIMSTEC is also India's preferred vehicle of co-operation between countries of the region.

1. Cross border issues are addressed more effectively when countries which share common borders are brought together as a group. If one of them lags behind it affects the progress of the entire group. The countries become accountable to each other. These countries share not only the geographical milieu but the cultural milieu as well.
2. One another example of using BIMSTEC platform is that all countries in this group are member countries of SEA region of the WHO. SAARC has Afghanistan and Pakistan (which are members of The WHO Regional Office for the Eastern Mediterranean); ASEAN has Br.

The political arm is a high-level political body, with Prime Ministers or equivalent as members. It would be chaired by the Indian Prime Minister and a rotating Co-chair. It would have a high level representation from the Ministries of External Affairs, Home Affairs/ Internal Security, Finance, and Health from each country. The PM meeting will take place annually.

A bi-annual meeting of the Health Ministers of the countries is also proposed. To take stock of the progress being made. Identify the bottle-necks and possible solutions, and provide oversight.

Sub-regional Technical Arm

The second component is a technical arm, comprising of experts, which will provide technical guidance on all aspects of cross-border control of diseases. This must be geared towards addressing the challenges to elimination that have been prioritized by member states and may benefit from including other regional stakeholders.

The Technical arm would have development partners, philanthropic organizations, local country health programmes, relevant, government and Non-government organizations, independent experts, research and academic bodies. It would be a network of stakeholders and independent experts.

2. Technical Arm

- It's a network of stakeholders + Independent experts (**PLUG-IN**)
 - Partners (development) and Philanthropies
 - Local country Programmes
 - Universities and other R&D Institutes
 - Governments and Non-Govt Organizations
 - Independent Experts / UN Agencies
 - Network
- Partner mapping exercise identified partners and their strengths
- To provide technical guidance on all aspects of cross-border control of diseases
- May have sub-Committees on specific areas like surveillance
- WHO SEARO is already doing this, should continue

Coordinating arm

The third component is the coordinating arm. It is proposed to establish a coordination arm to address coordination issues on cross-border malaria and Kala-azar. Coordination, for practical purposes, is the act of bringing organizations and partners under an umbrella of a common goal to work together.

Why is coordination with partners necessary?

The coordination helps partners in:

1. Knowing and understanding the work other partners perform
2. Ensuring effective use of resources
3. Forging common strategies
4. Adopting targeted approaches
5. Harmonizing programmes and policies
6. Mobilizing resources
7. Avoiding fragmentation of assistance
8. Reducing transition costs
9. Lessening administrative burden on the countries
10. Minimizing duplication

It is proposed that the coordination be done by WHO SEA Regional office.

Why WHO?

The WHO's constitution (Article 2) provides it the mandate to be a directing and coordination agency in international health and to establish and maintain effective collaboration with other partners in health. It has played a critical role in past in bringing partners together on important health issues.

The SEA Regional office has led the regional response to cross border control of diseases, and accords high priority to building strategic partnerships with all stakeholders. Its link with member countries of the region and with its convening power is in a distinct position to coordinate between countries and with various partners involved.

The WHO has a key role in supporting cross-border control of Kala-azar and malaria and to ensure success of their elimination strategy and action plans. This WHO, therefore, is best suited to house this hub.

Why in SEARO?

Since cross border issues involve sovereign states in the region, the Regional office is in a best position to interact with the different countries. SEA Regional office has presence in each country through its Country offices, which work very closely with the National Programmes. This facilitates dealing with the Governments of the countries. SEARO has been active in the cross-border activities since mid 1990s and has 'hands-on' experience on the subject.

The SEARO would continue to guide and assist especially in facilitating MOUs with countries, providing technical assistance, and catalysing resource generation.

Aim: to improve coordination, both with partners, and of activities across five countries essential for cross border control of Kala-azar and malaria.

Objectives :

1. Coordination with partners and countries
2. Provide support to
 - a. strengthen national monitoring and evaluation systems,
 - b. generate high quality national data
 - c. improve exchanges of information across borders.
3. Establish a database on:
 - a. epidemiology
 - b. resistance,
 - c. entomology,
 - d. policies and programme implementation for
 - i. containment,
 - ii. control and
 - iii. elimination,
4. Allow access to the data to countries and partners.

The activities would be to ensure / facilitate:

1. Cross-border collaboration
2. Advocacy for prioritizing cross border activities
3. Baseline situational analysis for development of joint action plans
4. Development of joint action plans
5. Implementation of action plans

6. Standardization and harmonization of policies and practices
7. Monitoring and evaluation, including
 - a. Access to diagnosis and treatment
 - b. Coverage of personal protection and vector control measures
 - c. Coverage of migrants and mobile populations
8. Mapping of patterns of human mobility
9. An effective communication system
10. Complete mapping of intervention coverages
11. Develop a regional data-base to give an overview of available information for activities, policies, funding and data on drug efficacy.
12. Sharing of lessons learnt
13. Advocacy for country level funding
14. Regular cross border meetings
15. Organize an annual stakeholder forum involving ministries of health, WHO, other international organizations, nongovernmental organizations, development partners and researchers.
16. Release annual regional reports and newsletters.

Though the SEA Regional office appears the logical choice to anchor the coordinating role, another contender for this role is emerging, the South East Asia Regional Coordination Mechanism Forum (SRCMF)

South East Asia Regional Coordination Mechanism Forum

The South East Asia (SEA) Constituency of the Global Fund is among the ten constituencies that form the Implementer Group of the Board of the Global Fund. The SEA constituency provides a platform to governments, the private sector, and people infected and affected by HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, and malaria, from 11 countries in the region, to voice their concerns to the Global Fund Board. The need for better coordination between the SEA constituency and other constituencies at regional level led to the formation of the South East Asia Regional Coordination Mechanism Forum (SRCMF). In July 2021, SRCMF organized its 4th meeting to accelerate malaria elimination program in the region.

During the meeting the importance of leadership, multilateral, and bilateral partnerships to support national malaria programs tackling border malaria was highlighted. The members highlighted the need for establishment of coordinating mechanisms between various partners in the region and malaria programs at national and sub-national level to maximize input and resource allocation. The members also suggested that SRCMF, along with APLMA can effectively take up this role of bringing together partners and national programs of the region for cross border collaboration. In the past, the WHO's SEA Regional Office has helped organize bi-annual meetings of the SEA Constituency of the Global Fund.

SRCMF is emerging as a strong contender for taking up the role of coordination among its members for cross border control of Malaria, Kala-azar, HIV and Tuberculosis. The SEARO would have to double up its efforts if retain the coordination function, which it is so suitably placed to perform.

Role of the WHO

1. Facilitate MOUs with countries to facilitate Coordinating regional action
2. Providing technical assistance
3. Catalysing resource generation

The activities of the coordinating arm would be guided by the operational frame work developed by the SEA regional office. Increased support will be given to promote quality of data as well as the comparability of data reported form. The quality of the action taken based on the data is as important

as the data itself. Therefore, assistance will also be given for trainings, and use of technology to improve staff ability to use the data for planning and directing activities.

Implementation

This is the fourth arm. The implementation of plans and strategies will have to be done by respective countries. Since all the activities will be implemented through the state and local health, its strengthening is pivotal to the success of the any programme. Countries should engage closely with WHO and other technical partners to bolster the performance of all components of the health system at the national and subnational level to ensure that investments in human resources, infrastructure, surveillance and supply chain systems for malaria elimination also contribute to broader public health programmes and Universal Health Care goals. Each country would need to develop monitoring of progress and periodic evaluation plan.

Cross border collaboration and coordination of activities are critical to reach and maintain elimination targets. With strong political leadership, meaningful partnerships and the necessary financial commitments, will immensely assist these efforts. It is hoped that this framework for an action plan will ignite a discussion to take for taking concrete steps to provide a momentum to cross-border control of priority communicable diseases in the sub-region of Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Myanmar and Nepal^{177 178 179 180}.

ANNEX 1

List of persons consulted

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ANNEX 2

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